

GREENGAGE

ENGAGING CITIZENS - MOBILIZING TECHNOLOGY - DELIVERING GREEN DEAL

GREENGAGE CO Academy Roadmap

Work Package 3, Deliverable D3.3

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List of Acronyms

AIT	Austrian Institute of Technology (AIT)
BCC	Bristol City Council
Borghini	I Borghini piu Belli D'Italia
BUAS	Breda University of Applied Sciences
CO	Citizen Observatory
COs	Citizen Observatories
CObs	Citizen Observers
EBLN	The East Bristol Liveable Neighbourhood
EU	European Union
GA	Grant Agreement
IA	Innovation Action
IAB	Innovation Action Board
KPI	Key Performance Indicator
KWMC	Knowle West Media Centre
PNB	Province of North Brabant
PNRR	National Recovery and Resilience Plan
PST	Pilot Support Team
UWE	University of the West of England

Glossary

<p>Active intermediation</p>	<p>GREENGAGE seeks to intermediate between public authorities and citizens, green initiatives, researchers, tech providers and other potential stakeholders of Observatories. Mediating here is the process of enabling authorities of urban policy making to democratically respond to a community’s understanding of the local needs for effective and sustainable innovation. This includes the navigation of legal and regulatory requirements, the negotiation of appropriate institutional arrangements, the mobilisation of resources and the facilitation of active participation of citizens in decision-making processes of urban planning. GREENGAGE Observatories will enable the active dialogue between authorities and communities by co-designed observation and analysis of real-world environments. Through active intermediation with the Pilot’s situations, GREENGAGE Observatories will shape policy innovation in five different contexts of urban planning. Through active intermediation coordinators of the GREENGAGE Observatories aim to meet the needs of communities and serve the improvement of their well-being through the process and its outcomes (cf. May & Perry, 2017, p. 24).</p>
<p>Citizen Observatory</p>	<p>According to EU project WeObserve, “Citizen Observatories (COs) are community-based environmental monitoring and information systems, that invite individuals to share observations, typically via mobile phone or the web. Throughout these activities citizens become able to participate in environmental management/local governance.” [Reference: D2.1 - GREENGAGE Methodological Framework]. In GREENGAGE, CO is a place like a Living Lab (a laboratory in a real context, putting stakeholders at the centre of the process) for collective learning that exploits the opportunity of using sensors and the use of Earth observation technology where citizens collect data and are empowered by the information generated from these data to improve environmental management towards an innovative governance of the territory. In this deliverable, a case is made to instead call them GREENGAGE Observatories (GOs)</p>
<p>Citizen Science</p>	<p>“In Citizen Science, a broad network of people collaborates. Participants provide experimental data and facilities for researchers, raise new questions and co-create a new scientific culture. While they add value, volunteers acquire new learning and skills and gain a deeper understanding of the scientific work in appealing ways. As a result of this open, networked and transdisciplinary scenario, science-society-policy interactions are improved, leading in turn to a more democratic research, based on evidence and informed decision-making” (Socientize consortium, 2014, p. 10).</p>
<p>Collaborative Environment (CE)</p>	<p>The Collaborative Environment platform acts as the front-end visualisation of Knowledge Assets and tools that help organise the co-creation of thematic co-explorations. The co-production processes modelled by the CE hyperlinks the resources, e.g., data chart or geospatial visualization, from the tasks where they were generated.</p>
<p>Communities of Interest (Col)</p>	<p>Cols are characterized by their shared interest in the framing of and responding to a problem of common concern. Cols often are more temporary than CoPs and bring together stakeholders from different CoPs and/or spatial communities in the context of a specific project and dissolve after the project has ended (Fischer, 2001, p. 4)2.</p>

Communities of Practice (CoP)	CoPs consist of practitioners who work as a community in a certain domain undertaking similar work, such as researchers, Citizen Observers, urban planners (Fischer, 2001, p. 3) ³ who deepen their knowledge and expertise in this area by interacting on an ongoing basis.’ (Wenger et al., 2002, p. 4).
Coordinators of GREENGAGE Observatories	Coordinators of GREENGAGE Observatories are those participants that deliver the Innovation Action (IA). To demonstrate innovation, these coordinators have to ensure that the urban challenges are communicated as defined by top-down perspectives (e.g., EU policies, academic expertise). Therefore, they regulate their co-examination by providing methodologies, communication platforms, templates, checklists, surveys, consent forms and frameworks for specification. These coordinators can be the local planning agents but can expand to include involved Observers.
Experiments	Within use cases, experiments are data-based co-production processes pursuing a co-created objective that are situated in GREENGAGE Observatories to drive policy innovations or other local interventions, e.g., campaigns, public debates, exhibitions, urbanistic demonstrations or public services.
GREENGAGE Academy	The GREENGAGE Academy hosts the emerging GREENGAGE Community of Practise and is the central platform for sharing understandings of the process of developing GREENGAGE COs. As such, the Academy serves as the central interaction platform between CO coordinators, Citizen Observers and other participants of COs. The Academy acts as a knowledge base and toolbox around the setting up and effective coordination of citizen observatories. The Academy stores and indexes training resources, MOOCs, success stories, findings and best practises collected from the four GREENGAGE pilots as well as generated or adapted to guide the setting up of the pilots.
GREENGAGE Citizen Observatory Methodological Framework	The GREENGAGE Citizen Observatory Methodological Framework suggests core concepts, processes and guidelines on how to develop Observatories in GREENGAGE in ways that are ethical, democratic and responsive to common urban challenges and their situational manifestations in GREENGAGE’s five Pilots.
GREEN Engine	The GREEN Engine consists of the Collaborative Environment, the GREENGAGE Toolbox and the GO knowledge assets, also known as GO Enablers. The GREEN Engine is the mechanism that drives co-creation of evidence-based interventions (such as campaigns among others) based on the provided tools and knowledge assets.
GREENGAGE Observatories	See Citizen Observatories. An update of the term Citizen Observatory to comply with equity, diversity, and inclusion frameworks, as some of the participants and target groups of these associations do not necessarily possess citizenship.
GREENGAGE Toolbox	The GREENGAGE Toolbox is the main stack of data processing and management tools. It comprises the set of tools within the “Data crowdsourcing and capture” and the “Data analysis and insights generation” layers of the GREEN Engine. Some of the tools included are MindView, MODE and HOPU apps, GREENGAGE app, Urban TEP/VISAT, Data Quality and Structure Dashboards, DIGITWIN, DataHub, Superset, Druid or NiFi.
Innovation Action	Horizon Europe Innovation Action projects are "primarily consisting of activities directly aiming at producing plans and arrangements or designs for new, altered or improved products, processes or services. For this purpose, they may include prototyping, testing, demonstrating, piloting, large-scale product validation and market replication. [...] Projects may include limited research and development

	activities” (EU HORIZON 2020). For GREENGAGE Observatories this means participatory research for innovation is not the focus but a means for understanding the GREENGAGE Innovation Action collectively.
Interventions	Interventions are community-led and/or government-led actions performed with the aim to improve the socio-political context of a location based on situated understandings of the conditions that need to be addressed to generate societal impact as well as the possibilities for improvements.
Knowledge Assets	A collection of templates, documents, references, and information files that facilitate an understanding of co-creation, and Observatories. The Assets are part of the Knowledge Base and have to be combined with the Toolbox to fully facilitate the setting up of Observatories. See also ‘Observatory Enablers’.
Knowledge Base	The Knowledge Base is the co-created, curated, organised, and published assembly of GREENGAGE Knowledge Assets that enable meaningful participation by users in co-creating GREENGAGE Observatories and also in delivering the Green New Deal beyond GREENGAGE. This base is published on the website.
Living Labs	According to the European Network of Living Labs, “Living Labs (LLs) are open innovation ecosystems in real-life environments using iterative feedback processes throughout a lifecycle approach of an innovation to create sustainable impact. They focus on co-creation, rapid prototyping & testing and scaling-up innovations & businesses, providing (different types of) joint-value to the involved stakeholders.”
Local Planning Agent(s)	See ‘Pilot Owners’. An update of the term Pilot Owners, as the owners of the pilot can be members of Observatories themselves. In the current phases (PREPARING and PILOTING), only public authorities and advisory institutions are involved, hence the more accurate renaming.
Marginalized groups	“Different groups of people within a given culture, context and history at risk of being subjected to multiple discrimination due to the interplay of different personal characteristics or grounds, such as sex, gender, age, ethnicity, religion or belief, health status, disability, sexual orientation, gender identity, education or income, or living in various geographic localities” (European Institute of Gender Equality).
Observatory Enablers	Enablers are the set of co-produced knowledge assets (including results of a thematic co-explorations) that enable participants of GREENGAGE Observatories to co-deliver meaningful thematic co-explorations and ensure exploitable outcomes with the purpose to inform situated experiments and policy innovations. GREENGAGE Enablers are published in the GREENGAGE Academy together with training materials, videos, deliverables, publications or newsletters. See also ‘Knowledge Assets’.
Observatory Participant Journey	The Observatory Participants Journey depicts the generic process of newcomers or people that are already participating in GREENGAGE Observatories becoming GREENGAGE Observers, then contributing to thematic co-explorations (in response to urban challenges as they are understood in different locations).
Participants of the Observatories	The participants include the pilot owners, local planning agents, members of the PSTs, the actual observers and other stakeholders that are actively contributing to the realization of Observatories. Beyond human actors we see technologies and knowledge assets as actively shaping Observatories. A broader

	understanding of participants is useful for addressing the existing power relations that shape open innovation ecosystems such as GREENGAGE Observatories and to reflect on the use of technologies and knowledge assets that should serve localized social-ecological change, not market interests.
Participant Onboarding	Situational onboarding conceptualises the GREENGAGE engagement methodology. Situational onboarding is sensitive to context, time, capacities and other variables that impact on the ability of citizens to actively participate in Observatories. It seeks to meet people where they are, be inclusive, and extend and diversify the contributions of participants at different stages of the co-creation process. The methodology suggests reflexive questions as a tool for develop engagement strategies with the different pilot partners.
Pilot Owner	The city or authority responsible for the implementation of a particular GREENGAGE innovation pilot. Is changed in Local Planning Agent in this deliverable.
Place-based communities	Place-based communities are related to a geographical area and constituted by certain characteristics of a place. They can range from small localities (e.g., villages or a small neighbourhood within a town or city) with a population of up to several hundred, to much larger geographical areas (e.g., a town, a large neighbourhood within a town or city, an island, a cluster of villages etc.) ⁴ . In GREENGAGE, we think they are already existing or evolving informally or formally where pilot is located and through activities of public engagement within Observatories.
Planio	Planio is a project management platform based on Redmine: “Redmine is a free and open source, web-based project management and issue tracking tool. It allows users to manage multiple projects and associated subprojects. It features per project wikis and forums, time tracking, and flexible, role-based access control. It includes a calendar and Gantt charts to aid visual representation of projects and their deadlines. Redmine integrates with various version control systems and includes a repository browser and diff viewer.” (Source: Wikipedia , 2024)
Thematic Co-Explorations	A Thematic Co-Exploration involves a group of people that combines already available datasets (Open Data, Copernicus) with those datasets that Citizen Observers can contribute with. The idea is that heterogenous datasets are combined and correlated to give place to indicators and visualisations that are widely understandable by laypeople. Besides, the conclusions or insights driven by each pilot will be mapped into storylines, i.e., narrative, and visual communication to raise awareness about the issues associated to Green Deal and possible solutions that as society we can tackle.
Use cases	Generally, use cases are specific situations in which a product or service could potentially be used. In GREENGAGE we experiment in localised and place-based, co-created and living platforms and learn about the useability of Observatories as intermediators of urban policy innovation. The products that are tested on their usefulness for driving transformative urban planning are existing technologies, tools and practices that brought into play by the GREENGAGE consortium to build tech-aided and co-created environmental monitoring and information systems, or GREENGAGE Observatories.

Executive summary (publishable)

This report follows the development of GREENGAGE Academy within which GREENGAGE Observatories will operate. Firstly, it starts by defining GREENGAGE Observatories as living labs for local policy innovation and GREENGAGE Academy as a platform that enables the interaction and collaboration between people participating in GREENGAGE Observatories but also those outside. In other words, GREENGAGE Academy provides a theoretical, practical and ethical environment for the strategic co-production of GREENGAGE Observatories, setting an exemplary framework for performing the Green Deal and a precedent for Citizen Observatories in general, i.e., extending beyond the scope of the GREENGAGE project. The latter will be crucial for translating the acquired knowledge and lessons learnt into a replication roadmap.

Secondly, the report outlines a series of steps undertaken for setting up the necessary infrastructures to support the GREENGAGE Academy as a whole and the GREENGAGE Observatories for each of the GREENGAGE pilots individually. From its governance (Innovation Action Board) to its methodology (Situating Experimentation), tools (interaction platforms) and timeline (Journey), the conceptualized Roadmap sets out a detailed plan of action including major milestones and desired outcomes.

The third part of the report describes a series of actions already undertaken as part of initiating GREENGAGE Academy. These address several of its aspects, notably setting up an organisational structure, testing existing or adopting new interaction and collaborative platforms, managing challenges, and defining KPIs for next steps.

The aim of the report is to draft a manual (i.e., a Roadmap) for setting up, running, and maintaining material and immaterial infrastructures for GREENGAGE Observatories so that the latter can play a bigger and more sustainable role in influencing local governance and policy innovation.

Related documents

D1.5 - Ethical management plan and activities

D2.1 - GREENGAGE CO Methodological Framework

D2.4 - Smart governance model 1

D2.6 – GREENGAGE technological requirements 1

D3.2 - CO solution mapping to pilots, recruitment and training report

1 GREENGAGE summary

The pan-European Innovation Action, funded under the Horizon Europe Framework Programme, aims to promote innovative governance processes, and help public authorities in shaping their climate mitigation and adaptation policies. To achieve this aim, the GREENGAGE project will leverage citizens' participation and equip them with innovative digital solutions that will transform citizens' engagement and cities' effectiveness in delivering the European Green Deal objectives for carbon neutral cities.

Focusing on mobility, air quality and healthy living, citizens will be inspired to observe and co-create their cities by sensing their urban environments. The aim is to complement, validate, and enrich information in authoritative data held by the public administrations and public agencies. This will be facilitated by engaging with citizens to co-create green initiatives and to develop Citizen Observatories. In GREENGAGE, Citizen Observatories will be a place where pilot cities will co-examine environmental issues integrating novel bottom-up process with top-down perspectives. This will provide the basis to co-create and co-design innovative solutions to monitor environmental problems at ground level with the help of citizens.

With two interrelated project dimensions, the project aims to enhance intelligence applied to city decision-making processes and governance by engaging with citizen observations integrated with Copernicus, Global Earth Observation System of Systems GEOSS, in-situ, and socio-economic intelligence, and by delivering innovative governance models based on novel toolboxes of decision-making methodologies and technologies.

The envisioned Citizen Observatory campaigns will be deployed and fully demonstrated in 5 pilot engagements in selected European cities and regions including: Bristol (the United Kingdom), Copenhagen (Denmark), Turano and Gerace (Italy) and the region of North Brabant (the Netherlands). These innovation pilots aim to highlight the need for smart city governance by promoting citizen engagement, co-creation, as well as gathering new data which will complement existing datasets and evidence-based decision and policymaking.

Figure 1: Structure of project GREENGAGE.

2 Object of the Deliverable

This deliverable, the GREENGAGE Academy Roadmap for GREENGAGE Observatories, provides a guideline on how to (1) set up, run, and maintain GREENGAGE Observatories; (2) assess, design and apply a variety of Observatory tools (both technical and participatory), methods for engagement and data collection, and (3) produce a set of resources, from now on called GREENGAGE Observatory Knowledge Assets. The roadmap also discusses how to involve communities, local authorities, and other relevant stakeholders in every step of the process of the PREPARING, PILOTING, and COLLECTIVE LEARNING phases of the GREENGAGE Innovation Action, to perform the delivery of Green Deal objectives, both during and beyond the project. In the core the deliverable explains the Academy as conceptual and technical framework that ensures a collaborative, replicable environment for situated experimentation and collective learning. It defines related roles, tasks and interaction platforms that are relevant for developing the Academy and participating in the innovation ecosystem. At the end, the deliverable details and reflects on the approach GREENGAGE project adopted for operationalising GREENGAGE Observatories, which is a reflexive, experimentative and highly contextual (situated) approach that focuses on the co-design, testing and refinement of the participatory aspect of the process, with the aim to foster a culture of sharing and learning and maximise its impact on policy making. This makes the deliverable not only relevant for the next phase (PILOTING) of the project, but also for other cities, the Citizen Science field and its practical relevance to urban planning and governance.

3 Introduction

First, a word of clarification: During the reflexive phase of WP3 regarding the creation of this deliverable (and the further operationalisation of GREENGAGE’s observatories), a decision has been taken to refine the term **Citizen Observatory (CO)** to a more inclusive **GREENGAGE Observatory (GO)**. This change has been recommended, to broaden the term to also include people who might not possess the citizenship of the Pilots under investigation. This was already set to action for the creation of this deliverable.

In the GREENGAGE project, GREENGAGE Observatories follow a three-staged process (coined as GREENGAGE Innovation Action): PREPARING, PILOTING and COLLECTIVE LEARNING (see for reference deliverable D2.1). This deliverable, **D3.3 looks at the second phase of the process, the PILOTING and offers guidance on its realisation. It does so by laying out the main stages in the production and application of knowledge assets at different levels, according to which the project interacts with the public:**

- (1) within GREENGAGE partners and pilots as part of the Innovation Action,
- (2) within and across the local communities addressed by or emerging through the Observatories, and
- (3) beyond the GREENGAGE project, reaching out to the wider audience that is interested in tools, practices and technologies for urban governance and policy innovation.

To effectively and sustainably respond to socio-ecological problems and related urban and regional challenges that result from climate change, we need to set up infrastructures that enable capacity building on these three levels. Capacity building in this sense requires situated understandings about the opportunities and challenges in governance that exist in specific contexts. In GREENGAGE we aim to co-produce these understandings in collaboration with different kinds of communities and apply them in the context of urban and regional planning to drive socio-ecological transformation towards more just, healthy and solidary futures.

The purpose of this deliverable is **(1) to provide guidelines for how we can set up, use and maintain these infrastructures (2) to enable the creation, dissemination and application of situated understandings on opportunities and challenges for local governance and policy innovation, and (3) to foster cultures of knowledge development and exchange within and across different communities and localities.** For a start, the GREENGAGE Academy Roadmap conceptualises GREENGAGE Observatories as situated, ethical, data-driven, and community-led processes for local governance and policy innovation (Chapter 4). It then discusses lessons learned during the PREPARING phase, whilst setting up the necessary infrastructures to be able to engage with the public at three levels (Chapter 5). In a next step it envisions the GREENGAGE Academy as the main interaction platform for diverse communities and as the enabler for meaningful participation in the governance and policy labs (Chapter 6). This leads to writing an action plan (strategy) for the next PILOTING phase of the GREENGAGE Innovation Action, effectively illustrating the adaptation of the GREENGAGE Academy to the specific pilots set up during the project (Chapter 7). This chapter will answer how site constraints are identified and addressed to support the organisation and operation of Observatories; Ultimately, this chapter illustrates what lessons can be learned from the Pilots. Finally, Chapter 8 discusses how these case-based learnings become relevant for more citizens or how they can be applied to other localities. This culminates in an initial overview of guiding actions that can be undertaken when initiating the GREENGAGE Academy in different contexts (Chapter 8). The findings will provide the basis to run full-scale piloting in WP5 and create knowledges that are meant to outlive the GREENGAGE project.

4 Envisioning GREENGAGE Observatories as situated, data-driven, community-led intelligence for implementing the European Green Deal

This chapter aims to outline the rationale for refining the vision for GREENGAGE presented by the consortium in 2023 by conceptualising GREENGAGE Observatories in localised policy and governance labs that enable situated, data-driven, and community-led intelligence for performing the European Green Deal. This conceptualisation derives from a critical reflection of the socio-political challenges living labs face in their effort to influence policy making. It also results from working closely with our consortium partners that act as local planning agents in five different pilot localities to develop and operationalise GREENGAGE Observatories in their capacities together with consortium partners that set the metrics, suggest core models and terms that are framing the GREENGAGE approach methodologically. By revisiting set ethical values to be adopted and adapted across all Observatories and stressing the importance for co-developing distinctive guiding principles for coordinating each Observatory, we are setting the tone for a collective innovation approach towards transdisciplinary knowledge co-creation and its application in localised and place-based GREENGAGE Observatories that engage with the public in governance and policy innovation labs. While not aiming for an outline of the related scientific discourses, this conceptualisation should make GREENGAGE Observatories meaningful contributors to the successful integration of citizen science in enabling systemic changes and delivering the Green Deal at the level of Europe as well as the level of five distinctive urban and regional contexts.

4.1 The GREENGAGE Innovation Action

The GREENGAGE Innovation Action (IA) is granted by the European Commission, which aims to innovate and streamline their modes of democratic governance to ensure successful green and digital transitions and coherent delivery of the European Green Deal across the member states and the associated countries. To approach that on the ground, the European Commission builds on the idea of enabling digital and green technologies and calls for living labs to perform innovation, to improve societal acceptance and to generate insights for future proof regulations (Joint Research Centre 2022, COM/2022/289 final). GREENGAGE responds to that by developing GREENGAGE Observatories through processes of situated experimentation, active intermediation and collective learning for public engagement.

GREENGAGE's specific objectives are:

Objective 1 – Raise citizens' awareness, interest, and engagement in urban environmental issues by offering a better factual understanding of urban stressors and resulting environmental degradation aided by GREENGAGE Observatory educational and training campaigns and advocacy campaigns.

Objective 2 – Provide scientifically-sound and rigorous methods for citizen understanding of environmental data - its purpose, goals, use, quality issues, and collection best practices - facilitated through GREEN Engine environment, its methodology and supported by its toolbox and training and success cases from GREENGAGE Academy, thus achieving a higher response rate in ongoing and future environmental monitoring campaigns towards a greater data availability within existing observation systems (e.g., GEOSS, Copernicus).

Objective 3 – Promote and ensure broader acceptance and implementation rates of data collected by citizens in policy- and decision-making in the environmental domain towards innovative citizen-centred urban governance, by validating and demonstrating their added value through GREENGAGE Observatories and piloting.

Objective 4 – Promote the co-creation of data solutions for the urban environment together with domain experts, data scientists, policy makers and citizens by leveraging the use of existing technological toolkits, methods and wearables used to facilitate environmental observation and validation throughout GREENGAGE Pilots.

Objective 5 – Establish synergies among partner cities, with other CO-oriented networks and initiatives, and environmental agencies to exchange best practices, ensure transferability, **uptake, and replication of successful GREENGAGE Observatory experiences** in different contexts across Europe and with different groups to ensure society's representativeness and beyond, while also ensuring continuous take on of GREENGAGE activities after the project ends.

To achieve these objectives, GREENGAGE Observatories apply citizen science tools, technologies and practices to promote, “test, demonstrate and advance new socio-technical arrangements and associated modes of governance in a model environment under real-world conditions” (Engels et al. 2019, p. 1). Through reflexive practices they gain localised, place-based and community-led or situated understandings on challenges and opportunities for local planning strategies in favour of an undergoing socio-economic and environmental transformation.

In the interest of The New Bauhaus initiative¹, GREENGAGE Observatories address the critical urban and regional planning challenges driven by environmental change, socio-economic inequalities and low civil participation in democratic policy making processes by making them meaningful to people’s daily lives and environments. KWMC as one of the consortium partners runs a neighbourhood-based living lab and invites to develop citizen science experiments within collaborative environments that are applying aesthetic practices to bridge between the worlds of science and technology, art and culture to address complex societal problems in co-creative ways. In GREENGAGE, we see ethically framed aesthetic practices² can intermediate between top-down and bottom-up visions and plans and moderate aspirations and expectations of different participants that collaborate in GREENGAGE Observatories creating more inclusive regulatory instruments for local climate mitigation and adaptation. In GREENGAGE, consortium partners together with different stakeholders and participants are part of emerging communities across Europe that are interested in designing socio-ecological transformation and apply co-creative practices, tools for knowledge co-production and digital technologies to promote collaborative responses to critical urban and regional planning challenges. This is to develop and apply solid knowledges that help to enhance localised intelligence to inform interventions into the current socio-material order of different geopolitical contexts and environments. As such, GREENGAGE Observatories can contribute to the still silent discussion about data-based, community-led living innovation ecosystems that organise climate action and learn about their potential for reworking the relationships between science and society, between local politics and communities and between different disciplines and cultures of urban and regional knowledge production. GREENGAGE partners themselves are working within a given regulatory framework but aim to co-create Observatories across different activities and groups as open-result processes. Related to the idea of building cultural commons, they are pooling their knowledge, creatively adapting existing tools and technologies, defining suitable organisational structures and cultivating an intersectional approach on participatory research to build capacity for socio-ecological transformation. Doing so, they are testing and reflecting on GREENGAGE’s potential as a promoter of governance transformation within the European Commission’s research and innovation funding programme. This might inspire future Innovation Actions in their ways of organising project partnerships to enable effective collaboration in addressing critical planning challenges. Furthermore, insights from this experiential process will give public authorities a hands-on approach and recommendations on how they can support the development of Observatories in response to complex, changing situations and thus engage in the democratisation of local decision-making processes of their socio-political contexts.

The EU’s self-reflexive approach on policy innovation is remarkable and truly a gesture for democratising the means of producing knowledges for better policy making. Nevertheless, it is the means of production, the ability of collective learning and acknowledging transdisciplinary, localised forms of intelligence as well as the will of authorities to implement policies and modify governance processes that will decide on its potential for driving the systemic changes needed for future societies to thrive within planetary boundaries. The GREENGAGE Academy Roadmap provides a guide for Observatories organising knowledge co-production in localised governance and policy labs and use of knowledge assets and tools in piloting activities during the GREENGAGE project, but also extends beyond the project in providing pointers on how to coordinate future innovation actions related to the co-creative policy making towards preferred urban and regional situations for the many, not the few.

¹ https://new-european-bauhaus.europa.eu/about/about-initiative_en

² As research is always creating a deviation, a simplification and a vision (Haraway, 1988, p. 585) of the realities that it is referring to, it is also an aesthetic practice.

4.2 Partnering with local planning agents to perform mission-led policy innovations

In GREENGAGE we partner with local planning agencies aiming to tackle socio-ecological problems in relation to environmental changes by enhancing situated intelligence through public engagement. These pioneers of emerging local planning communities understand the importance of democratising governance systems to be able to deal with local effects of the global climate crisis. Their pilot activities seek to onboard different kinds of communities and enable civil society to meaningfully participate in the local planning processes which is key for organising representational and sustainable transitions of societies, and to build trust in their ability to govern these by not leaving anyone behind. These sentiments are displayed in the quote from a regional authority representative from the North Brabant pilot below.

“Fully agree and recognise the above description and analysis. Fits with our experiences as a province in programs and ambitions for transitions related to societal challenges. Among others in our Smart Health program ten years ago the aspects and approach of collective learning, living labs and design thinking were involved. In general, within the region user centric design concepts and active citizenship are embraced. But it is still only some niches based on action by individuals. It is easier said than done and not yet a mainstream approach. So, I hope and expect that GREENGAGE can have impact in the regions and with our stakeholders and partners to embrace co-creation more often. To make it a starting point for the transitions and transformations we work on” Edwin Mermans, GREENGAGE partner and Senior advisor international affairs (Province of North Brabant) .

GREENGAGE Observatories aim to make co-creation experienceable and impact societal changes beyond the right to participate in policy making processes given by citizenship. This is, why as a result of our collective learning we speak about GREENGAGE Observatories rather than “Citizen Observatories”. In GREENGAGE we understand local policy making processes can be transformative when based on co-designed decisions – or policies – that apply ethical considerations and reflect situated, co-created understandings on the fundamental social agreements about how cities, neighbourhoods, villages and regions will continue to be built. Beyond future development of the built environments, urban policies also determine basic rules on how their inhabitants will relate to each other and can prompt ways of inhabiting places that enable systemic changes towards more just, healthy and solidary ways of living within changing natural environments. When building on collective experimentative learning and reflexive practices of common sense making, such ways of challenge-based can enable urban and regional governance systems to effectively change the societal order democratically into fossil-free ecosystems. As such GREENGAGE Observatories are themselves politically engaged or mission-led processes with the potential to validate, refine and ground the European Green Deal in local contexts together with diverse participants. As placed in real-world environments, GREENGAGE Observatories engage in this “democratic revitalisation” (Rasmus Reeh, GREENGAGE partner and local planning agent in Ørestad, Copenhagen) and appear as pathfinders to rework the relationships between ‘the state’ and ‘the citizens’ through active intermediation between the meaning of current situations and the objective futures for distinctive localities. Active intermediation here refers to a set of interstitial practices, tools and technologies adopted by the GREENGAGE Innovation Action to ‘transform, translate, distort or modify the meaning’ (Latour, 2005, p. 30, cited in Perry & Smit, 2022, p. 688)¹ of the situation in pilots.

As such GREENGAGE Observatories, as processes of situated experimentation and enabled by active intermediation, have the potential to drive meaningful changes themselves.

“A GREENGAGE (Citizen [sic!]) Observatory has an advantage selling-point of being a potential problem solver of lived experiences - in technology terms; it is a large, decentralised intelligence with distributed nodes of data crunching. The task of the GREENGAGE (Citizen [sic!]) Observatory is to connect individual nodes and instigate a ‘societal optimisation process’ from ‘business as usual from everyone minding their own businesses to a connected systemic solution developer/change agent” Rasmus Reeh, GREENGAGE partner and representative of Copenhagen Pilot.

Assuming technologies generate agency themselves (Haraway, 1988) in coordinating knowledge production and application, and therefore driving discursive interventions which can inform systemic changes, is indeed a key selling point of the manifold technologies provided from consortium partners to GREENGAGE Observatories. At the same time this brings to the fore ethical and political questions that we address through reflexive practices of collective learning alongside our experimentation.

4.3 A situated experimentation approach

In the Methodological Framework for GREENGAGE Citizen Observatories (D2.1) we suggested to develop Observatories in GREENGAGE in a living lab approach that is outstanding through its emphasis on active intermediation, ethically framed, situated experimentation and collective learning. Since then, we have been working with all the project partners, refined our understandings and elaborated a distinctive logic for co-creation within GREENGAGE that informs conceptual pathways for innovation. As a result of this we see the need to update the former proposed idea of developing GREENGAGE Citizen Observatories and think about them here as GREENGAGE Observatories that are developed within localised governance and policy labs.

The updated framing is based on the idea that we will create not only living labs (which can have various manifestations and meanings) but also processes of experimentation that are situated within the pilots’ socio-political contexts and – as introduced in the beginning of this chapter – in the context of Pan-European governance innovation. The process is described as situated experimentation for developing GREENGAGE Observatories within governance and policy labs and will be explained in detail in Chapter 6 of this deliverable. What is important to remember at this point is that central to the process is active intermediation which alongside the processes of PREPARING, PILOTING and COLLECTIVE LEARNING help to develop understandings of the changing, complex situation of the distinctive socio-political contexts of the pilots and other aspects that determine their abilities to perform innovation so that we can suggest actions that are responsive to these rather than imposing ideals on how to model the pilots. Practices, tools and technologies are further intermediating between top-down/bottom-up expectations and aspirations for policy innovation as articulated in plans, missions, visions and other discourses coming from different authorities and communities. As such, these intermediating tools, practices and technologies are likely to support the effective application of the GREENGAGE engagement methodology (D2.1, Chapter 4.5) based on the principle of situational onboarding and training of participants of Observatories. In other words, it depends on how the situation in pilots is understood to make reasonable decisions on where to look next and whom to bring on board to explore use cases that are ultimately supposed to drive local governance and policy innovation.

A methodological framing like that of situated experimentation, enables that knowledge production and application stays responsive to the specific, changing situations in the pilots and builds the conceptual foundation for comparison and mutual learning across these. To test and validate the process of situated experimentation, GREENGAGE Academy will be developed in collaboration with participants of five pilots to promote GREENGAGE Observatories as integral part of a participatory governance process. The five pilots will be co-designed and fully demonstrated in Bristol (United Kingdom), Copenhagen (Denmark), Turano and Gerace (Italy) and the region of North Brabant (Netherlands). How governance and policy innovation is possible, is determined by the understanding of challenges and opportunities in the distinctive pilot’s situation. This is, why innovation can only to a certain extent follow existing models and be inspired by theories but necessarily requires the will and openness of multiple stakeholders to actively engage in experimentation and collective learning in specific situational environments. As these envisioned “Innovation Pilots” are operating in real world environments, the potentials for delivering innovation during the partnership of GREENGAGE are changing. Moreover, what can be seen as

potential is highly dependent from an intersubjectively valid interpretation of the interplay of different elements that matter for innovation in GREENGAGE. An updated specification of their socio-political contexts, targets, and expected impacts for engaging with the local public is provided in Chapter 7 of this deliverable. Through collective learning on the process of situated experimentation we can generate transdisciplinary interpretations on their interplay and might validate our situational understandings to support governance and policy innovation in whatever that means in relation to the different five “Innovation Pilots” and their performance through public engagement.

Beside the active intermediation among the consortium partners to conceptualise “Innovation Pilots”, active intermediation is suggested to guide the process of developing Observatories in each of the pilot localities: In GREENGAGE, place-based policy labs seek to make space for the dialogue between public authorities and communities, green initiatives, researchers, tech providers and other potential stakeholders and understand the concerns, advantages and practical implications of implementing GREENGAGE Observatories as integral parts of urban and regional governance systems. Intermediating here can also mean to enable local planning agents and authorities of local policymaking with tools and knowledges to democratically respond to a community’s understanding of the local needs for effective and sustainable innovation. Equipping local planning agents with these enablers can be delivered within the scope of the project through dedicated training but necessarily needs to be grounded in the specific contexts by navigating legal and regulatory requirements, negotiating appropriate institutional arrangements, mobilising resources and facilitate active participation together with those stakeholders who actually have a say in the local public and mandate to shape decision-making processes of urban and regional planning.

To ensure this dialogue is meaningful to the local planning challenges and evidence-based, it will be based on use cases that are developed with the help of volunteering participants of the Observatories in the GREENGAGE Academy. They generate new datasets which will complement existing authoritative data and help map and analyse environmental, infrastructural and mobility patterns in a rather comprehensive way. Through the integration of new data, existing data held by local authorities will also be validated³. The different participants of Observatories will be trained (where the objectives of the Observatory require so) to collectively interpret these data and learn with other stakeholders of the policy and governance labs what can be done to design local policies that are adaptive to the consequences of environmental change and new realities of post-pandemic societies. These insights will be communicated in local campaigns or other interventions and understood as use cases and stories that perform the delivery of European Green Deal objectives in meaningful ways for innovating urban and regional governance. As such, GREENGAGE Observatories will define and deliver innovative processes of urban and regional planning based on real-world experimentation and collective learning in multi-stakeholder collaboration. The feature of approaching real world scenarios in different European locations enables learning on systemic conditions for democratic innovation through comparison across five pilots. These “transformation knowledges” will be published along the process in pilots, might inform further interpretations of innovation challenges and opportunities during the ongoing experimentation by being available on the GREENGAGE Academy and further disseminated as recommendations for public authorities in the GREENGAGE White Book.

As the situated experimentation process depends on the contextual situation and the contribution of multiple stakeholders, the roadmap in this deliverable can only provide guidelines and pointers for the actualisation of pilot-specific Observatories (see Annex for specifications). The overall strategy needs to be agile enough to be adapted and adopted to the changing environments the pilots and GREENGAGE are operating with. Considering that the operational conditions of these governance and policy labs are affecting the planned experiments of Observatories, this deliverable can only offer a guide to set up a pilot in a real-world environment. Considering that the local capacities and cultures of knowledge production and application differ across the pilots, the GREENGAGE Academy Roadmap can only give recommendations for co-creating the Academy in ways that enable the generalisation of pilots’ discoveries within a generic conceptual and technical framework that aims for replicability beyond the project to drive local governance and policy innovation through building technological and intellectual

³ This requires an acknowledgement of citizen-generated data as qualitative, valid data at first. Second, to ensure the validity and reliability of data generated by citizen scientists is an essential methodological question that we need to respond to when we are designing the use cases together with pilot and tech partners.

capacity and situated intelligence engage in climate action across Europe and perform a community-led delivery of the European Green Deal.

4.4 Ethical values for co-creating GREENGAGE Observatories

The GREENGAGE Ethical Framework ensures that experimentation is ethically framed, but as co-creating a process ethically cannot be a ticking boxes activity, we introduced in the first chapter of the Ethical Management Plan – GREENGAGE Values as Living Practices (D1.5, Chapter 1.2.1). The principle of “Values as Living Practices” implicates that values should be liveable and lived by those who set them up. Based on our learnings during GREENGAGE Academy roadmapping activities, we list here an updated version of these normative markers:

- Democratising local knowledge and policy making.
- Understanding the local as the object and starting point for political action.
- Addressing existing power relations and social hierarchies.
- Empowering inclusive and diverse participation in communities.
- Enabling self-governance of communities.
- Facilitating reflexivity and community-led sense making and theory building.
- Developing and applying technologies by the purpose to serve the wellbeing of communities now and in future, not market interests.
- Generating localised commons - community-organised public spaces and civic infrastructures.
- Rewarding and appreciating volunteering participation in GREENGAGE Observatories.

To ensure value-based co-creation in Observatories, we suggest that pilots define their values ideally together with the stakeholders of Observatories in the beginning of their activities. This can help to orientate decisions on where to look at or what to do in situated processes of experimentation and collective learning based on the importance that is given to some actions or things. By contrasting one's own actions against pursued ethical values can help Observatories to become meaningful for the lives of their participants. As such, they can be understood as complementary to the ongoing definition of KPIs and impact assessment on a larger scale. Beyond that, they might be even relevant for getting people on board that share the same values so we suggested this set of values that might be relevant across the pilots.

4.5 Guiding principles for coordinating GREENGAGE Observatories

We suggest that there is need to coordinate GREENGAGE Observatories based on guiding principles (D2.1, Chapter 4.6). Nevertheless, to provide meaningful orientation, these principles should be adopted and adapted to the pilot's local context and challenges, and ideally formulated together with the stakeholders of Observatories. When discussed honestly, they can act as a ‘critical friends’ that accompany the pilot's experimentation and ensure that the applied tools, practices and technologies that coordinate the co-creation between different stakeholders of Observatories serve the improvement of the Observatory participant's well-being through the process and its outcomes.

In their current version, guiding principles can serve as a tool to develop reflexive practices across pilots with the aim to achieve situated understandings based on common actions and set metrics. This could also be important in order to identify commonalities and particularities and share lessons learned from setting up five different Observatories. As active intermediators, guiding principles could help to build communities of practice and foster cultures of transformative knowledge generation and exchange in and across different communities and localities. Finally, by bringing them into action, we can test them on their usefulness for coordinating value-based living labs. This has already started while roadmapping the GREENGAGE Academy and a refinement of their first version was needed to reach common understanding for the tasks and responsibilities of the coordinators of Observatories. Here we list an updated version of the guiding principles suggested in D2.1 to guide the coordinators of GREENGAGE Observatories in the PILOTING stage of the GREENGAGE Innovation Action:

1. Coordinators of GREENGAGE Observatories need to ensure that the GREENGAGE methodological frameworks are the foundation for further conceptualisations of Observatories.
2. Coordinators of GREENGAGE Observatories need to contribute to the development of the GREENGAGE Academy as collaborative interaction platform.
3. Coordinators of GREENGAGE Observatories need to ensure intelligible structuring of experimentation, continuous evaluation & replication within the living labs.
4. Coordinators of GREENGAGE Observatories need to develop training materials responsive to the pilots' needs and aspirations for enabling meaningful participation.
5. Coordinators of GREENGAGE Observatories should design the development of Observatories based on patterns of commoning⁴.

At this point the guiding principles are listed as a set of instructions to follow for successfully setting up, running, and sustaining a GREENGAGE Observatory. However, Chapter 7 will demonstrate how these principles have governed the development of GREENGAGE Academy, starting from the establishment of organisational structures to the use of interaction and collaborative platforms and the definition of common KPIs.

4.6 Public engagement through GREENGAGE Observatories

Transformative knowledge co-production and application/academy

As a research innovation action, the development of Observatories towards informing transformative urban policy making forms the core of the GREENGAGE project. According to the HORIZON-IA, Innovation Actions are “primarily consisting of activities directly aiming at producing plans and arrangements or designs for new, altered or improved products, processes or services. For this purpose, they may include prototyping, testing, demonstrating, piloting, large-scale product validation and market replication. [...] Projects may include limited research and development activities” (EU HORIZON 2020). This means participatory research for innovation is not the focus but a means for delivering the GREENGAGE Innovation Action (IA) and creating pilot specific GREENGAGE Observatories as a multidisciplinary consortium that engages with local publics to create improved understandings and tools for sustaining climate action collectively.

To use participatory research as a means for transdisciplinary learning within and about an innovation action seems reasonable, as the purpose of the GREENGAGE Academy is to address urban challenges that are articulated by local planning agents in co-creative ways together with different stakeholders that become part of their governance and policy labs. In GREENGAGE Observatories, we apply participatory research to increase the democratisation of urban knowledge production. We are building on the pilots to highlight to communities (of place, practise and interest), what citizen science can do to shape policy innovation. From a discourse theoretical point of view, knowledge co-production has the potential for democratic structuring of urban transformations in a logic beyond top-down/bottom-up. In GREENGAGE, an altered understanding of the conditions for transformative knowledge co-production is emerging in the consortium's community of interest and continuously materialised in the knowledge assets hosted by the GREENGAGE Academy. This GREENGAGE community might evolve beyond the project as identified potentials for replicating, adopting, or scaling up Observatories will be shared with policy makers through the White Book and the generic framework of the Academy will be made accessible for upcoming initiatives.

We suggest that collective learning is not only the task of a few meta-thinkers but a transdisciplinary endeavour. We know from research on sustainable urban knowledge co-production, that experimentation for democratic policy innovation needs to be grounded in reflexivity based on

⁴ Patterns of commoning have been developed based on research of communities and societies that relate in ways that enable the building of commons, a concept which inspires the theory and practice of alternative economies. For further information, see <https://patternsofcommoning.org/>.

interpretations of those participants that are actively shaping political experiments, which here are the stakeholders of localised and place-based governance and policy labs.

“Reflexivity is different from reflection. Whereas the latter involves looking back on past experiences to capture learning, the former constitutes a process of meta-learning – reflection not only in but on action. Reflection entails ‘in-the-moment reflective episodes’, whereas reflexivity is ‘a conscious cognitive process whereby knowledge and theory are applied to make sense of remembered reflective episodes’” (Hemström et al., 2021, p. 28).

Thus, practising reflexivity seems central to any form of participatory research that aims for democratisation of local knowledge and policy making, but especially for an approach of Observatories that is embedded in governance and policy labs to promote and demonstrate the value of widespread participation in shaping transition policies. Urban experimentalisms rooted in democratic philosophies claim the need for intelligible cities that depend on active intermediation between the different realms of the urban society (May & Perry, 2017, p. 24) and create situational frames for the collaborative search for new solutions. It is in these situated and collaborative forms of urban experimentalism where mutual learning becomes the common ground for localised transformations. Collin McFarlane (McFarlane, 2011, Introduction) connects the situational, material, and transformational qualities of learning the urban:

“Learning, even where it is explicitly described as uncertain (...) refers to a process involving particular constituencies and discursive constructions, entails a range of inclusions and exclusions of people and epistemologies, and produces a means of going on through a set of guidelines, tactics or opportunities. As a process and outcome, learning is actively involved in changing or bringing into being particular assemblages of people-sources-knowledges. It is more than just a set of mundane practical questions but is central to political strategies that seek to consolidate, challenge, alter and name new worlds.”

In GREENGAGE, we envision that throughout collaboration, reflexive practices and collective learning we can build new communities and strengthen existing communities that engage in climate action by equipping them with knowledges and tools that enable meaningful participation in policy making. These communities are forming through collective activities in relation to a geographical area, e.g., through observing a neighbourhood (communities of place), their deepening of knowledge and skills in a common practice, such as research or urban planning (communities of practice) and their shared interest in the transdisciplinary framing of and a co-creative responding to a problem, such as within experimentation and collective learning in the GREENGAGE innovation action (communities of interest).

4.7 A legacy beyond GREENGAGE

If GREENGAGE Observatories are the containers for situated, data-driven, community-led experimentation and collective learning for localised governance and place-based policy innovation, then we can define GREENGAGE Academy as the platform that will enable the transdisciplinary learning and community building between participants of GREENGAGE Observatories but also those outside those containers. In other words, GREENGAGE Academy can provide the theoretical, practical and ethical environment for the strategic co-production of Observatories, setting an exemplary technical and conceptual framework for performing the community-led delivery of the Green Deal and precedent for future citizen-/user-centred Observatories (i.e., beyond the GREENGAGE project).

As part of GREENGAGE Academy, GREENGAGE pilot specific Observatories will enable the different communities (of place, practice and interest) that interact in localised and place-based policy and governance labs to organise collective learning around issues addressed by the European Green Deal and other sustainability topics. Through its provided training and applications, the Academy builds capacities (in terms of knowledges and skills) to for meaningful collaboration between participants of Observatories and institutional stakeholders or local authorities to work towards co-creative policymaking based on situated intelligence. Yet, the knowledge assets produced by and planned for these Observatories, the technical containers that enable collaboration, as well as engagement and data gathering strategies will not only be specific to engage with localised publics, but also de-contextualised to be passed on to other communities which want to set up their own operational Observatories as living labs. Trainings, tools, and infrastructures will be provided to facilitate the setting up of GOs, but each community revise the experimentation process to fit their own situated context of challenges, resources, and stakeholders. In what follows, the deliverable lays out the step-by-step of setting up GREENGAGE Observatories and reflects how this was approached in active intermediation with the situation of five

REENGAGE pilots and provides guidelines on the establishment of Observatories that build capacity for meaningful climate action beyond the project.

5 Where do we come from: Learnings from the PREPARING phase

The GREENGAGE Academy is the platform that will enable the interaction and collaboration between participants of GREENGAGE Observatories but also those outside. This platform will cut across expertise and activities of the project. This chapter reflects on the activities across work packages that together shaped how the GREENGAGE Academy was envisioned, as outlined in Chapter 6. The PREPARING phase, described as building communities of practise, co-designing tools, practises and technologies (D2.1, Chapter 4.2.1), saw asset creation, a variety of activities, role definitions, and the setup of technological support, cutting across all work packages. In line with the co-designing approach of GREENGAGE, this chapter will reflect on these joint activities in the PREPARING phase to present the principal formative activities shaping the GREENGAGE Academy. An overview of the formative activities of all partners has been gathered through a comprehensive survey sent out in M12 to all WP3 partners and work package leads. This joint reflection ensures that the GREENGAGE Academy Roadmap is based on a somehow collective reflection of representatives of different actors that are part of the multidisciplinary consortium. The chapter first presents chronicle of the main formative activities that contributed to the framework of the GREENGAGE Academy and secondly highlights the continuing challenges that should be addressed in the GREENGAGE Academy Roadmap.

5.1.1 Description of main activities

This section outlines the collaborative efforts of the contributing project partners when setting up the infrastructures for co-creating and applying GREENGAGE Knowledge Assets for the use in Observatories. The interrelatedness of the actions illustrates the emergent process of the conceptualisation of the GREENGAGE Academy across all WP3 actions. The main actions revolve around organisation, roadmapping, training, technological support, and evaluation.

Organisation

The GREENGAGE Academy must facilitate PILOTING within five localised Pilots and beyond the project itself. For this purpose, two interlinked support structures were established: the Innovation Action Board (IAB) and the Pilot Support Teams (PST). Whereas the former ensures that the setting up of GOs and the process of PILOTING can be extended beyond the project, and in other locales (hence delivering the Innovation Action), the latter – a team for each Pilot location - supports the Pilot owners in running their Pilot. Both teams then provided an inventory of what specific requirements had to be met for PILOTING. Here specifically, a call for closer collaboration between WP3 (Pilot preparation and community engagement) and WP4 (technological underpinning) became apparent. This organisational structure was proposed by WP3 and was organised by the project coordinator, who made sure that WP leads, and members of all WPs were distributed over both teams according to their expertise and use of their technology in the Pilot. Further, all PSTs got a double lead for redundancy reasons and coverage of both, social sciences and technology expertise.

Roadmapping

To ensure that the GREENGAGE Academy can facilitate the interaction between Observatory participants, it is essential to know what kind of interaction, participation, and activities are anticipated by the Pilot owners. WP3 developed methodologies and associated questionnaires to inventory the vision, challenges and the considered technologies of each Pilot. The creation and analysis of this Situational Screening Questionnaire gathered both the current state of the Pilots, as well as possible ways of how to run co-creation. While primarily an activity undertaken by WP3 and its task leads, extra attention to the GREENGAGE framework as outlined in WP2 and technological requirements discussed by WP4 leads and members, made this questionnaire a joint effort. Finally, the results of the questionnaire, and thus the required workflow and relations, was visualised in flyers, the GREENGAGE webpage, and visuals by the WP7 members.

Another dimension which became apparent as part of questionnaire and extensive Pilot exploration was the language barrier. The GREENGAGE Academy should incorporate a reflection and workflow on the local language adaptations. In the PREPARING phase, several technology partners, as well as Pilot owners, stepped up to the plate to translate the provided assets, tools, and Academy resources.

Training

Profiling GREENGAGE Observatories as situated, ethically run, and community led activities required a strategy for co-designing and delivering a GREENGAGE Train-the-Trainers Programme, committed to co-design and deliver trainings. Trainings pursued the continued ethical embedding but also manuals for the technologies adopted and methodologies of co-creation and data analysis, including the benefits that citizens can have through Copernicus data, and any support to provide an attractive experience for citizens, were indicated in the aforementioned survey. Apart from trainings, training materials and support materials were also deemed necessary, and were provided by WP7, such as visual representations, registration means and guidelines.

GREENGAGE's training materials contribute to the Knowledge Assets in the GREENGAGE Academy. Next to these specific trainings, WP3 also set out to identify the actions and workflows needed by the different Pilots for them to realistically onboard people to the Observatories. However, the local situations and the timing of the project (such as the limited availability of possible participants in the weeks around Christmas time in 2023, when the onboarding means were finished) made this an unfeasible prospect. A soft launch of GOs was made possible through a registration process, implemented on the website, facilitated by WP4 and WP7.

Technological Support

In GREENGAGE, the community-led, situated, Observatories are supported by a toolbox of data-gathering and processing technologies. The GREENGAGE Academy facilitates the interaction between Observatory participants, which also includes the technology toolbox. The link between WP4 and WP3 became more explored through this roadmapping process; onboarding requires technical support, and technologies require an idea of their users to be adequately explained. This was chiefly represented on the website, in collaboration with WP7. Conceptualising and setting up the GREENGAGE website indirectly supported the state of the knowledge and problem statement for each Pilot. The website will now serve as the entry point for future Observatory participants where they can register their interest and get informed about the ongoing data collection campaigns. Additional features of the website will hold the newly named "Knowledge Base" – a repository of all the information, resources, training materials and supporting data essential to Observatory participants.

Next to that, technological specifications were provided by technology partners and Pilot owners. The latter drew attention to knowledge gaps, such as costs of materials or third-party options, and the associated budget constraints. Some technology partners significantly contributed to the exploration of needed recommendations regarding technology, both illustrating their own technology, exploring third-party technologies, and explaining the use of different data types to Pilot owners. By providing a clear image of how the technologies can support Pilots, technology partners could provide a clear view of what the GREENGAGE Academy should and will offer.

Evaluation

Finally, WP3 leads and members have collaborated closely with the Pilot owners and WP6, focused on evaluation of the Pilots. The KPIs, metrics and methods designed for evaluation in WP6 highlight stakeholder groups, expected number of participants etc., which have impact on the activities required of WP3. The required KPIs and their strategy per Pilot gives a clear framework of what should be facilitated by the GREENGAGE Academy.

As illustrated in this overview of activities in the PREPARING phase, the GREENGAGE Innovation Action follows a similar community-led and co-creative approach as they envision of the Observatories. Setting up a GREENGAGE Academy that extends beyond the project and specific Pilots then requires contributions from a variety of specialisms.

5.1.2 Reflection on main activities

With the joint activities from the PREPARING phase outlined above, the infrastructure for the GREENGAGE Academy was in place. This section will reflect on the results of the joint actions and highlight current challenges and decisions. This gives an overview of the GREENGAGE resources and infrastructures used for the Academy, but simultaneously illustrates several areas of work in progress

that will be improved during WP5. The reflections present the first recommendations on how to organise the co-creation and application of GREENGAGE Knowledge Assets and Toolbox during PILOTING – namely in the setting up of an Academy. Related recommendations on the operationalisation will be presented in Chapter 7 and Chapter 8 of this deliverable.

The main activities that were performed to develop and apply the GREENGAGE logic on co-creation in setting up the infrastructure for the GREENGAGE Academy are listed here. Some of these actions are paired with recommendations for improvement or ideal functioning.

1. Prototyping and testing a co-creative organisational structure through an IAB and PSTs to facilitate the understanding and response to the pilots’ specific situations in the PREPARING phase.
 - In general, the **organisational structure** based on IAB and PSTs was accepted, although accompanied by concerns on their purpose and confusion about their distinction. This situation improved after the **role and duties** of PSTs and IAB were clearly communicated to the team.
 - Regarding the **coordination structure** shift to PSTs and IAB, it might be necessary to adapt the overall project organisation (e.g., reduction of frequency of general meetings such as General Assembly Board, or WP Review Meetings) to focus more on IAB and PST meetings to reduce the large amount of meetings which accumulated through the first year of the project.
 - The **composition** of PSTs – a blend of Pilot owners, technological partners, and social scientists – was generally perceived as a good way to shed some light on the existing expertise and skill sets relevant to the project on the side of the pilot partners. Since some PSTs were more effective in gathering relevant information than other PSTs improvements are under discussion for the operationalisation phase of the project.
 - For the purpose of **understanding the Pilots’ situation**, the PSTs were perceived as a good idea to clarify the situation and to gather baseline information of the Pilots (including existing channels of communication, outreach with external stakeholders within pilots) as well as to identify existing needs.
 - For the purpose of **responding to the Pilots’ situation**, PSTs have been helpful in understanding the pilots’ specific progress of preparing Observatories, but less so in responding to their raised issues, concerns and needs. PSTs were useful to identify areas where continuous support by the consortium will be needed, but the PSTs will need to focus even more on the real-world conditions and resources of each pilot since this can and will have consequences for the progress of the project (e.g., the decision on what technologies will be used in the Pilots has already delayed the tailored invitation to GREENGAGE Observers and other stakeholders).
 - For the purpose of **co-designing GREENGAGE Observatories in WP3**, the **IAB** has currently been focussing on making sense of specific Observatories, not so much on streamlining the process of *how to make sense* of Observatories and giving advice to the PSTs on what information is needed to co-design Observatories. In a first step, the validation of situated understandings on the Observatories was done by the project coordinator together with the pilot owners, to be broadened to a transdisciplinary assessment and co-monitoring located by the IAB in a second step.
2. Co-creating digital and analogue interaction platforms during workshops, meetings and surveys to help an ongoing understanding and ways for responding to the pilots’ specific situations.
 - **Workshops** allowed the emergence of abundant information but came with the difficulty of how to fully synthesise and operationalise the information later. Some of them seemed to stay in the brainstorming phase which others yielded concrete output (e.g., Situational Analysis in PST Break out session).

- **Surveys and Questionnaires** seemed to work well for reporting or describing (bringing back already done activities). Nonetheless they need to be synthesised, interpreted and transformed into an agreed response.
 - **Meetings** seemed to be the most efficient mechanism to update the Pilots' situations and attempt to respond to them when focussing on a concrete problem, situation or need. In general, it was challenging to balance between asking for information and responding to Pilots. Meetings with a clear agenda and a filtered list of attendees worked well, while open invitations or too big meetings proved to be less effective as sometimes misunderstood content led to frustrations and lower uptake. Generally, explaining concepts face to face and with the help of appropriate visualisations was perceived as useful.
3. Testing the existing digital collaboration platforms (e.g., MS Teams, Miro, Collaborative Environment, Planio etc.) on their potential to support co-creation across WPs.
- Overall, **the platforms used** were perceived as adequate resources for fostering collaborative work to a reasonable extent, although their use for co-creation was disputed. Finding was, that in order to increase usefulness, the choice and use of tools should be based on actual planned activities, and the information should be cohesively collected to reduce oversights and possible confusion.
 - **SharePoint** was perceived as a repository for storing information on the whole project. The chat was an effective communication tool in ad hoc working groups.
 - **Miro** was perceived as providing an excellent platform to co-create artefacts and for workshops but weak in translating content to other platforms and suffering from accessibility issues.
 - **MS Teams** was used for holding meetings, recordings and to keep all documents in one repository. Challenging was switching between personal MS Teams and the enterprise AIT MS Teams - especially saving and recording files when meetings were set up from partners outside AIT. This led to extra need for mail communication to coordinate MS Teams setups.
 - **Planio** has been useful to validate use cases and it provides good provenance. Nevertheless, since Planio is a platform used mainly for technical requirement collection, it was less accessible to partners with lower technical affinity. This sometimes hindered the use case discussion and development on the platform when interdisciplinary development of use cases was required.
 - The **Collaborative Environment (CE)** has not been used, yet. The overall meta-process configuration and the following process activities is perceived as useful tool for processual co-creation. Nevertheless, the platform needs to make sure not to overwhelm project partners and especially GREENGAGE Observers during the operationalisation phase of the project.
4. The coordination of co-creation between the consortium partners for the PILOTING phase.
- The work to refine the GREENGAGE technologies, as well as the corresponding specifications of the use cases regarding potential benefits for Pilots needed a substantial amount of work. Additionally, their alignment with the top-down expectations according to the description of tasks in the Grant Agreement created a notable delay since further communication was needed within the consortium. For WP5 an organisational and operational improvement is therefore required.
 - The fact that at proposal writing time the use cases had been mostly developed by the Pilot owners in the first place meant that social science perspectives needed to be further improved during the preparational first year of the project. Further, sufficient expertise of urban planning and governance needed to be integrated into the project team, too, to create valuable insights for a wider range of potential users. Lastly, the project is currently establishing additional support for the analysis of the data that the GREENGAGE Observers will collect. This will be achieved by the partners themselves, through their data science expertise.

- Further, the work in silos of WPs (common in EU and other projects) and disciplines conflicts with the principles of multistakeholder co-creation set out in the PREPARING stage. Collaboration between WPs needs to be fostered further so that the reality mirrors the expectations of the GREENGAGE Observers in performing their research activities.

This chapter has outlined the actions that provided the required infrastructure for the GREENGAGE Academy. In this overview, especially the cooperations have been highlighted as these provide a validated and interdisciplinary basis for a co-creative, community-led, and ethically shaped Observatories as a living lab. However, several challenges remain that will have to be addressed in the PILOTING phase to ensure that the recommendations about the GREENGAGE Academy are based on a successful practice. When these challenges are overcome, the GREENGAGE Academy can attain its ideal form, which will be discussed next chapter.

6 Where do we want to go: the GREENGAGE Academy

In previous methodological framings of GREENGAGE Observatories, we recommended building the Academy as collaborative interaction platform (D2.1). Here a collaborative interaction platform was envisioned as a digital interface that hosts co-creation applications of the consortium and interlinks them with already used or specifically set communication channels in the pilots. In the PREPARING stage, the consortium partners assembled existing applications and tested an interconnected system that encompasses mainly digital but also analogue interaction platforms to prepare governance and policy labs, as described in Chapter 5. The Situational Screening gave further insights of the communication channels which the pilot owners use already or plan to apply to interact with stakeholders and potential targeted groups of GREENGAGE Observers. In this deliverable, we envision them as interconnected system of digital and analogue interaction platforms that make the basic technical infrastructure for running GREENGAGE Observatories within localised governance and policy labs as they enable multi-stakeholder collaboration. The conceptualisations of GREENGAGE Observatories, as shared in various previous deliverables of WP2, WP3, WP4, WP6, WP7 make the other dimension of this framework which ensures these living labs and Observatories are developed in line with the GREENGAGE objectives, consider ethical standards and methodologies for engagement and impact assessment. They interact with the technical infrastructure to systematically produce and apply knowledge assets that are relevant for performing local governance and policy innovation in line with the European Green Deal through engaging participants in activities and processes of Observatories. Together, the technological and conceptual infrastructures make the generic framework for delivering the GREENGAGE Innovation Action as innovation ecosystem.

Strategic and effective development of the Academy

To foster the further specification and application of this framework, and to develop the GREENGAGE Academy, it is important to recap the purpose of knowledge co-creation and application in GREENGAGE. The purpose of multi-stakeholder experiments and data-based interventions deduced from our challenge-based, mission-led approach on innovation, or to be as concrete: **The socio-political relevance of GREENGAGE derives from the critical urban and regional planning challenges that are driven by environmental change, socio-economic inequalities and low civic participation in democratic policy making processes.** In GREENGAGE we aim to address these challenges by situated experimentation and collective learning in partnership with local planning agents and support them in creating and applying GREENGAGE Observatories to enhance localised intelligence for innovating policy making through public engagement. Following our set of ethical values and guiding principles as listed in Chapter 4.4 in this deliverable, we now specify their implications for developing and applying the Academy. For a start, to interact ethically raises questions around accessibility: How does the Academy regulate access to knowledge assets and tools that enable meaningful participation in activities of Observatories? How is the dissemination of knowledges about the situated experimentation and collective learning regulated in localised governance and policy labs? Further, it is important to develop the Academy effectively towards the achievement of the GREENGAGE mission. For this, we need to clarify the objective of the Academy which in general is public engagement. Public engagement contains a complex set of tasks that, when named, defines the Academy's role in the GREENGAGE innovation ecosystem. The specific naming of the collection of tasks will follow during PILOTING and will be performed relative to the entire site of the GREENGAGE framework, instead of an individual item. For now, at the stage of setting up Observatories in localised policy and governance labs, a strategized definition of the Academy's system role points towards ensuring the co-design of its interfaces in dialogue with participants of Observatories and managing information flows in ways that enable public engagement with different user types and different types of stakeholders of governance and policy labs and meaningful participation in Observatories at the different localities. To enable the Academy to engage strategically and effectively with the public on different levels requires methodologies that structure the development and application of knowledge assets. **The Academy's main task is to structure and "fuel" discursive interventions (or campaigns) that inform participatory governance and policy innovation.** Following our situated experimentation approach, the structuring is an emergent task that will be approached through active intermediation between top-down/bottom-up expectations and aspirations regarding knowledge production and application, situational onboarding of human and non-human participants of Observatories (e.g., technologies, tools, discourses) and dissemination activities targeting the enhancement of situated intelligence for innovating policy making through public engagement.

In the following, we outline the status quo and point towards implications for a further strategic and effective development of the Academy in relation to its conceptual and technical infrastructure which is key for developing the GREENGAGE methodology on Observatories.

6.1 The Academy as mission-led framework: infrastructure for public engagement and regulation of access

The Academy is set up and will be equipped and maintained as collaborative environment for performing the GREENGAGE Innovation Action and is as conceptual and technical framework replicable beyond the project. It should contain the main knowledge assets and tools needed for operationalising GREENGAGE Observatories in the PILOTING phase and enable the COLLECTIVE LEARNING across pilots and communities in GREENGAGE. As it targets to bring into being GREENGAGE Innovation Pilots, the Academy needs to ensure that knowledge assets are widely available to aid citizen science experiments within GREENGAGE Observatories. This is achieved by two interrelated interfaces of the Academy: The Knowledge Base published at the project's website make one interface of the Academy which is accessible for the wider public. This dimension of the Academy is disseminating outcomes of the COLLECTIVE LEARNING on situated experimentation in pilots and across them in the Innovation Action. The GREENGAGE Collaborative Environment (CE) together with the GREENGAGE Toolbox and specific knowledge assets or Observatory Enablers acting as "co-production fuel" make the other interface of the Academy which is accessible for onboarded and trained participants of GREENGAGE Observatories. This dimension is supporting the co-creation of knowledge assets, driven by the GREEN Engine (suite of community-led, co-production process and data workflow management tools comprising the whole GREENGAGE platform) which is hosted by DEUSTO⁵ (layer of community and process organisation) and VRVIS (layers of data capture, storage, analysis and visualisation) and therefore only accessible when already being part of a GREENGAGE Observer's community. The GREENGAGE CE works to support the objective of structuring situated experimentation and collective learning and applying knowledge assets interdependently with the intention to enable iterative processes of knowledge co-creation in GREENGAGE Observatories (by using tools from the Toolbox and knowledge assets from the Knowledge Base to apply for data collection, analysis and visualisation) and producing further knowledge assets to be published on the Knowledge Base.

6.2 Academy's role in the GREENGAGE emerging innovation ecosystem

The GREENGAGE Academy potentially plays a powerful role in GREENGAGE governance and policy labs, as it seeks to ensure that Observatories are developed within the frameworks that were assembled by consortium partners during the PREPARING stage of the Innovation Action. Frameworks here make the conceptual and technological infrastructure of the Innovation Action that intends to support and guide Observatories so these might expand into useful containers for participatory research and action towards policy and governance innovation. In practical terms, the Academy engages with participants of localised governance and policy labs and organises knowledge co-production and application within their specific Observatories and across these to enable real world interventions based on situated intelligence. As such, **the Academy's task is not only to coordinate the activities and processes of the GREENGAGE Observatories, but to do so in ways that ensure these data-driven experiments are responsive to situational understandings generated in localised and place-based living labs.** For the Observatories, it provides an access point to all the educational resources and guidelines to support undertaking of the pilot activities (e.g., through training and onboarding materials). Although the

⁵ As mentioned in the GAB meeting on 10/1/24, DEUSTO commits to host the different platforms on their servers and keep the GREENGAGE Collaborative Environment running over the project duration and 2-3 years after lifetime to be available to use in the pilot's locations. After that, potential users would need to pay to continue using it, which is mainly a matter of maintenance. The legacy of digital interaction platforms always also depends on people who are capable to maintain them. The benefit of storing the Collaborative Environment on the DEUSTO server is that, if needed in the future, interested parties can move all the software (including the database) to another server.

pilots are focussing on their own Observatories, the Academy needs to engage with the public beyond these to drive the exchange of information that is relevant for real world governance and policy innovation. Following this logic, the Academy can successfully deliver the GREENGAGE Innovation Action.

The GREENGAGE Academy seeks to build on the COLLECTIVE LEARNING of the experimentation in the different Observatories to support and document an emerging GREENGAGE innovation ecosystem. This is why the **application and reflection of the GREENGAGE methodology to Observatories**, the **dissemination of knowledge assets in the Knowledge Base** and Toolbox and the **enabling the replicability** of the GREEN Engine comprise the second set of tasks of the Academy, which will be performed in different interaction platforms and documented on the website. By reflecting on the process of co-creating GREENGAGE Observatories through published deliverables, papers, success stories, findings and best practices collected from the five GREENGAGE pilots, the Academy will engage with those who are interested in policy innovation as a result of GREENGAGE Observatories (defined as community of practice) and with those beyond in the distinctive community of interests who wants to apply citizen-centred, community-led Observatories to drive the delivery of European Green Deal objectives (defined also as community of interest). By disseminating knowledge assets in accessible and visually appealing ways, the Academy will support the community of interest in the setting up and effective coordination of Observatories in different places. The Academy will also interact with the GREENGAGE community of practice through sharing MOOCs and success stories and hosting a forum.

Thinking of GREENGAGE Innovation Action as an innovation ecosystem, the GREENGAGE Academy will not only be key to deliver five Pilots, but further enables capacity building that goes beyond the GREENGAGE project to support a community-led performance of the European Green Deal objectives through Observatories that engage with the local public through policy and innovation labs.

6.3 Key co-creators and core user types of the Academy

Considering the above description of the Academy’s role in the GREENGAGE innovation ecosystem, we name key types of co-creators and differentiate them from core user types of the Academy. The engagement with these target groups will follow the principle of Situational Onboarding. Key types of co-creators of the Academy

Co-creators of the Academy are those who set up and maintain the conceptual and technological infrastructure of the Academy as well as those who will participate in knowledge co-production and application by joining the Collaborative Environment.

- GREENGAGE Observatory Coordinators, responsible for the infrastructural development of the Academy (e.g., PSTs and dedicated to ad hoc working groups, WP leads composed by consortium partners).
- GREENGAGE Observatory Participants, engaging in the learning and creation of knowledge assets (e.g., Observers, Moderators who will make the set conceptual and technological infrastructure meaningful to drive innovation).

Core user types

- Users here are encompassing all the above actors that are using knowledge assets and tools that are accessible for onboarded participants of Observatories. Beyond that, there are end-users that will only have access to those assets published in the Knowledge Base and Toolbox.
- Interested public, e.g., academia, public authorities, NGOs and communities that want to adopt the GREENGAGE approach to adapt in their contexts.
- Different stakeholders of Observatories and wider policy and governance labs, interested in: i) engagement mechanisms and approaches to involve and motivate different social groups; ii) data and findings generated through our four pilots and iii) exemplary use cases generated from the pilots' experiences, including the set of tools implemented from the GREEN Engine.
- Participating Observers engaged in Observatories: they will target training material and manuals (MOOCs) including scientific work training, toolbox introduction and state of the knowledge and problem statement related to the pilot areas. These materials are created, and they are used to train citizen observers.

Figure 2: Evolving Communities through collaborating collective actors and their interplay in co-creating and applying GREENGAGE CO knowledge assets.

This graphic depicts the different collaborating actors and their interplay in co-creating and applying tools and knowledge assets with, for and about GREENGAGE Observatories. We understand collaboration happening among and across collective actors organised in different working groups, informal collective actors such as different kinds of communities, defined individual actors that are significant for active intermediation with Pilots and the delivery of the Innovation Action as such. By their collaborative experimentation they help to activate, deliver and sustain Observatories that are situated in five different pilots and throughout their collaboration facilitate the evolvement or improvement of different kinds of communities. We expect that through making and applying discourses and tools in their different realms of action, place-based communities as well as communities of interest and practice together with Observatories enable meaningful collective action for the delivery of the Green Deal across the evolving Pan-European GREENGAGE innovation ecosystem.

The graphic aims to make visible existing overlaps and potential formations of situated collective actors and showcases how their collaboration can enable local, place-based communities, communities of interest and communities of practice to perform the New Green Deal with the help of GREENGAGE knowledge assets and tools as well as with lessons learned from setting up and running Observatories in a transformative living lab approach. It should help the Observatory coordinators to effectively organise the situational onboarding and enabling of Observatory participants that aim to get the right people on board at the right time and leave no one behind. Making explicit not only organised (e.g., civic

action groups) but also informal collective actors (e.g., families) can help to ensure that the invitation to participate is tailored and addresses people as members of distinctive societal groups that matter for driving socio-political impact. The visualisation should further serve as a means for the the project coordinator as well as the members of the IAB and the PSTs to consider diverse collective actors as potentially meaningful for making and using knowledge assets and tools when forming ad hoc working groups. By visualising the individual actors that are bridging between different working units and communities (PST leads, Observatory moderators, GREENGAGE Ambassadors) the graphic functions to define tasks and responsibilities in the development of engagement strategies and thus is relevant for the strategic development of the Academy and setting up local GOs. Further, it can be used as orientation to reflect on, and importantly to address existing power relations and social hierarchies. Social hierarchies are evolving through the coordination of the situated experimentation process and powerful roles of bridging actors are expected to significantly affect the outcomes of active intermediation with Pilots and the delivery of the Innovation Action as a whole.

As the graphic shows, the GREENGAGE Pilots are encompassing not only the GREENGAGE Observatories but will also be brought into being by the IAB, the PST, ad hoc working groups and the evolving or improving communities. What the graphic does not show are the technologies and discourses that – beside the human actors – are effectively participating in the activities and processes of the situated experiments and thus shaping the pilots. In GREENGAGE we understand that **the participants of Observatories are GREENGAGE Observers, local planning agents, members of the PSTs and other stakeholders that are actively contributing to the realisation of Observatories.** Beyond human actors we see technologies and knowledge assets as actively shaping Observatories. Building on feminist perspectives in science and technology studies, we understand that humans do not drive change by themselves but through their interactions with technologies and discourses (Clarke et al. 2018, p. 70). A broader understanding of participants is useful for addressing the existing power relations that shape open innovation ecosystems such as GREENGAGE Observatories and to reflect on the use of technologies and knowledge assets that should serve localised socio-ecological change, not market interests. It is through the interplay of these different participants based on active intermediation that GREENGAGE Pilots are made which goes along with methodological implications for their further descriptions.

In the core of GREENGAGE Pilots are the GREENGAGE Observatories. These Observatories are ethically framed activities and processes happening in situated, mission-led and data-based experiments. They enable different kinds of communities to produce and apply distinctive sets of tools and knowledge assets to co-create thematic explorations based on defined use cases with the purpose to inform policy innovations and other interventions that deliver the New Green Deal in their local contexts of urban planning. As Observatories are politically engaged, situated experiments, their stakeholders are neither neutral bystanders nor the owners of a situation but rather people with a vested interest in the process or activity of Observatories. As the processes and activities of Observatories are addressing critical problems such as environmental change and weak democratic governance, the co-creation of these experiments requires localised intelligence and individuals that can become responsible for the outcomes of an intervention. **Stakeholder can be a way of describing how relationships which are already in place can be understood to constitute a sphere of action. It is an open category that depicts those individuals and organisations that are already or might become involved in delivering the Green New Deal by the means of Observatories.** “It [is] simultaneously a description, an invitation, and a potentiality” (Knox, 2020, p. 220). As one of the GREENGAGE objectives is to deliver a more widespread participation of citizens in urban governance processes, **there are distinctive target groups that are invited to join the Observatories as GREENGAGE Observers. Generally spoken, these target groups are civic action groups and civic associations, women, marginalised groups⁶ (such as people of colour, children, people that belong to the LBGTQ+ community, single parents, etc.), disadvantaged populations and disabled persons.** As we are applying an intersectional approach on participatory research, we suggest to especially focus on the engagement with marginalized groups and see that prioritising their engagement is important for their meaningful participation. Meaningful participation requires being in powerful

⁶ Marginalised groups are “Different groups of people within a given culture, context and history at risk of being subjected to multiple discrimination due to the interplay of different personal characteristics or grounds, such as sex, gender, age, ethnicity, religion or belief, health status, disability, sexual orientation, gender identity, education or income, or living in various geographic localities” (European Institute of Gender Equality). Who can be understood as being part of a marginalised group differs across situations and therefore Observatory coordinators need to identify who in their socio-political context will be directly affected by the local policy innovations of the pilot but is usually underrepresented in participatory science and urban planning processes.

positions in the co-design of data-based experiments. Therefore, we suggest to tailor invitations in forms that are aesthetically appealing and accessible for those members of marginalised groups, that we want to have on board in the beginning stages of PILOTING within these experiments and in positions where they are listened to when use cases are defined and thematic co-explorations are designed.

Roles, tasks and responsibilities of participants in GREENGAGE Observatories

The human participants of Observatories embody different roles within the Observatory activities and processes that go along with certain tasks and responsibilities. These roles can change, be named with pilot specific terms and Observatory participants can take different roles at the same time. Nevertheless, it is important to clearly define the tasks and responsibilities that go along with these roles. This can be a topic for the GREENGAGE training programme if the current Observatory coordinators see this need. The **Observatory coordinators** are those participants of Observatories that ensure the delivery of the GREENGAGE Innovation Action through the five pilots (e.g., Pilot Owners, Pilot Support Team members, Moderators of Observatories). To demonstrate innovation, Observatory coordinators organise knowledge co-production and application in active intermediation between top-down expectations defined by the Innovation Action Board and bottom-up expectations defined by the participants of the Observatories. The Observatory coordinators regulate Observatories by providing tailored methodologies for co-creation, communication platforms, templates, checklists, surveys, consent forms and frameworks for pilot specification. Some of them are setting up and maintaining the infrastructures for onboarding and enabling newcomers or people that already engage in the Observatory to become GREENGAGE Observers. Some are focussing on an effective structuring of the experimentation and the delivery of the thematic co-explorations that take place in these. Some are responsible for defining targeted groups, individuals and organisations specific to their experiments and inviting them to become stakeholders of the Observatories. The **Pilot Owners** are constituted by project partners placed in the pilot's localities, that we previously named as local planning agents. From a radical democratic perspective, we see the potential for other stakeholders becoming pilot owners too, which could be important for sustaining the evolving Observatory information system and sharing power and responsibilities e.g., in form of climate commissions, urban health councils and similar platforms that have started to enable an integration of top-down and bottom-up climate action into the broader development of the place. As the pilot owners know the pilot's situation best and are already part of or at least know their local governance processes they are important in bridging interests of different stakeholders as well as maintaining all in-situ relationships. This is why they need to validate all relevant conceptualisations and have the "last word" in decisions related to the specification and co-design of their own GREENGAGE pilot. To bring their experiential knowledge into the project the Pilot Owners are part of the **Pilot Support Teams (PST)** and the **Innovation Action Board (IAB)** too. The IAB should steer the PSTs and monitor the Innovation Action and ensure that the Observatories are progressing as intended. The IAB is the place for all important decisions related to the overarching goal of delivering five Innovation Pilots and a replicable GREENGAGE approach on Observatories and therefore is constituted by members of the consortium who bring in the relevant expertise to make complex decisions (e.g., technological, citizen science, urban planning and policy making). The IAB is composed by the project coordinator and currently consists of 22 colleagues. As a multidisciplinary group interested in responding to a challenge of common interest by considering different expertise, it can become a community of interest. For this to happen in a democratic way, it needs inclusive but still effective ways of decision-making as well as the communication of these towards the PSTs. The focus of the IAB should not be to discuss the pilot's situations in detail, but providing backend support for PSTs when they need it and gather the right information at the right time (e.g., in relation to deliverables). To make use of the embodied expertise on citizen science, technological know-how and urban planning and policy making in situated, interdisciplinary understandings of the complex and changing situation of pilots. To achieve situated understandings in systematic ways, the methodologies of how they exchange information matters. Bringing in social scientific approaches such as Situational Analysis is demanding but required to find methods of intersubjective value to support the situated understanding. Otherwise, we lose the potential of delivering situated understandings based on collective, interdisciplinary intelligence. As mentioned in the beginning of this chapter, the PILOTING stage requires a much closer, ongoing exchange about the situation in the pilots within the PSTs. There are PSTs for each of the five pilots in place to support them in all aspects for further developing their specified use cases and activating functioning GREENGAGE Observatories. This is why the members of the PSTs need to learn the pilot specific situations in depth, so that they can respond to upcoming challenges with truly suitable solutions that might not come up to the table if the understanding is superficial. To enable the consortium

partners to make time for that deep and ongoing learning of the context and the pilot’s conditions was one of the main objectives for establishing PSTs. Now, this ambition must be realised which is the joint responsibility of **PST leads** who coordinate the exchange and decide what matters to be understood better based on a double leadership model including technological expertise as well as social scientific knowledges. For a start, this exchange is coordinated by the GREENGAGE project coordinator and PST leads who are establishing regular PST Jour-Fix meetings for all PSTs that will take place every three weeks unless changes are required. It can become important to organise site visits for supporting with co-creation activities or delivering training where distinctive expertise cannot be delivered by pilot owners or other stakeholders. To accommodate the PST Jour-Fixes, the project coordinator hosts IAB meetings that are in place to organise supportive actions in response to the updated understandings of the changing situation in pilots and to support the PSTs in making and applying tools and knowledge assets with, for and about the pilot’s Observatories. For the starting period of the Observatories, the IAB meets weekly. This might be reduced when we see the Observatories run as planned.

The task of the **Observatory Moderators** is to facilitate the generation of “intersubjectively valued” (McFarlane, 2011, Conclusion) understandings of the situations that GREENGAGE experiments are embedded in. In a process of transdisciplinary experimentation, they help “bringing everyone on the same page” and then going beyond that together. The direction of that journey is generally given by the envisioned outcomes of pilots and further specified by the defined use cases. In ethically framed experiments moderators are important for the cultivation of collective reflexivity: In contrast to ideas of “neutral moderators”, we suggest understanding moderation as a tool to organize the process of collective meaning making in a participatory research project and due to our ambition to democratize knowledge production, it seems appropriate to critically reflect on the practice and impact of this powerful position and to share the responsibility e.g., through frequently passing on the role to other participants of the Observatories (Costa Carneiro, 2024). In GREENGAGE Observatories an important role is that of **GREENGAGE Observers**. These are onboarded, trained participants of GREENGAGE Observatories that meaningfully contribute to thematic co-explorations with the purpose to drive policy innovations or other local interventions. All the stakeholders of Observatories can become Observers. Certain Observers can become **GREENGAGE Observer Ambassadors** that promote know-how to other audiences targeting especially those groups that rarely engage in participatory processes. The most active Observers and/or Observer Ambassadors will be invited to visit other pilot cities to meet other Observatories and learn from each other’s experiences and knowledges. All the different stakeholders of an Observatory can form **ad hoc working groups** to investigate a topic together (in the sense of focus groups), to co-design an intervention or to set up a training programme, as it is happening at the time this deliverable is written. **Communities of place, interest and practice** can emerge on every level of knowledge creation and sharing. Nevertheless, on the project level a community of interest is the most likely and a community of practice the ideal (as we want to innovate the approach on Observatories). In general, the potential for community building through knowledge co-creation, communication and dissemination seems the biggest on the level of the pilot locations as place can work as a catalyst for collective action.

6.4 Developing the Academy alongside the situated experimentation process

In the following we outline the methodology for developing the Academy together with certain participants of Observatories that are onboarded, trained and equipped with tools and knowledge assets provided by the Academy that help them to meaningfully engage in activities and processes of situated experimentation in Observatories.

The situated experimentation process for developing the GREENGAGE Innovation Action as a living lab is an updated version of the “GREENGAGE process for developing GREENGAGE Observatories as a living lab” (D2.1) that was orientating co-creation across consortium partners within the PREPARING stage of the GREENGAGE Innovation Action. An update was needed as the original graphic was often perceived differently to its intended meaning. It was further needed to integrate conceptualisations from the PREPARING stage to specify and translate the process to be applied in the Collaborative Environment, so it can guide and support activities of making and using knowledge assets from GREENGAGE Observatories in active intermediation with the situation in pilots. At this moment of the Innovation Action, the process is highlighting the aspects relevant for the operationalisation of prepared Observatories. As the basic process for developing pilot specific Observatories and by extension the GREENGAGE Innovation Action, it now informs other illustrations that show pathways for co-creating and applying GREENGAGE Knowledge Assets. Wherever possible, it refers to

methodological implications and gives practical recommendations for co-creating and applying knowledge assets from GREENGAGE Observatories.

To cater for the successful delivery of the GREENGAGE project and the fulfilment of the pilot expectations, we are pursuing a phased approach for developing GREENGAGE Observatories and an agile/iterative approach to learn across the pilots and improve activities. Given our vision and mission for developing Observatories based on situated experimentation towards informing transformative policy making (D2.1), we integrate these expectations and relate the two approaches to each other within one graph.

This graph depicts the development of GREENGAGE Observatories and the GREENGAGE Academy as developed alongside the process of situated experimentation in pilots. **Situated experimentation is structured by the three continuous stages of PREPARING, PILOTING and COLLECTIVE LEARNING and facilitated via active intermediation, which is subject to the ongoing evaluation and alignment with the complex and changing situation in pilots.** Active intermediation is happening through ongoing activities of conceptualising and sharing in dialogue with the situation in pilots and materialised by GREENGAGE Knowledge Base, Toolbox and White Book that are based on the situated understanding about the development of the Innovation Action as a whole and the different Pilots. These activities give meaning to the situated experimentation approach of GREENGAGE on Observatories, so that it remains:

- **meaningful** to GREENGAGE Observers,
- **applicable** for identified actors and stakeholders in the Innovation Action, and
- **replicable** for other project partners beyond GREENGAGE.

The situationist and experimentative nature of the approach is supported by the produced Knowledge Base and Toolbox part of the GREENGAGE Academy. Engaging with the knowledge assets will be essential for emerging communities of practice to perform localised pilot innovation in their pilots.

Figure 3: Situated Experimentation Process for developing GREENGAGE Innovation Action as a Living Lab.

In the following, we describe the generic co-production processes which will populate the Collaborative Environment and their outcomes:

- **Situated experimentation** requires and therefore starts with generating an understanding of the situation in pilots, that is communicated by the local planning agents, GREENGAGE Observers, and other stakeholders to initiate active intermediation.

- **Active intermediation** here refers to a set of interstitial practices, tools, and technologies that are deliberately applied in research and practice of the Innovation Action to ‘transform, translate, distort or modify the meaning’ (Latour, 2005, p. 30, cited in Perry & Smit, 2022, p. 688)⁷ of the situation in pilots. This set of assets for making meaningful changes through situated experimentation is as such composed and applied alongside the process of developing Observatories and intends to inform and to improve the situation by the outcomes that are intended by the pilots. The purpose of the creation and the use of these knowledge assets, tools and lessons learned is to situate the experimentation in the project’s objectives of demonstrating pilots that are delivering the Green New Deal through GREENGAGE Observatories and developing a replicable and sustainable approach on Observatories with and for the GREENGAGE Academy which is enabling wider long-term effects on society, environment, economy and science. This is why in GREENGAGE active intermediation supports a politically engaged way of learning the pilot’s socio-political contexts and of responding to these with GREENGAGE Knowledge Assets. Generally, use cases are specific situations in which a product or service could potentially be used. In GREENGAGE we experiment in localised, co-created (regional) planning.
- GREENGAGE Observatories are based on collective sense making alongside SITUATED EXPERIMENTATION driven by the ACTIVE INTERMEDIATION of issues that are identified by participants of Observatories as being meaningful to inform policy changes and governance innovation in the SITUATION IN PILOTS. The prefix ‘inter-’ is drawing attention to the intersubjectivity of understanding, which implies that instead of claiming certainties in the interpretation of the experimentation e.g., through the domination of certain perspectives, the project participants are learning to recognise that there are different perspectives that are relevant and therefore need to be considered for making sense of the process of SITUATED EXPERIMENTATION and its outcomes. Recognising different ways of knowing is key for driving co-creation of Observatories that is supposed to become a meaningful experience for different participants to sustain participation. Transdisciplinary knowledge co-production by different participants of Observatories is aiming for knowledge assets that are equally meaningful for different target groups and audiences to use. Meaningful co-creation in GREENGAGE is ethically framed by values of equity, diversity and inclusion and appreciates different perspectives as being important for informing localised innovation ecosystems that seek to drive changes towards social-ecological transformation. As social-ecological transformation requires widespread participation of citizens in the monitoring and protection of urban environments, it is important for the project to not only engage but to empower participants to become active contributors in the activities and processes of the situated experimentation upon understanding their meaning. In other words, GREENGAGE aims to empower citizen participation by onboarding and enabling participants to create and use GREENGAGE knowledge assets, tools and lessons learned to inform and drive meaningful governance policy innovation in pilot specific localities.
- Through SHARING, the active intermediation grounds the experimentation and makes activities and processes accessible for its participants. Ongoing activities of SHARING help to disseminate co-produced assets that actively intermediate the learnings from the experimentation in form of SITUATED UNDERSTANDING. **ACTIVE INTERMEDIATION through explicit practices, tools and technologies supports SITUATED UNDERSTANDING in the experimentation which is key to refine target audiences for the GREENGAGE assets.**
- **CONCEPTUALISING the set of GREENGAGE assets in ways that support the making of transformative changes is an ongoing activity.** This activity is important to define key activities and roles among the participants of the situated experimentation which helps to onboard the ‘right people’ and the ‘right technologies’ at the ‘right time’. As such it supports the GREENGAGE engagement methodology that seeks to meet participants where they are and get them on board when they can (see D2.1). The methodological principle of situational onboarding is applied through the ONBOARDING and training of participants that – when empowered with GREENGAGE tools and knowledge assets – can contribute to the monitoring

⁷ Beth Perry & Warren Smit (2023) Co-producing city-regional intelligence: strategies of intermediation, tactics of unsettling, *Regional Studies*, 57:4, 685-697, DOI:10.1080/00343404.2022.2044464

and protection of urban environments by generating insights about pilot specific localities that are needed for driving situated experimentation towards democratic revitalisation and sustainable policy innovation.

- By **CONCEPTUALISING** the **SITUATED UNDERSTANDING** of the experimentation e.g., through relating to issues of use cases, the experimentation discerns, tests, and adapts the set of interstitial practices, tools and technologies to become appropriate to inform and improve the **SITUATION IN PILOTS**.
- At the same time, ongoing activities of **CONCEPTUALISING** and **SHARING** feed into all stages of the process of developing the Innovation Action as a Living Lab in different localities to materialise the situated experimentation in form of **GREENGAGE** Observatories. **CONCEPTUALISING helps to define metrics, models and terms for interpretation of the activities and processes of coordinated experimentation towards informing transformative urban governance and policy making.** This is important for **PREPARING** Observatories, the stage of the iterative process that focuses on co-designing tools, use cases and technologies for **PILOTING**. **PILOTING (highlighted in orange) is about prototyping, testing, monitoring, gathering and making sense of data. Throughout SHARING activities during PILOTING, participants communicate actionable insights that are useful to address common concerns.** The **PILOTING** contributes to **COLLECTIVE LEARNING** that is about engaging in reflexive activities. Rather than looking back on past experiences to capture learnings through reflection, reflexive practices constitute a process of meta-learning that applies knowledges and theories to make sense of past activities (Hemström et al., 2021, p. 28) in **PREPARING** and **PILOTING**. Moderators of Observatories should ensure that the knowledges and theories that are applied for **CONCEPTUALISING** these activities are useful to support the situated understanding of pilot specific activities as well as of common activities. Besides, they need to ensure that the foils for collective theorising in the context of use cases consider pre-defined metrics, models, and terms for the interpretation of Pilots as well as the **GREENGAGE** approach on Observatories. **CONCEPTUALISING** these experiences together within reflexive practices enables **COLLECTIVE LEARNING** and ensures that the participants of Observatories are on the same page. Moderated reflexive activities that document the perspectives of participants with diverse backgrounds and roles in the Observatories can ensure that the **SITUATED UNDERSTANDING** of the experimentation is based on its transdisciplinary interpretation. This way, the co-production of **KNOWLEDGE ASSETS**, **TOOLBOX** and the **WHITE BOOK** can be based on solid knowledges. Solid in this context means, that knowledges are commonly accepted among the participants of the Innovation Action and beyond **GREENGAGE** and that they are reliable enough when it comes to informing further activities of co-producing assets for the **KNOWLEDGE BASE**. As we aim to apply an intersectional approach on research and co-creation, we suggest speaking about knowledges rather than knowledge to acknowledge the different ways in which knowledge can be produced. The **KNOWLEDGE ASSETS** together with the **TOOLBOX** empower **COLLECTIVE LEARNING** across the participants of pilot's Observatories and support capacity building of the evolving **GREENGAGE** community of practice. **The COLLECTIVE LEARNING stages enables mutual learning between those participants of the Innovation Action that exchange their understandings through SHARING activities and vice versa.** By grounding further activities of **CONCEPTUALISING** in reflexive practices of **COLLECTIVE LEARNING** ensures that the situated experimentation stays relevant for the Innovation Action and responsive to **GREENGAGE** ethical considerations. **COLLECTIVE LEARNING** within the specific Observatories enables the building of communities of interest which are **PREPARING** the next iteration of developing Observatories through situated experimentation.

Adaption of Situated Experimentation Process to the **COLLABORATIVE ENVIRONMENT**

Translated the above Situated Experimentation process into a schema process within the CE could help the IAB to (1) streamline the top-down/bottom-up expectations, (2) organise the situational onboarding of the participants to understand the delivery of the **GREENGAGE** Innovation Action in a Living Lab approach and (3) document the **GREENGAGE** methodology on Observatories.

The co-creation and use of GREENGAGE knowledge assets on the Collaborative Environment platform is structured by PREPARING, PILOTING and COLLECTIVE LEARNING and builds on information that is generated across pilots and different communities. It supports working across different activities of the working groups and helps the consortium to deliver their WP related tasks. It is the platform where the consortium collaborates in groups such as IAB and ad hoc working groups to co-create and apply knowledge assets with, for and about the GREENGAGE Innovation Action. It should support WP6 tasks of ongoing evaluation and learning across the pilots. For WP7 it can be important to organise the co-creation of knowledge assets about GREENGAGE and to further set the grounds for the replication and sustainability roadmap. WP5 can use it to prepare the operation of Observatories, e.g., through briefing PSTs and building up the Academy through active intermediation between tasks outlined in GA and the situation in pilots. The use in context of WP1 would be that this process guides the collaboration and co-creation among consortium partners, and therefore basically serves as a process-orientated project management tool that enable a collectively governed process throughout the GREENGAGE approach on Observatories.

6.5 Organising the co-production and application of knowledge assets

The GREENGAGE Academy will organise the co-production and application of knowledge assets on two levels, related to the GREENGAGE Innovation Action and related to the pilot-specific Observatories, and in an agile way through active intermediation with the situation in pilots. The definition and classification of use cases will be key for organising the co-production and application of knowledge assets and this will be developed with participants of Observatories. Besides, the focus on challenges as specified by local planning agents and other stakeholders of localised and place-based governance and policy labs can give pointers on how to structure the learning to produce meaningful outcomes. Further, the anticipated communities of interest and their languages will matter for classifying knowledge assets to support community-led innovation action. Nevertheless, the Grant Agreement sets certain expectations on knowledge production and dissemination that GREENGAGE needs to consider first when organising the co-production and application of knowledge assets.

6.5.1 Classifying types of knowledge co-creation and application

To provide useful orientation for how to develop and apply Observatory-related knowledge assets in line with our commitments in the Grant Agreement during PILOTING, the GREENGAGE Academy Roadmap needs to be aligned with related objectives and tasks that are planned for this phase in all WPs. In the following table we gathered information to help understand the requirements as outlined in the GA and to start identifying different types of knowledge assets.

General objectives and function of dissemination knowledge for the PILOTING phase

	Knowledge assets related to GREENGAGE Innovation Action	Knowledge assets related to pilot specific GOs
WP1		
WP2	Citizen Observatory governance framework, stakeholder engagement and requirements analysis	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • GREENGAGE CO Methodological Framework defines conceptual underpinnings for each Observatory • Piloting Use cases provide policy and environmental priorities where new data collection through COs may add value • Continuous management of requirements highlighting varying needs and priorities of pilots • Governance Models define varying approaches by pilots and will produce comparability with other EU cities
WP3	Knowledge assets that conceptualise the GREENGAGE approach	

	(methodology) on Observatories and foster its replication (e.g., GREENGAGE Academy Roadmap > Workbook)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Training materials for specific target groups of GOs that enable active participation in processes & activities of COs • Onboarding materials that support pilot owners and core group to reach out to required citizen segments and policy makers & make them commit to • Strategies to support building Observer teams
WP4	GREENGAGE co-creation process application for Innovation Action	<p>GREENGAGE co-creation process application for participants of Observatories and associated knowledge assets from GREENGAGE Academy:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Observer problem statement questionnaire • Co-production and CS process checklist • Observatory Specification • Resources and budget template • Core team assembly template • Observatory participants canvas • Ethics and inclusivity check • Data protocol specification • Observatory Data Management Plan • Contact channel and support team definition • Data quality and visualization (WeObserve) • Communication template to inform about Green Deal Challenges • Scientific Method and Citizen Science guideline • GREENGAGE Toolbox quickstarts • Manuals for data pipeline tool • Manual on sensor technology • Mixing authoritative and crowdsourced data training • Data charter for Citizen Science • Profiling questionnaire to select Observatory's ambassadors • Communication plan • Engagement plan • Piloting planning and evaluation checklist • Observatory launch communication • Monitor pilot progress guideline • Continuous engagement material • Analyse and interpret data guideline • Report results guideline • Template to publish datasets

		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Template to publish insights / results of Citizen Observatory • Observatory's KPIs achievement report • Data evidence to policy definition template • Sustainability long term plan template
WP5	Lessons learned from GREENGAGE Observatories experimentation and knowledge sharing	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Strategies to foster continued motivation among GO members • Scientific knowledges generated by pilots and their derivatives • Lessons learn during experiments in citizen science (e.g., methodology) • Knowledges on strategies for pilots' community building and knowledge sharing
WP6	A White Book for public authorities about lessons learnt, recommendations for uptake of GREENGAGE assets.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Pilot specific lessons learnt, recommendations for uptake of GREENGAGE assets for public authorities.
WP7	Dissemination Assets (GREENGAGE website, scientific and non-scientific publications, pilot success stories, webinars), GREENGAGE Replication and Sustainability Roadmap, International (Citizen-led) Community of Citizen Observers (CoCObs) as potentially independent living platform	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Pilot success stories (description of the specificities of the pilots, methods used to study the local context, relation with the engagement methods used, GREENGAGE tools selected for the pilot, description of the activities and campaigns designed and implemented in each pilot, data gathered, challenges encountered and solutions to counteract them) • Members of the international CoCObs will in part be pilot cities and their participating citizens • Best practices and lessons learnt from pilots will be a foundation of GREENGAGE Replication and Sustainability Roadmap

Besides that, a list of knowledge assets that materialise these objectives and tasks in the Academy has been gathered. For the agile strategy of developing the Academy, this overview shows that it's important to create a varied inventory that covers multiple bases. The focus of this deliverable is not on outlining specific tools for a local pilot, but on the steps and strategies necessary to set up an Observatory in different communities. Hence, an inventory of knowledge assets is a necessary step.

In a next step, these first classifications need to be aligned with the with pilot specific processes and specified e.g., through situated experiments related to WP5. To support the effective co-creation of these across pilots and communities a timeline showing the different knowledge assets in relation to the pilot specific CO participant journeys is required.

6.5.2 Co-creating knowledge assets in pilot specific localities: GREENGAGE Observatory Participant Journey

The **GREENGAGE Observer Journey** (Figure 4) depicts the generic process of newcomers or people that already participate in GREENGAGE Observatories, becoming GREENGAGE Observers and contributing to the co-creation of experiments situated in different locations. GREENGAGE Observers

are onboarded, trained participants of GREENGAGE Observatories that meaningfully contribute to thematic co-explorations with the purpose to drive policy innovations or other local interventions.

Figure 4: GREENGAGE Observer Journey.

The **GREENGAGE Observer Journey** starts with the following **general considerations** that need to be acknowledged at any stage of the process:

- Observers can join the journey at any stage after completing the Onboarding (Ethics) requirements.
- Privacy and data anonymisation are essential before reporting or publishing outcomes.
- Observers may not be involved in all stages of the Observer journey and consent withdrawal is possible at any stage. However, it may not be possible to withdraw the data that has been anonymised and aggregated with the rest of the Observatory data. The consent form should indicate the deadlines of withdrawal for specific data sets.

Onboarding is encompassing a set of interactions between Observatory coordinators and people that are interested in participating in activities and processes of the Observatory as Observers (see more in deliverable D3.2). Onboarding is realised when concluding the following steps:

- The GREENGAGE Observer Journey starts with an invitation to participate in the GREENGAGE Observatory.
- If the person is interested in GREENGAGE project, they need to register their interest and insert the following information, name, email, project-related interests, and relevant expertise in a digital form provided either through the GREENGAGE website or EU survey links or printed and filled in in person in the presence of the local planning agents on the ground of each pilot; this step is not consistent across pilots due to differences in organisation on the ground. The data will be then transferred and safely stored digitally, and a unique ID for each person will be generated. At this point, people will only sign up to receive further information about how to become a GREENGAGE Observer whilst anonymising any further collection of personal data from hereby on. They can also choose to sign up to pilot-specific newsletters or events, with the option to unsubscribe any time they wish to.
- If the person is also interested to become an Observer, then a 2nd point of interaction takes place: They are being sent all the information about pilot-specific Observatory participation, namely the Participant Information Sheet (PIS), Privacy Notice, and Participant Consent Form (PCF) to be read and filled in before becoming a GREENGAGE Observer.
- Once they agree on becoming a GREENGAGE Observer, a 3rd point of interaction takes place where the onboarded person is asked to fill in a survey with all their demographic information, e.g., age, occupation, gender etc. This survey and data collected will be discussed and to the extent this is permitted, harmonised across pilots.

Training is about enabling onboarded people to become GREENGAGE Observers (see more in deliverable D3.2). It is important that Observers get access to training for all the activities they are supposed to participate in and that training activities are part of at all stages of the process. GREENGAGE Observatory Coordinators (as defined in 6.3) need to develop training materials efficiently and responsive to the pilots' needs and aspirations for onboarding participants. Training materials might differ between materials for equipping participants with the knowledges on how to do research as Observers, materials for how to make use of outcomes from research and materials for collective learning across the pilots. The formulation of the materials needs to be adjusted to the local cultures and purposes for training. The first step for developing training materials is to understand the provided technologies, tools and practices of the consortium and identify the targeted participants in the different pilots. It is further recommended, that training is tailored to specific use cases and pilots and delivered in interactive manners. Once the participants have become Observers, they can explore and contribute to existing use cases. Beside the co-exploration of predefined use cases, **some Observatories will enable Observers to create additional use cases and shape all steps of their thematic co-exploration (functional requirements)**. There are various occasions in which this could happen, e.g., through workshops or council meetings/assemblies organised by municipal officers or during discussions on Discourse. Observers might identify new issues that matter for the community and the

pilot's objectives, that are worth investigating in the form of new use cases. In this optional case, the Observers would need to co-deliver collectively the following steps:

- Describe a new use case, including rationale, feasibility, pre- and post-conditions
- review available data and potential data gaps/requirements
- review relevance and applicability of available tools and knowledge assets,
- update existing or integrate new tools and knowledge assets to respond to new use case.

In any case, Observers will explore and develop existing use cases by becoming part of concept-**refining experiments and the related data collection process**. This process builds on:

- Data collection using GREEN Engine and Knowledge Base or other assets (technologies, apps, sensors, solid knowledges) outside the Academy.

Observers will be further invited to contribute to

- define the mission of the data collection (collectively)
- design experiments within the Observatories (collectively)
- generate data by participating in surveys or interviews (individually)
- generate data by participating in workshops or focus groups (collectively)
- organise data collection through other technologies, apps, sensors or knowledge assets outside the Academy e.g., Sensor Community.

Based on the collected and organised data sets, Observers will then take part in the collective **data analysis and visualisation process**. Together with other participants of the Observatories, they will:

- Deposit/upload data directly on the GREENGAGE cloud storage system or through the GREEN Engine tools,
- explore data and assess their quality and resolution,
- perform data analysis / analytics if the data quality standards are met.

The steps of data exploration and analysis are complemented and facilitated by data visualisation. At this point, it is important to be clear about the intended use of the outcomes as this has implications for the usefulness of the form of data visualisation. Based on the decision for a useful form of data visualisation, it might become necessary to engage additional/other stakeholders who carry inherent knowledge of place and may have more impact on actualising changes on the ground. These stakeholders may have already been identified in the PREPARING stage of the pilot specification process and may involve policy makers, specialised scientists, artists, influencers or representatives of activist groups. Once the data are analysed and visualised, GREENGAGE Observers can participate in deriving conclusions, translating data into concrete actions, whilst deciding on next steps or (re)formulating a local action plan.

Observers are also invited to participate in the **evaluation and impact assessment**. Evaluation and impact assessment occur during all stages of the process and focus on reflexive practices that can be performed through questionnaires/surveys, interviews, workshops and other evaluation exercises. In consideration of the co-creation logic, these exercises are contributing to the collective learning stage of the development of the Observatories and help to refine the GREENGAGE approach on Observatories.

Based on the collective learning about the use cases in relation to the pilot's socio-political context and their objectives, Observers are enabled to **make use of the GREENGAGE Observatory outcomes together with other stakeholders of the Observatories to initiate other local actions or help contribute to policies, amongst other possibilities**.

6.5.3 Developing GREENGAGE dissemination assets: Knowledge Base, Toolbox, and White Book

While in the PREPARING stage of the Innovation Action the Academy was set up together with partners with different expertise (ICT, Citizen science, environmental science, etc.), it will start in the PILOTING stage of the Innovation Action by being co-created by different participants of GREENGAGE Observatories alongside the process of PREPARING, PILOTING and COLLECTIVE LEARNING on GREENGAGE Observatories that happens across pilots and different kinds of communities. Co-creation will happen in active intermediation with the pilot specific Observatories that are developed and performed in five different localities and their use case specific GREENGAGE Participant Journeys. Supported by WP7, the project partners are working across different activities in existing and evolving working groups to co-create knowledge assets and apply the GREENGAGE Academy as GREENGAGE Knowledge Base and Toolbox.

Based on recommendations from D3.3 amongst others, WP1 will provide guideline for knowledge assets (documents, data, media created and used within GREENGAGE) and WP7 will give suggestions on how to co-create these in form of different 'journeys for co-creation of knowledge assets and work on the sustainability of project assets within T7.5.

In GREENGAGE, dissemination assets and knowledge assets represent distinct facets of information sharing, each catering to specific audiences and purposes within the realm of knowledge transfer. Dissemination assets primarily pertain to the scientific community, encapsulating the various channels and methods used to share and disseminate scholarly output. These may include research papers and conference presentations, each aimed at contributing to the existing body of knowledge within a particular field. On the other hand, knowledge assets are strategically crafted to engage and educate the general public, transcending the specialized language often inherent in scientific discourse. These assets are designed to bridge the gap between complex research findings and public understanding, utilizing accessible formats and voicing.

During the project, all these resources will be created and stored in the GREENGAGE website, making them accessible for everyone. All the resources will be presented in an educational manner by simplifying its contents and adapting the language by avoiding use of formalisms/technicisms.

To become accessible for everyone, the GREENGAGE website (see deliverable D3.1 for more details) will be undergoing major restructuring and repurposing to serve as the entry point for the Observatory participants facilitating registration and easy access to the GREENGAGE Knowledge Assets and Toolbox, however these changes will be gradual with implementation starting early January 2024.

Figure 5: High-level process for co-developing the GREENGAGE Dissemination Assets.

6.6 GREENGAGE Infrastructure for knowledge co-creation and application: Interaction platforms, participants, roles and information flows

Participants of the GREENGAGE Observatories engage with the GREENGAGE framework and the participants of the innovation ecosystem through different interaction platforms, in distinctive system roles to contribute to information flows that ultimately perform the “Innovation Pilots” and the GREENGAGE Innovation Action as a whole.

Figure 6: Knowledge co-creation and application in active intermediation between GREENGAGE Innovation Action (GA) and situation in Pilots.

Figure 6 depicts where interaction of project participants happens and how the information flows to deliver the GREENGAGE IA as a whole and to develop use cases as the backbone of pilot specific Observatories as well as specific interventions within local governance and policy labs as the outputs of Observatories. In the PILOTING stage the top-down logic that defined the 1st iteration of this graphic⁸

⁸ The graphic is an updated version of a former representation of different collaborating units and their imagined interplay in co-creating GREENGAGE Observatories. The initial version was created in the beginning of the PREARING stage and was supposed to orientate the iterative information flow between the Innovation Action Board (IAB) and five different Pilot Support Teams (PSTs) to conceptualize and test the GREENGAGE co-creation logic (as being based on the active intermediation between top-down/bottom-up expectations, situational onboarding and a transformative living lab approach): The initial conceptualisation asked the IAB in a first iteration to define what information is needed from the situation in pilots and would then ask the PST to deliver the needed information. In a second iteration the IAB would respond to that information with ad hoc

needs to change in favour of a bottom-up logic for the active intermediation with the situation in pilots. Based on the validated specifications of pilots and their planned Observatories and other conceptualisations from D3.3, the PSTs should support the Pilots' Observatories in their activities and processes of prototyping, testing, monitoring, gathering and making sense of data. This requires a much closer, ongoing exchange about the situation in the pilots within the PSTs.

The information flow starts from the communication channels and interaction platforms that are in place by now and applies the GREENGAGE logic of co-creation (situated living labs, situational onboarding, active intermediation between top-down/bottom-up expectations). The description of the graphic goes beyond that to - where possible – shows how to organise the interplay of different interaction platforms in ways that ensure an information flow in support of meaningful and effective co-creation and application of GREENGAGE knowledge assets that want to be user for governance and policy innovation.

- The information flow relevant for pilot's Observatory is starting by interacting with potential *Observers and other stakeholders of the local governance and policy labs* through the *communication channels* that are existing in pilots. There are *digital* (such as websites, newsletters) and *analogue* channels (such as face-to-face conversations) that are already in place and used by local planning agents to reach out to potential participants of local governance and policy labs – or pilot owners, and to *inform* about *and invite* participants to Observatory related activities and processes. As such, the interplay between these is key for *activating and organising participation in Observatories*.
- *Digital interaction platforms* are ranging from complex interfaces (such as commonplace) to platforms used in everyday life (such as WhatsApp). *Analogue* ways for sharing and gathering information are especially important to include groups in Observatories with few or no digital literacy or access to devices. Digital channels in combination with analogue means for the interaction between participants of Observatories (such as public events) are further helping to *gather first information for specific citizen science (CS) campaigns or other interventions* in the context of the pilot's Observatory. It is important to consider analogue channels as relevant for the co-creation of use cases, CS campaigns and related interventions as this could have implications for the documentation, digitalisation and further flow of information that is gathered in these (e.g., on flipcharts, post-its, surveys).

Together, these interaction platforms are established, run and maintained by pilot owners. It is their responsibility to decide which information finds its way to the Academy. An inclusive, use case orientated interpretation of the information generated within the different interaction platforms (analogue and digital) can help to decide, which information should find its ways into the situated experiments. The curation of this information is done by moderators of the Observatories who decide which information is needed to drive the co-production of GREENGAGE knowledge assets towards outcomes that are relevant for the use cases:

- The information flow related to the Academy starts with selected information from local governance and policy labs that contextualise use case specific citizen science campaigns. The data for the latter will be generated through the GREENGAGE app. The app has the function to simplify and centralise the data collection process and generates information that is needed to develop the use cases. (The data generated by GREENGAGE app is currently stored at decentralised servers provided by consortium partners but were possible is aimed to be centralised with open-source licences.)
- Beyond that, GREENGAGE provides the forum app Discourse to facilitate the *ongoing dialogue between different participants of Observatories* and supports with setting up a landing page (Wordpress) to *keep relevant stakeholders informed*. Discourse enables moderated conversations that can be *structured alongside different topics that are relevant for the co-*

support and with generic recommendations based on the understanding of the pilot's situation. To validate the IAB's conceptualisations and to ensure they are useful for the preparation of five different pilots, the PSTs were asked to give feedback on the shared recommendations. This way we started to activate these two working units and organised their collaboration in a way that we hoped would ensure the effective and meaningful co-design of tools, use cases and technologies for GREENGAGE Observatories for PREPARING five GREENGAGE pilots that are based on defined metrics, models and terms for interpreting their situation.

creation of use cases, campaigns, and interventions by participants of Observatories. This way, moderators (e.g., members of the PSTs, including pilot owners) can curate and adopt information to the pilot specific processes hosted by the Collaborative Environment. The Collaborative Environment hyperlinks to the main stack of data processing and management tools (*Toolbox*) as well as to the GREENGAGE knowledge assets (*Knowledge Base*). As such, it applies the GREENGAGE Academy assets within the co-creation of CS campaigns and interventions and supports coherence in the development of Observatories across the pilots.

- The technical partners of PSTs use Planio to tackle upcoming issues that are related to the technological dimensions of use cases. The social science partners of PSTs tackle upcoming issues that are related to the required engagement aspects to develop the use cases.
- The situated experimentation is the process that structures the CS activities during PILOTING and is documented on the Collaborative Environment. As the GREENGAGE Observers will probably be interested in the interpretation and visualisation of data (instead of raw data), the content that is produced at a final stage of every thematic co-exploration should be adapted to platforms that are broadly accessible for Observers (e.g., Digitwin) so that dissemination can be performed within related campaigns/stories.
- Due to the interdisciplinary constitution of the use cases, the interpretation of information requires different expertise that should be embodied by dedicated moderators. The moderators can make use of the provided process schema that structures the thematic co-exploration to orientate the curation of content and guide the selection of information from all the platforms that are actively used by Observers and other stakeholders of the Observatories. It might be appropriate that members of the PSTs become moderators of the process of active intermediation (see Process of Situated Experimentation) to facilitate situated understanding of the pilots (e.g., through translating). At least, they will be responsible for setting up and maintaining the project related interaction platforms (Discourse, WordPress, Collaborative Environment) and provide guidance and support with applying the GREENGAGE tools that drive the operationalisation of Observatories. The PST leads are responsible for selecting information that is relevant for the GG IA as such, e.g., regarding the comparison of insights related to the use cases across the different pilots (lessons learned). To ensure the selected information includes different perspectives on the situation in pilots, the PST leads are composed interdisciplinary through at least one colleague with social scientific expertise and one colleague bringing in technological expertise.

Together, these participants perform roles system roles and interact on platforms to strategically support the information flow towards delivering “Innovation Pilots”.

- The information that is generated through the process of active intermediation with the situation in pilots and curated by PST leads is then stored on the Collaborative Environment in a schema based on the “process for situated experimentation for developing the GREENGAGE Innovation Action as a living lab”. Here, these pilot specific understandings about the development of Observatories are further compared with information that is conceptualising the GREENGAGE approach on COs (such as metrics, models, and terms). The IAB is governing this 3-stages process (PREPARING, PILOTING, COLLECTIVE LEARNING) which is specified by the objectives and tasks of each phase and grounded in the expectations defined by the GA, validated through active intermediation with the expectation in pilots (actively performed by PSTs) and refined through reflexive activities about the experiences in previous stages (at this point PREPARING). The Innovation Action Board (IAB) assembles information in the Collaborative Environment to document learnings across the pilots.
- Next to the PST members and the IAB members that use the Collaborative Environment, the project partners work on diverse digital platforms. They organise themselves in ad hoc working groups and collaborate within an Ethic Board as well as with an external Advisory board through support from MS teams and use MS SharePoint to store all project related work.

Together, these interaction platforms and their participants help the IAB to monitor the situated experimentation towards delivering the Innovation Action as a whole and make the GREENGAGE approach on Observatories replicable and sustainable.

6.7 GREENGAGE Academy Roadmap

Based on the above rationale, the GREENGAGE Academy Roadmap is visualised below (Figure 7), with a focus on its pathways to deliver Innovation Action and drive systemic changes with social, political and environmental impact. As GREENGAGE Observatories are based on critical urban and regional planning challenges, the Academy is set up and will be further structured to enable learning and dissemination of knowledges in response to these challenges.

Figure 7: GREENGAGE Academy Roadmap.

The REENGAGE Academy Roadmap encompasses tactics for building the Academy as enabler for building an open, community-led, data-driven innovation ecosystem and using it in support of creating knowledge assets for operationalising REENGAGE Observatories. It prioritises the tactics in form of a strategic order and relates them to the different dimensions of the Academy. It also depicts the meaning of these and reflects on the interrelatedness of the dimensions and pathways for innovation.

The REENGAGE Academy Roadmap also outlines the innovation logic in application to the strategic development of the Academy during the lifespan of the Innovation Action. We can now envision the Academy and identify the implications for the further development of its conceptual and technological infrastructure and guide the organisation of data-based experiments in Observatories according to this logic.

7 How do we want to get there: Designing the PILOTING phase

In the previous chapter we introduced and laid out fully the concept of GREENGAGE Academy which will serve as a conceptual, methodological and technical infrastructure to support the GREENGAGE Observatories. Although GREENGAGE Pilots were mentioned, the process was described in a non-pilot specific manner to provide a conceptual and practical framework for the entire GREENGAGE approach to Citizen Observatories that is useful both for the next steps of the GREENGAGE project as well as for those communities of interest outside the project. What is essential to do next is to address the application of this framework into the specific context of the five GREENGAGE Pilots.

In what follows, we discuss **how the GREENGAGE Academy can respond to bottom-up expectations and aspirations for specific pilots**. We look closely into the five GREENGAGE Innovation Pilots, giving a detailed update on their situation, their plans for knowledge co-creation and application, their smart governance model and technical requirements as these were reported previously in deliverables like D2.4 and D2.6. The aim is to see how the situated approach of GREENGAGE Academy applies according to the situation in each pilot. Each pilot specification follows the same structure. It starts with providing a background, describing relevant socio-political context that helps understand the situation within which Observatories will operate. It then reviews the vision, expected impacts, and timeline of their GREENGAGE Observatory after adaptation of the generic GREENGAGE Participant Journey diagram (see section 7.2.2) for each pilot. The next sections explain the main stakeholders and target groups of the Observatories, and their inter-sectional dynamic collaborations are visualised as a slice of the generic GREENGAGE pie chart (see section 7.3), which demonstrated how evolving communities can participate in the production of knowledge assets. Each pilot specification is then completed with an overview of existing use cases addressed by the pilot-specific Observatories, the data required, and the GREEN Engine tools employed for each use case.

It is worth mentioning that the GA asks for an **overarching strategy** (presented in chapter 6) that is **agile** enough to respond to particularities of the pilots and **streamlined** to meet the GREENGAGE objectives (see what follows in Chapter 7), so that the project can identify common actions that favour the applicability of the outcomes in other venues (a first iteration to be attempted in Chapter 8). To ensure agility, the contextual (pilot-specific) application and testing of the overarching strategy needs to be continued throughout the different stages of the process of co-creation (PREPARING, PILOTING, COLLECTIVE LEARNING) and in every iteration of this process. As an outcome of each iteration, a set of guidelines and reflections can be extracted to feed into both the COLLECTIVE LEARNING phase and the incremental drafting of the GREENGAGE White Book as co-produced knowledge asset. To further validate and streamline this process, these ongoing reflections should constantly be shared in different languages according to the audiences we seek to address every time.

7.1 Bristol

7.1.1 Background and Context

The East Bristol Liveable Neighbourhood pilot is in the inner east of Bristol with geographical coverage 1.7 sq. km. It has approximately 6000 properties and businesses within the area.

This pilot is embedded in the Bristol City Council's vision for the East Bristol Liveable Neighbourhood scheme (EBLN) which seeks to empower local communities to transform their neighbourhoods into places that provide better access to green and play space, more seamless and convenient connections to local amenities using sustainable forms of travel, and more space for social and community activity.

Liveable Neighbourhoods are areas of a city where improvements are designed in partnership with local communities to achieve a better balance between how streets are used for vehicles and people. In June 2021 Bristol's Citizens' Assembly called for our neighbourhoods to be reimagined so that they are people-centred and more 'liveable', meaning they are safe, healthy, inclusive, and attractive places where everyone can breathe clean air, have access to better quality green and play space, and feel a part of a community.

Rolling out two Liveable Neighbourhood pilot projects are Mayoral priorities for Bristol, with the East Bristol Liveable Neighbourhood being the first scheme to be piloted in the city.

A strategic walking and cycling route, the Wesley Way, in east Bristol was identified along Beaufort Road through St George, Redfield and Barton Hill (Bristol/South Gloucester Route 3) in the Local Cycling and Walking Infrastructure Plan (LCWIP).

The West of England Combined Authority (WECA) has provided funding to use an area-wide approach to develop a Low Traffic Neighbourhood (Liveable Neighbourhood), rather than just design linear infrastructure for route improvements. The project area covers parts of five wards of Bristol: Lawrence Hill, Easton, St George West, St George Central and St George Troopers Hill, south of Church Road and north of the River Avon.

In January 2024, Bristol Administration approved to advertise the Traffic Regulation Order (TRO) for the full EBLN scheme. It is due to begin late January.

Socio-political context

Currently, there are the following challenges:

- A climate and ecological emergency articulated by local and national plans require widespread citizen participation to deliver the set goals of social-ecological transformation in the city. The pilot's work within the EBLN is supporting BCC's ambition of becoming Carbon Neutral by 2030.
- LN schemes offer a promising pathway for community-led urban transformation beyond the pilot's area of intervention if they are recognized and accepted by local communities and municipalities. However, Liveable Neighbourhoods have been controversial in some areas of the country where they have been introduced rapidly. The most successful schemes of this nature are delivered in partnership with and at the pace of the local community.
- As the pilot starts, the EBLN team has already been working with the community and other stakeholders for two years and realised the "Co-Discovery" and "Co-Design" stages of their process. They intend to use the GREENGAGE methodology on COs to re-engage with the community, to re-iterate the first stages and to deliver the "Trial" stage using the GREEN Engine and toolbox.
- At the time when their GREENGAGE CO Activation was supposed to happen, the pilot owners could not start the re-engagement due to Barton house [evacuation](#), that is at the heart of the pilot area and "communication shutdown" in East Bristol, demanded by BCC.
- Bristol City Council will face changes due to the municipal governance shift from a mayor to a committee system. The change in governance structure will be effective from May 2024. The

EBLN programme is required to reflect timescales associated with the Pre-Election Period (PEP) which runs from March, as well as the formation of the new Committee System.

Goals and Objectives of EBLN

The vision for the Liveable Neighbourhood programme is to empower local communities to transform their neighbourhoods into places which provide better access to green and play space, more seamless and convenient connections to local amenities using sustainable and active forms of travel, and more space for social and community activity.

The objectives of Liveable Neighbourhood programme are to:

- Improve local and citywide air quality and contribute to meeting the climate and ecological emergency.
- Improve residents' physical and mental health and wellbeing.
- Improve levels of physical and perceived safety in our communities.
- Contribute to reducing inequality and opening opportunities for all in our communities.
- Improve local accessibility and connectivity to shops, schools, services, and other amenities for everyone to move around safely and sustainably.
- Transform our neighbourhoods to places where people want to spend time, can interact with neighbours, and enjoy their unique identities.
- Reflect the needs and characteristics of the local community and increase the sense of pride and belonging.

7.1.2 Pilot Specification

The pilot project has utilised a co-design approach seeking feedback and input from the local community to help design a re-imagined streetscape that realises the vision set through the Citizen Assembly.

The pilot seeks to implement the phase 1 scheme as a trial, following the submission of an Outline Business Case to the funding body, WECA. This will be delivered using temporary materials and will remain in place for 6-18 months whilst further engagement is undertaken with the community to determine how the scheme could look if made permanent. The phase 2 scheme will deliver elements of the project that can only be constructed in a permanent way such as, new crossings and junction upgrades.

The pilot project will collect data throughout the trial scheme to determine whether the scheme is a success. GREENGAGE tools will be deployed with citizen scientists to fill the 'data gap' that is often experienced with transport schemes. By directly involving the community in the data collection, monitoring and evaluation of the trial, the pilot project can build community trust with the Council and create greater transparency for decision making on how the scheme could become permanent.

The pilot project will involve a multidisciplinary team of experts (as participants of Bristol's Citizen Observatory) who will bring in localised knowledge, including data scientists, software developers, transportation planners, policy makers, and community engagement specialists, to ensure a participatory, situated, and user-centred approach. The pilot will also provide tools to citizens to explore and contribute to existing use cases, co-create new ones, collect and visualise data, as well as evaluate and assess the impact of all these stages. They will have the opportunity to make use of pilot and auxiliary open data to solve problems deemed more relevant to the pilot community and make use of the same tools to create their own experiments at a later point. These actions can provide useful insights to public administration for interventions and/or policy making.

The pilot project will be evaluated based on its ability to collect high-quality and representative data, generate useful insights and recommendations, and engage citizens in the project.

7.1.3 Bristol's GREENGAGE Observatory

The pilot owners (Liveable Neighbourhoods Team) envision at least two GREENGAGE Observatories. One will give the possibility to re-engage with the local community, especially with those members of the local community who were concerned about the scheme and its trial interventions. Through means of engagement that go beyond data collection, the pilot owners will seek to discover issues of shared

concern (around journeys, traffic displacement, perception of and actual safety, air quality/pollution, opportunities for increased green infrastructure etc) amongst participants and support them to envision their neighbourhoods together. Grounding the GREENGAGE Observatory in issues that still matter to the people is important for rebuilding trust in BCC and ensuring participation of historically underrepresented groups as well as supporting the co-design of forthcoming interventions that will be part of the second GREENGAGE Observatory.

The 2nd GREENGAGE Observatory will consider the learnings from the 1st GREENGAGE Observatory as well as the issues that need to be addressed to successfully deliver the 1st phase of the “trial” stage of the EBLN scheme as well as the metrics to evaluate GREENGAGE Observatories (as in WP6). Ensuring a representative participation, the pilot owners will attempt to monitor and explore the effects of the interventions performed by the EBLN scheme, in other words validate whether those interventions are delivering positive effects in line with policy objectives for a more equitable city, and just transition towards becoming climate neutral by 2030. This should inspire local authorities to adopt and adapt the scheme to the contexts of their neighbourhood’s considering policy demands for climate mitigation.

GREENGAGE Observatory Journey

GREENGAGE will play an important role during phase 1 of the Trial scheme and provide useful insights based on which permanent interventions can be applied in phase 2. Phase 1 will involve the implementation of the temporary trial measures e.g., model filters, pocket parks, whilst phase 2 will focus on the permanent infrastructures e.g., new active travel crossing facilities, tree planting, junction upgrades, lighting.

The GREENGAGE methodology will support in setting up a 1st smaller GREENGAGE Observatory mobilised between January and March 2024 before the instillation of EBLN trial scheme and a 2nd larger GREENGAGE Observatory mobilised post-implementation of the trial scheme, allowing for comparable data gathering. While the former will mostly rely on low-tech methods and tools of engagement that not necessarily use the GREEN Engine, the second full-scale GREENGAGE Observatory will build on the previous understandings and will be fully supported by the GREENGAGE Toolbox. Due to the change within the municipal governance system, both GREENGAGE Observatories will need to be responsive to any related effects that go with that.

Social-political relevance of 1st GREENGAGE Observatory

- Legitimate concerns raised about the potential impact of the trial scheme regarding access to local services from some groups.
- Ensure ongoing representative participation in the co-design / engagement process, helping to ensure the scheme reflects the diverse range of needs from across communities in the project area.
- Opportunity to re-engage with the local community in advance of the trial scheme being delivered, supporting the need to build trust between some local groups and BCC.

Social-political relevance of 2nd GREENGAGE Observatory

- Unsafe for walking and cycling and unpleasant for spending time in public spaces due to poor air quality, traffic, and noise.
- Lack of sense of pride and community due to limitations of access, poor appearance and connectivity to civic infrastructure (public spaces, food providers, education and other public services).
- Social inequalities and lack of possibilities for achieving wellbeing, embodied through physical and mental health problems of local neighbourhood residents.
- Lack of power of local communities to transform their neighbourhoods into places which provide better access to green and play spaces, more seamless and convenient connections to local amenities using sustainable forms of travel, and more space for social and community activity.

Expected impact of pilot

1. By partnering with local communities and especially empowering people from marginalised groups such as children and families in East Bristol to meaningfully participate in the co-creation of EBLN, the pilot expects to increase trust in the scheme and insights on the effects of interventions (e.g., removing cut through routes for non-local vehicle traffic) on local people's everyday lives.
2. By preparing, testing, and evaluating the community-led performance of mitigation policies through EBLN, the pilot owners will gain understanding of success criteria of LN projects that will be shared through a Handbook for LN. Learnings will feed into of the city-wide scheme of Liveable Neighbourhoods and inform future plans, policies and strategies in the context of LN that are already planned for South Bristol.
3. By engaging citizens and community anchor organisations not only through data collection but in various ways in urban planning processes, local interventions will become more responsive to concerns and visions expressed by local communities. This is expected to strengthen BCC's aspirations of enabling co-creation of liveable neighbourhoods together with the local population and should lead towards manifested long-term citizen participation modes as integral part of municipal governance, e.g., through Citizen Assemblies which democratise urban planning and politicise citizen engagement.

Figure 8: Bristol GREENGAGE Observatory Journey.

7.1.4 Governance model

The project team and project board are already in place and have had the benefit of delivering the pilot Liveable Neighbourhood throughout the last 18 months. The structure has worked effectively and has guided project development through the initial phases, shaping the community engagement and Outline Business Case.

The Delivery Group is responsible for each aspect of project delivery, drawing on the technical expertise of a wide range of Council services. The delivery group will report to project managers on a bi-weekly basis, who will then report to the East Bristol Liveable Neighbourhood SRO. The Project managers will be responsible for co-ordination and delivery of each work package, reporting to the Project Board monthly.

The Project Board will be led by the SRO and will assist the political champions with decision making and steering the delivery of the Liveable Neighbourhood programme. The Board itself is also made up of a diverse range of Council services to ensure that resources can be co-ordinated effectively.

Stakeholders

The stakeholders in the East Bristol Liveable Neighbourhood Pilot include:

6. Public institutions:

- Council cabinet members
- Bristol ward members
- Members of Parliament
- Bristol City Council internal project teams

7. Organised groups:

- Bristol One City Transport Board (such as Sustrans and Bristol Walking Alliance)
- Accessibility and equality groups (such as Bristol Physical Access Chain or Older Peoples' Forum, Green and Black Ambassadors and Black Seeds Environmental Social Justice Network)

8. Unorganised groups:

- Community champions (such as paid professionals, community animators and connectors from local organisations as well as active residents)
- People who live in the area, or just outside the area
- People who travel to or through the area
- Local businesses, shops and local services (such as waste collection)
- Local schools and other educational establishments

Target groups of GREENGAGE Observatories

The GREENGAGE Citizen Science process that will be carried out by the configured GREENGAGE Observatories in Bristol will demand the involvement of different societal groups from beginning to end. People will not only contribute gathering data with devices or answering to surveys, but they will also help co-designing the hypothesis and associated experiments/campaigns to allow their validation or rebuttal.

It is as important to know precisely what datasets should be used, what technologies employed, what data analysis to perform, as to understand how many people with what capabilities and social backgrounds should be engaged throughout the whole process. Only that way co-creation will govern the whole GREENGAGE Observatory operation.

From the stakeholders identified above, the following are most relevant for the GREENGAGE Observatories.

1st GREENGAGE Observatory

- a) Those residents most affected or concerned by EBLN the trial scheme,
- b) historically underrepresented or marginalized groups such as families and young people or diverse ethnic communities,
- c) members of community anchor organisations.

2nd GREENGAGE Observatory

- a) Those who already participated in the 1st GREENGAGE Observatory,
- b) a full-scale representative sample of local residents and members of community groups.

Figure 9: Situational understanding of collective actors for East Bristol Liveable Neighbourhood pilot.

7.1.5 Use Cases

Use case #533: Analyse and visualise impact of road closures on mobility patterns (journey quality)

The system will use historical mobility data and road closure data and analyse mobility patterns before and after road closures. It will also compare traffic flow, travel times, and congestion levels before and after road closures as well as identify any significant changes in mobility patterns and potential causes. It will visualise and report the results to stakeholders and decision-makers. Possible steps:

1. User opens visualisation tool.
2. User loads data for visualisation.
3. User selects analysis mode (mobility patterns, traffic flow, congestion levels etc)
4. User downloads / exports analysis information (images, spreadsheets etc).

Use case #534: Air quality/ Environment monitoring

Monitor and visualise air quality of the neighbourhood at different times (e.g., at different times of the day, for different congestion levels etc).

Use case #535: Monitor environment and identify safety / threat levels

Analyse threat levels of various neighbourhoods and visualise for further analyses and input to policy-making.

Use case #536: Mobility Pattern Analysis to determine accessibility to shops, schools, services, and other local amenities

Use techniques such as GPS tracking and to determine routes that citizens take to local amenities and identify improvements. Categorise routes by mode of transport and analyse alternative travel modes.

7.1.6 Data Collection Requirements

ID	FR-DC.1
Name	Collect data on road and sidewalks usage (e.g., number of people gathering near shops or other amenities)
Description	Implement a mechanism to collect data on the usage of roads and sidewalks both from people passing by and from people standing in front of shops and other places.
Rationale	Understanding the usage patterns of roads and sidewalks, particularly in relation to areas with high foot traffic near shops, amenities (e.g., local health services, local parks), places of employment and education, is essential for urban planning, optimizing infrastructure, and identifying areas for improvement or potential interventions.
Fit criterion	Data accurately represents the usage of roads and sidewalks, including comprehensive information on trip origins and destinations, travel modes (wide diversity should be provided), distances, durations, and accessibility features.
Pre-conditions	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> The system should have access to sensors or devices capable of detecting and counting people in specific areas. The special areas such as shops or other amenities should be detected and defined.
Post-conditions	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Data on road and sidewalk usage should be successfully collected and stored in the system. The collected data should be available for analysis and decision-making purposes.
Potential technologies	MODE + REENGAGE app (AIT), Realtime Mapping & Image Analysis (MindEarth)

ID	FR-DC.2
Name	Collect environment data from portable sensors
Description	Deploy portable sensors to collect environmental data such as temperature, humidity, air quality, noise levels, and flood data
Rationale	Gathering accurate and up-to-date environmental data is crucial for monitoring and assessing the quality of the urban environment. Portable sensors provide a flexible and efficient way to collect data across different locations and capture variations in environmental conditions.
Fit criterion	The system should be capable of collecting environment data using portable sensors for various parameters, including temperature, humidity, air quality, flood hazard, and noise levels.
Pre-conditions	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Sensors capable of measuring temperature, humidity, air quality, flood hazard and noise levels should be available. (Portable?) The sensors should be properly calibrated and configured to ensure accurate data collection.

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> If the sensors are static, the location where they are placed must be carefully chosen.
Post-conditions	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Environmental data, including temperature, humidity, air quality, and noise levels, should be successfully collected from the deployed portable sensors.
Potential technologies	Portable Devices for environmental data capture (HOPU)

ID	FR-DC.5
Name	Collect real-time GPS data
Description	Capture and collect real-time GPS data to track the location and movements of individuals, vehicles, or assets within the city.
Rationale	Collecting real-time GPS data provides valuable information for various purposes, including transportation planning, traffic management, public safety, and resource allocation. It enables city officials and service providers to monitor and analyse movement patterns, identify congestion points, optimize routes, and make informed decisions based on real-time location information.
Fit criterion	The system should be capable of collecting and recording real-time GPS data accurately. It should capture the location coordinates, timestamps, and any additional relevant information associated with the tracked entities
Pre-conditions	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> The tracked entities (e.g., vehicles, individuals) should be equipped with GPS-enabled devices (mobiles).
Post-conditions	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Real-time GPS data should be continuously collected from the tracked entities. The collected GPS data should include accurate location coordinates, timestamps, and relevant metadata. The data should be accessible for analysis, visualisation, and integration with other systems or applications.
Potential technologies	GREENGAGE app (AIT)

ID	FR-DC.6
Name	Collect survey data on citizen experience of public transports
Description	Implement a mechanism to collect survey data from citizens regarding their experience with public transportation services.
Rationale	Gathering feedback from citizens about their experience with public transportation services is crucial for identifying areas of improvement and making informed decisions to enhance the quality of transportation services.
Fit criterion	Corresponding online surveys uploaded into co-production process managing Citizen Observatory
Pre-conditions	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> A platform that allows sending questionnaires to members of a specific pilot. Users should be registered on that platform. The survey questions should be defined and available for citizens to respond to.
Post-conditions	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> The questionnaires should be successfully delivered to the intended users. Users should be able to access and complete the questionnaires within the GREENGAGE technologies platform.

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Survey responses should be successfully collected and stored in the system. Reports and analytics should be generated based on the survey data.
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Potential technologies	Collaborative environment (DEUSTO), GREENGAGE App (AIT)
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ID	FR-DC.7
Name	Import air quality data in different formats (CSV, JSON, etc)
Description	Provide the capability to import air quality data to the GREEN Engine in different formats
Rationale	Supporting multiple data formats allows for compatibility with diverse sources and systems, ensuring comprehensive coverage of air quality data.
Fit criterion	Availability of imported air quality data into GREEN Engine data repository
Pre-conditions	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Available air quality data formats from compatible sources
Post-conditions	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Air quality data successfully imported and accessible within the GREEN Engine data repository
Potential technologies	Data Quality and Structure Dashboards (VRVis), UrbanTEP/VISAT (GISAT)

ID	FR-DC.8
Name	Import historical mobility data
Description	Enable the import of historical mobility data into the system for analysis and visualisation purposes.
Rationale	Importing historical mobility data allows for a comprehensive understanding of past mobility patterns, trends, and behaviours. It facilitates data-driven decision-making, supports urban planning initiatives, and helps evaluate the effectiveness of mobility interventions and policies.
Fit criterion	Availability of imported historical mobility data into GREEN Engine data repository.
Pre-conditions	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Historical mobility data is available in a suitable format for import. The system has the capability to validate the imported data and ensure its integrity.
Post-conditions	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Historical mobility data is successfully imported into the system. The imported data can be combined with real-time or other existing data sources for comprehensive mobility analysis.
Potential technologies	UrbanTEP/VISAT (GISAT)

ID	FR-DC.9
Name	Import crime data in different formats
Description	Provide the capability to import crime data to the GREEN Engine
Rationale	Importing crime data allows for a comprehensive view of crime patterns and trends, facilitating analysis and decision-making processes. Also, it enables the generation of perceived security analyses.
Fit criterion	Availability of imported crime data into GREEN Engine data repository
Pre-conditions	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Availability of crime data from reliable sources

Post-conditions	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Crime data successfully imported an accessible within the GREEN Engine data repository
Potential technologies	Data Quality and Structure Dashboards (VRVis), UrbanTEP/VISAT (GISAT)
ID	FR-DC.10
Name	Import historical road closure data
Description	Enable the import of road closure data into the system to provide up-to-date information on road closures and disruptions.
Rationale	Importing road closure data allows for accurate and real-time information about road closures, construction activities, and other disruptions. It helps in improving traffic management, rerouting strategies, and providing timely updates to drivers and commuters. It also enables the analysis of movement patterns when roads are closed.
Fit criterion	Availability of imported historical road closure data into GREEN Engine data repository.
Pre-conditions	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Historical road closure data is available in a suitable format for import. • The system has the capability to validate the imported data and ensure its integrity.
Post-conditions	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Historical road closure data is successfully imported into the system. • The imported data can be combined with real-time or other existing data sources for comprehensive mobility analysis.
Potential technologies	UrbanTEP/VISAT (GISAT)

7.1.7 GREEN Engine tools

Execution of Citizen Observatory campaigns (piloting): Bristol’s Citizens’ Assembly called for their involved neighbourhoods to be reimaged in a people-centred and more ‘liveable’ manner. The neighbours voiced their opinions, from which several use cases could be extracted related with mobility analysis, air quality analysis and safety level identification. Through GREEN Engine tools and Citizen Observatory campaigns, it is expected that the necessary data will be collected to enable informed decisions to be taken. This is how the tools available in the GREEN Engine can help to collect, process, and exploit the data:

- **Collaborative Environment (DEUSTO):** This digital environment would be essential for managing the citizen observers' teams, co-ideating campaign goals, and orchestrating the campaign's different phases. Furthermore, it can be employed to survey and involve users in the extraction of specific information. Surveys can be created, indexed, and shared from it.
- **Portable Devices for environmental data capture (HOPU):** Sensor devices with air quality (measuring PM, CO, SO2, NO2, O3, and NO), noise and crowd monitoring capabilities, will be used to analyse the air quality and noise and its impact on the public health. ATMOTUBE devices from Libelium will be useful to measure air quality and to collect detailed data on the levels of air pollutants at specific key points within the city, including fine particulate matter (PM2.5), ozone (O3), carbon monoxide (CO), carbon dioxide nitrogen (NO2). Noisecapture app will help monitor noise pollution, building upon the notions of participatory sensing and citizen science. They will be linked to EU Copernicus services.
- **Realtime Mapping and Image Analysis (MindEarth):** This technology can help map and chart well-used or less popular routes and/or public spaces or specific locations to qualify demographics profiles of users (i.e., gender, age-group, social grouping) and to further qualify modality choices on a micro scale. It also can help to identify and annotate elements that may cause disruption in traffic or environmental quality factors that might prevent people from taking a certain route (i.e., rubbish, absence of sidewalk, street holes). Furthermore, the

mapping of large numbers of people can help to identify popular places where people with reduced mobility may have problems getting around.

- **MODE (AIT):** This technology is a trip recording and mode detection framework. It consists of two main software components: a data recording module for iOS and Android apps and a backend data analysis module. The purpose of the MODE library is to provide the out-of-the-box solution for mobility surveys via smartphone app and web service. It yields high-precision, multimodal mobility data for traffic planning, mobility research, cities, and communities. The most important functionality it provides for GREENGAGE are the routes and used travel mode(s) of users. The MODE library will be integrated into the GREENGAGE App to enable the citizen observers to track their commuting routes with specific means of transport, thus providing crucial data about transportation patterns.
- **GREENGAGE App (AIT):** This is an adaptation of the previously developed tool – HotCity App. Key idea behind is to provide a universal tool to help engage Citizen Observatories in the research within the scope of the project through completion of Pilot-defined tasks in a comprehensible and gamified manner. Whereas the initial tool had a primary focus on the measuring of the excessive heat signatures of the cities’ facilities, the GREENGAGE App version allows for a broader scope of research like visitor density, free-text surveys, route evaluation and overall, POI (Point of Interest) liveability reporting and validation. It can be further used to report obstacles, POIs (high traffic spots, unlit street areas, etc.) or already enhanced area spots (evaluate pre-defined data through self-reporting – to be agreed at a later stage). Moreover, citizen observers can validate those spots (reported by other observers or administrators) to raise the data accuracy and reliability.

Collective learning by analysing the Citizen Observatory’s data: As part of the utilization scenario of the GREEN Engine, the gathered data undergoes meticulous examination to identify recurring trends and share the resulting insights with citizen observers, data scientists, and relevant stakeholders. This process facilitates a thorough comprehension, active participation, and collective responsibility for the findings derived from the data, thereby fostering additional discussions on the outcomes.

- **Data Quality and Structure Dashboards (VRVis):** This component helps not only to visualise the data but also to co-curate it, reflecting on its quality and revealing gaps in the decision-making process.
- **Urban TEP/VISAT (GISAT):** Key component of the Urban Thematic Exploitation Platform¹ is a web-based Visualisation and Analytical Toolbox (VISAT) provided by GISAT. It allows easy integration of different data, their exploration, visualization and analysis and some collaboration functionalities for data/results sharing. VISAT is based on our Panther technology and current is under major technological upgrade. VISAT functionality is offered to support GREENGAGE activities in a similar role as in UrbanTEP here - to explore and visualise geospatial data related to mobility patterns. By employing this tool, real-time mobility patterns may be analysed in real-time and compare them with historical data to extract conclusions about the implemented changes. Visualisation of data shown in Urban TEP can highlight the impact of specific recurring mobility patterns on a larger (environmental) scale.
- **Realtime Mapping and Image Analysis (MindEarth):** The collected images would be processed and analysed to extract metrics of interest on number of people of different demographic segments using a specific route or public place in a moment in time or over a specific time window. Factors qualifying environmental quality of the built fabric would also be extracted. Aggregation units could be defined collaboratively with other technology providers to ensure that different data collected by the projects are comparable.
- Bristol has an **Open Data Platform**, [Open Data Bristol](#), which could be a useful channel for disseminating CO data, as well as a source of data to feed into GREEN Engine.

Data-driven policy making and verification (sharing): In the last phase, campaigns and their objectives should be reflected upon for future campaigns to use best practices and avoid possible mistakes. Furthermore, Citizen Observatory campaigns should make public administrations consider the outcomes of them their policy-making processes.

- **REENGAGE Toolbox:** open datasets generated, new open-source tools developed, manuals and HOWTOs developed should enrich the catalogue with Citizen Science resources assembled within REENGAGE Academy.
- **REENGAGE Knowledge Assets:** training materials, engagement practices, citizen science resources as part of Citizen Observatories
- **REENGAGE White Book:** the most valuable insights per Citizen Observatory campaign should feed the project's white book.

7.2 North Brabant

7.2.1 Background and Context

The Province of North Brabant is in the South of the Netherlands with geographical coverage 5,081km² housing about 2.5 million citizens. Due to its job and education opportunities, and appealing natural environment, the province is rapidly growing, which comes with challenges. Chief amongst which is a rapid urbanisation, creating a demand for 12.000 dwellings in liveable and sustainable neighbourhoods per year. To tackle this and associated traffic safety, health, inclusivity, economic and energy challenges the province of North Brabant envisions a transition to sustainable traffic and transport as a key pursuit. The regional policy aims at 20% more cycled kilometres by 2027 and 40% by 2040, achieved through stimulation of biking, but primarily through the provision of more space to use the bike in everyday movements, recreation, commute, and multimodal traffic.

Although the province already has a strong urban and even regional bike infrastructure (bicycle highways), the choice to shift to sustainable transport requires more than physical means. Motorized vehicular travel plays a dominant role in the mobility of Brabant as well, with about 80% of the trips longer than 6km made by car. The shift to sustainable transport has not occurred to its full capacity. The Province of North Brabant (PNB) is a meso-scale level of government that can set up long term visions and targets and public transport plans as well as fund or oversee connected local plans. Regarding its vision for cycling, it builds on widespread citizen participation to understand how to engage effectively with travellers that use the car for short distances, empower them to overcome their deterrents, and ultimately increase the amount of KMs biked in the region. In fact, they have already experience with participatory processes in response to societal challenges such as in the case of the small-scale activities to discuss a more intense form of participation with inhabitants of Brabant toolkit created by Het Participatiekompas for participatory processes that can help to integrate COs in governance processes. They currently organise small scale activities to discuss a more intense form of participation with inhabitants of Brabant which the CO should connect to.

To ensure fair representation in participatory processes, the Province is collaborating with a Data Lab which collects gender and diversity data to inform future societal decisions (Gendergelijkheidspan). Furthermore, strict policy guidelines are enacted to keep the process of decision making as inclusive as possible.

Nonetheless, biking policies are predominantly developed by white, old males who, although they make up for a vast number of actual bike users, cannot account for wider societal needs by themselves. This contrasts the demographics of current and potential bike users and fails to address some of the wider factual or perceived challenges in mobility, such as 'Mobility Poverty'¹. The deteriorating service of public transport to more remote areas effectively make these areas dependent on the use of the car. Therefore, when pursuing more sustainable transport options in the province requires the sensitivity to promote biking and public transport but not eschewing the need for car travel.

Goals and Objectives

The goal of this pilot project is to generate knowledge on how to achieve a higher shift to sustainable transport, specifically from car to bike. In detail, the specific objectives are:

- To collect, validate, and interpret qualitative and quantitative data on travel patterns and modality choice, and ensure they are structurally integrated into a dialogical approach to governance discussing the liveability and sustainability of Brabant.
- To include women and historically marginalized groups such as ethnic minorities, disadvantaged populations and disabled persons in the gathering and signification to ensure an inclusive perspective on the assessment of liveability and sustainability;
- To generate additional knowledge on the process of shifting to sustainable transport through different data analyses (e.g., why is the car still used when efficient and effective bike highways exist) and on involving citizens more intensely in governance through co-creation.
- To use the data and citizen engagement to improve the conditions for sustainable transport on, for instance, spatial, environmental, and community level.
- Provide a qualitative metric to map and measure the bikeability of a neighbourhood, supported by citizen-gathered data.

- To set up more targeted campaigns to remove obstacles for biking in the decision process.

7.2.2 Pilot Specification

The pilot project targets the mobility transition throughout the whole province. Despite the presence of bicycle highways in the province, many short and long-distance trips are done by car, specifically due to differences in accessibility differing per area. To ensure citizen observatories are set up in places where an increase in sustainable travel is possible, the pilot will take a two-phase approach: (1) a GPS-data localisation phase and (2) a Sustainable Transport Data phase. The first phase will gather multimodal travel patterns to pinpoint a promising site for sustainable travel behavioural change, while the second phase will dive into citizen motivations and obstacles at the promising site to enhance the performance of sustainable transport options.

In particular, the first phase is a collaboration with the Verplaatsingsdata (Movement data) project, a province-wide GPS gathering scheme through a local app. The pilot project developed by the Cycling Data project in partnership with Breda University of Applied Sciences (BUAS), integrates qualitative and quantitative data to update their dataset on bike use and routes and increase their insight into the decision process of modality choice. It leverages existing apps and data gathering projects, such as the Multimodal Tracking Project, and builds upon past research on cycling patterns. The initiative is focused on creating a comprehensive inventory of multimodal travel patterns to identify bikeable routes and areas, essential for addressing the province's high number of car trips.

The motivation for the second phase derives from the need for sustainable transport and targets at identifying cycling obstacles that may prevent that vision. This second phase has two branches. The first branch is the BUAS Cycling Lab. This entails a local CO that dives into the decision-making process around biking. The second branch of the second phase focuses on setting up COs in areas which the GPS data collected from the first phase identify as carrying potential or serving as bottlenecks for sustainable transport. In other words, the insights from the cycling lab will provide a framework for possible issue networks to deal with in this second branch. Ultimately, the localised COs will focus on highlighting obstacles or motivators in the current bike network and gathering data to improve sustainable transport options in the neighbourhood. To accommodate the different motivations of the GREENGAGE Observers and stakeholders, GREENGAGE Observatories are tasked with assessing their locale through a bikeability metric which can be supported with a variety of data sources,

The pilot project is enabled by the Argaleo DigiTwin technology, a data aggregation and visualisation tool that can be used to support governance decision making. This digital tool already holds detailed data shared by municipalities (such as traffic, and traffic light data) and transporters (such as bus performances) which will be complemented by the micro data of routing and citizen preferences gathered by the pilot project. The complete dataset will be analysed and visualized to generate insights and recommendations for easing the transition to bike use on regional and urban routes, as well as its associated neighbourhood improvements, to make them more liveable and sustainable.

The overarching goal is to identify pressure points in short cycling paths as a foundation for crafting effective and sustainable urban transport policies and supporting a modal shift from car use to bike use in North Brabant.

7.2.3 North Brabant's GREENGAGE Observatory

The North Brabant GREENGAGE Observatory will aim at addressing the above challenges of urbanisation, including traffic safety, health, inclusivity, and energy through a focus on sustainable traffic and transport. Working alongside the central and decentralised government, the observatory will empower citizens to use a data-driven approach to assess their cycling infrastructure, identify cycling obstacles, and map their travel activities. Next to this quantitative data gathering, the experiences and decisions of the citizens will offer qualitative data on possible apprehensions to switching from car to sustainable transport. Involving citizens in the gathering and signification of this data can strengthen the policy agenda through a more grounded understanding of obstacles to sustainable travel, and the decision process that precedes it.

The North Brabant pilot will have at least two GREENGAGE Observatories: the BUAS Cycle Lab CO which will aim at studying obstacles and motivators for bike use at the BUAS campus & co-design hands-on solutions with employees. This GREENGAGE Observatory will dive into the motivations and obstacles of cycling through qualitative methods. These insights will then inform the quantitative data gathering possibilities in the second GREENGAGE Observatory.

The second GREENGAGE Observatory will be set up in an area with a high potential for sustainable transport improvements. The selection of the area will be based on the first phase and the collection of movement data via the Verplaatsingsdata app for a representative group of users. This first Verplaatsingsdata (movement data) GREENGAGE Observatory will be focused on GPS tracking with less qualitative exposition. During the second GREENGAGE Observatory, citizens will explore local travel patterns, as well as qualitatively exploring obstacles and motivators that are lacking. Here, political decision making on bike facilitation will be actively addressed and included.

In both GREENGAGE Observatories, people from different societal groups will contribute to gathering data with devices (mainly their smartphones), answering to surveys, and help co-designing the hypothesis and associated experiments/campaigns to allow for data validation or rebuttal. They will also take part in the reflection of aggregated and analysed data so that decisions made can be issued collectively.

GREENGAGE Observatory Journey

Citizens will use a variety of digital and non-digital methods, such as a possible mobile app, to gather qualitative and quantitative data such as their mobility routes, their origins and destination, transportation mode, travel time, and purpose, but also choice considerations or affective appraisals. This bottom-up micro data will be added by the pilot partners into a digital twin, capable of visualising the gathered data and combining it with other datasets.

During the project, the digital twin will also be further equipped with mobility data and a set of specific indicators that can be used to evaluate policy goals and possible macro data in the form of satellite or census data. The aggregation of these different layers can contextualise the (non-)biking behaviour of the citizen observatory, highlight salient correlations, and identify missing data sets or insights.

The qualitative data will be gathered through periodically survey the GREENGAGE Observatory on their decision-making process, easily facilitated by the mobile app. This however targets the digitally inclined participants, and alternative communication channels should be set up to include all members of the observatory. These surveys will help to get an idea why certain modalities are chosen for which trips and why certain routes are taken. Especially this understanding of the choices and influencing factors allow for co-creation of a policy approach that facilitates the shift to sustainable transport.

These discussions will involve the GREENGAGE Observatories into areas of governance, thus requiring a multidisciplinary team of experts, including data scientists, software developers, transportation planners, and community engagement specialists, to ensure a participatory and user-centred approach. Together with these groups, PNB can assess focal points for campaigns to improve biking, either through advertising, spatial interventions, or stakeholder involvement such as employers. By including the citizen in the exploration of the topic and giving insight into the breaking points for their decision, the pilot introduces citizens to the data driven decision making process and involves them in a more bidirectional governance to solve problems deemed more relevant to the pilot community. This interaction is further facilitated by providing a bikeability metric per neighbourhood which the citizens can fill in and support through data gathering actions. This way, a clear distinction of localised obstacles can be delivered to authorities to hopefully spur action. These insights can provide useful insights to public administration for interventions and/or policy making. Expected impacts of the pilot

1. Collecting and validating a range of quantitative data (e.g., origin-destination and routing data on the urban-regional connection) and qualitative data (e.g., the process of decision making in modality choices) by Observatory participants through a variety of data gathering methods (e.g., a mobile GPS tracking app) and the analysis of this data within a digital twin to assess neighbourhood liveability and sustainability.
2. Aggregating mobility data into a digital twin to strengthen its use as an evidence-based decision support tool to facilitate policy making, looking at the combination of macro (e.g., GPS, Satellite, land use data), meso (e.g., mobility and spatial data from transport

companies, traffic organisations, and policy indicators), and micro (citizen gathered data on, for instance, mobility routes or decision processes) data.

3. By targeting (amongst others) non biking people, potential bikers are heard in the civic debate about their gripes about the bike system and empowered to create, suggest, or set up interventions to the physical or processual infrastructure to overcome deterrents.
4. By engaging citizens, including historically underrepresented groups, in a transition to sustainable traffic and transport, the provincial governance processes will become more representative to the current demographics and cultures of inhabitants of the province.
5. By actualising Crowdsourced Datasets, the Province will be supplied with a database of visual or anecdotal evidence of biking deterrents that can be found throughout the region. This can help the Province to tackle wicked problems such as 'Mobility Poverty'.
6. By updating the understanding of the decision-making process around biking and delivering recommendations on how to cater to the specific decision needs in a locality, the Province can learn how to actively involve citizens more in mobility matters.
7. By updating the current overview of bike use based on GPS data in the province, the provincial plan will be complemented with localised evidence.
8. By getting an indication of how many people may want to make use of the bike plan and by revisiting and complementing existing biking policies (e.g., bike schemes) of businesses and universities, employers will contribute to shift monetary flows in support of a more inclusive transition towards sustainable traffic and transport.
9. By revisiting and complementing existing plans, the Province's vision for a transition to sustainable traffic and transport will become more localised which supports them to implement structural changes on a local and municipal level.
10. By providing a qualitative metric to map and measure the bikeability of a neighbourhood, supported by citizen-gathered data.

Figure 10: North Brabant GREENGAGE Observatory Journey.

7.2.4 Governance model

The pilot owner is consisted of two teams, Breda University of Applied Science (BUAS) and the Province of North Brabant (PNB), which will collaborate with a variety of partners. Whereas some partners facilitate the formation of citizen observatories, others provide technical or data support or facilitate mobility inquiries.

- **Project Partners** - BUAS and PNB (and some smaller governmental agencies together run the pilot. BUAS functions as project lead and supervises the project management, required frameworks, and technological embedding. PNB is the main client with a network of associated partners that can be involved in the formation of citizen observatories. BUAS sets up the necessary frameworks and methodologies to set up the pilot according to the PNB requirements.
- **Technical Partners** - Within the pilot, two technical partners support the North Brabant case. BUAS has worked together with Argaleo and its digital twin in other research projects and within education. The digital twin functions as decision making tool and PNB has a license for use. Mobidot is the data-gathering app provider linked to other projects from the Province.
- **Research Projects** - PNB and BUAS together have already participated in research projects, together and separately, that deal with bicycle behaviour of citizens, including excluded groups, or discuss mobility behaviour through digital support. Some of the data gathered in these projects has also been integrated into the Argaleo digital twin, or this tool has played a role in the projects. Some of the data from these projects and previous interactions with citizens can form a basis for the current pilot.
- **SmartwayZ** - Funded by the province, SmartwayZ is a mobility collaboration in the south of the Netherlands that connects relevant stakeholders on smart mobility solutions as answers to urbanization challenges. This organization specifically fosters innovation in mobility solutions and can connect the pilot to the SmartwayZ panel of potential citizen observatory members, and to relevant projects undertaken in the area (such as Brainport Bereikbaar).
- **Mobility Advisory Organisations** - Some organisations have a clear overview of mobility in Brabant and can have a stronger voice in possible directions it could develop. These companies can highlight strategies for increased biking or reflect on the general accessibility of an area. These experts can offer relevant insights for citizen observatories and the data targets pursued by them.
- **Civic Advisory Organisations** - PNB at times collaborates with advisory organs that specify in civic participation. The organisations can organise citizen panels but can also participate in research projects that engage citizens in participating in mobility projects. These organisations can help in the formation of citizen observatories through their networks but also by following their approach to citizen engagement.

Stakeholders

The stakeholders in the North Brabant Pilot include:

- The Province of North Brabant with its policy agenda and decision-making process that is now complemented with a more intensive interaction with citizens. Next to this, PNB is responsible for the province wide connecting bike network, and strategic visions on the increase of bikeability;
- Local municipal governments oversee the local infrastructure. Any gathered data on the status of the infrastructure and possible alterations will have to be taken up by local municipalities.
- Citizen panels who are informed on mobility matters and consist of involved citizens of whom some can form a citizen observatory (e.g., SmartwayZ reizigerspanel, Ov-reizigerspanel, KBO-Brabant).
- Local organisations, such as local businesses, whose company policy can facilitate the switch to biking.

- Existing (non-REENGAGE) Citizen Observatories consisting of citizens, and domain experts from advisory organizations dealing with, for instance, accessibility, mobility, and citizen participation.
- Researchers and scientists who study mobility, citizen participation, and urban design (e.g., BUAS; Logistics Community Brabant).
- Technology companies such as Argaleo and Mobidot whose data gathering and visualisation tool will form the backbone for policy directions and citizen involvement.

Target groups of REENGAGE Observatories

As part of the GPS data gathering scheme that sets off this pilot, different citizen panels, such as the SmartwayZ reizigerspanel, funded by but independent from the province will be contacted. These panels are contacted periodically through mailing lists with surveys on travel behaviour or specific target group matters, such as the experience of the elderly population. The call for a citizen observatory can be dispersed through a similar mail request or survey. Interested and invested citizens taking part in the panels can choose to join the citizen observatory that explores the decision-making process around the transition to bike use and gathers data on the actual use of the bike. To map the decision-making process in as much detail as possible, the citizen observatories will engage a variety of stakeholders, ranging from invested citizens -bikers or non-bikers - to employers with a stake in mobility.

To involve at least 250 people in the pilot, it is essential for them to connect to local initiatives and citizen panels, like Fietsersbond that already gather base data. While some of their members will be part of the CO (core group), their network will be involved in the CO activities as well (stakeholders). This way the target of 250 citizen observers will be reached. In the context of the Netherlands, when it comes to biking, elderly people are not necessarily considered a marginalised group. Instead, the following groups are identified based on demographics, travel diaries, and accessibility indices:

- People with a migratory background
- Children taken to school by parents (through the parents)
- People suffering from mobility poverty (especially rural or disadvantaged inhabitants)

The motivation to include marginalized or vulnerable populations stems from the political will to empower aspirant bikers in overcoming obstacles by gathering quantified proof enough to take concrete (small scale) actions. Depending on the envisioned experiments, the target groups will be:

1. Experiment – Multifunctional runs
 - a. Parents
 - b. Schools
 - c. Employers
2. Experiment - Bike Stimulation
 - a. Employers/Universities
 - b. Stimulation App
 - c. Employees/students
3. Experiment – Mobility Poverty
 - a. Locals
 - b. Public Transport Company
 - c. Last Mile providers

Figure 11: Situational understanding of collective actors for North Brabant pilot.

7.2.5 Use Cases

Use case #539: Analyse multimodal travel patterns

Use GPS data to understand vehicular travel patterns, such as route choices and road network quality. Visualise mobility statistics using different parameters (traffic count, flow, congestion, road usage, etc) Send questionnaires through GREENGAGE technologies. Import historical mobility data.

Use case #540: Investigate deterrents for bike usage

Collect quantitative (such as number of trips by bike, trip distances by car or bike etc.) and qualitative (such as decision models) data to generate insights on shifting to sustainable transports and identify obstacles to the use of bike as primary mean of transport. Data around citizens experiences and decisions on using transports could be gathered through periodical surveys; next to these data, georeferenced data on physical obstacles around the region preventing the use of the bike could be gathered through digital apps.

Use case #708 Facilitate sustainable transport in areas of mobility poverty

The first phase focuses on gathering mobility data (GPS tracking) from multimodal users. This data will be integrated into the DigiTwin platform, where the mobility patterns (routes, intensities, modalities) can be overlaid on existing datasets. Looking at those areas which experience limited bike use and are not covered by public transport will highlight several areas of interest where a CO can dive into the deterrents into biking. Managing these deterrents can remove the disconnect of these areas from the mobility system.

Within these areas, and their associated GREENGAGE Observatories, observers can subsequently give insight into their decision-making process (interviews and surveys). Identifying specific obstacles (like infrastructure missing, safety, lack of service, travel time or cost, etc.) can then be logged and appraised with the help of different GREENGAGE technologies.

7.2.6 Data Collection Requirements

ID	FR-DC.3
Name	Collect georeferenced data on physical obstacles for bike users
Description	Capture and record georeferenced data on physical obstacles that may hinder or pose risks to bike users, such as potholes, road hazards, construction zones, or blocked bike lanes.
Rationale	Collecting georeferenced data on physical obstacles for bike users is essential for improving the safety and usability of biking infrastructure. By identifying and documenting obstacles, city planners and maintenance teams can prioritize repairs and implement measures to enhance the biking experience.
Fit criterion	The system should enable the collection and georeferencing of data on physical obstacles for bike users. The captured data should include the type of obstacle, its location coordinates, and any additional relevant information.
Pre-conditions	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Map of biking routes and infrastructure. • Platform for bikers to report physical obstacles.
Post-conditions	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Georeferenced data on physical obstacles for bike users should be successfully captured and recorded. • The collected data should be stored in a database and linked to their respective coordinates on the biking routes. • The data should be available for analysis, visualisation, and integration with other systems or tools.
Potential technologies	Realtime Mapping and Image Analysis (Mind Earth), GREENGAGE app

ID	FR-DC.5
Name	Collect real-time GPS data
Description	Capture and collect real-time GPS data to track the location and movements of individuals, vehicles, or assets within the city.
Rationale	Collecting real-time GPS data provides valuable information for various purposes, including transportation planning, traffic management, public safety, and resource allocation. It enables city officials and service providers to monitor and analyse movement patterns, identify congestion points, optimize routes, and make informed decisions based on real-time location information.
Fit criterion	The system should be capable of collecting and recording real-time GPS data accurately. It should capture the location coordinates, timestamps, and any additional relevant information associated with the tracked entities
Pre-conditions	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • The tracked entities (e.g., vehicles, individuals) should be equipped with GPS-enabled devices (mobiles).
Post-conditions	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Real-time GPS data should be continuously collected from the tracked entities. • The collected GPS data should include accurate location coordinates, timestamps, and relevant metadata. • The data should be accessible for analysis, visualisation, and integration with other systems or applications.
Potential technologies	Multimodal Tracking Data Project

ID	FR-DC.6
Name	Collect survey data on citizen experience of public transports
Description	Implement a mechanism to collect survey data from citizens regarding their experience with public transportation services.

Rationale	Gathering feedback from citizens about their experience with public transportation services is crucial for identifying areas of improvement and making informed decisions to enhance the quality of transportation services.
Fit criterion	Corresponding online surveys uploaded into co-production process managing Citizen Observatory
Pre-conditions	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • A platform that allows sending questionnaires to members of a specific pilot. • Users should be registered on that platform. • The survey questions should be defined and available for citizens to respond to.
Post-conditions	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • The questionnaires should be successfully delivered to the intended users. • Users should be able to access and complete the questionnaires within the GREENGAGE technologies platform. • Survey responses should be successfully collected and stored in the system. • Reports and analytics should be generated based on the survey data.
Potential technologies	Collaborative environment, GREENGAGE app

ID	FR-DC.8
Name	Import historical mobility data
Description	Enable the import of historical mobility data into the system for analysis and visualisation purposes.
Rationale	Importing historical mobility data allows for a comprehensive understanding of past mobility patterns, trends, and behaviours. It facilitates data-driven decision-making, supports urban planning initiatives, and helps evaluate the effectiveness of mobility interventions and policies.
Fit criterion	Availability of imported historical mobility data into GREEN Engine data repository.
Pre-conditions	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Historical mobility data is available in a suitable format for import. • The system has the capability to validate the imported data and ensure its integrity.
Post-conditions	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Historical mobility data is successfully imported into the system. • The imported data can be combined with real-time or other existing data sources for comprehensive mobility analysis.
Potential technologies	UrbanTEP/VISAT, DigiTwin (Argaleo)

ID	FR-DC.12
Name	Send questionnaires through GREENGAGE technologies
Description	Enable the functionality to send questionnaires to users through the GREENGAGE technologies platform.
Rationale	To study the modality choices and understand the conditions, asking users to fill in a question on their mode choice should be facilitated
Fit criterion	Questionnaires co-designed available in co-production process corresponding to each Citizen Observatory campaign for each pilot
Pre-conditions	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • A platform that allows sending questionnaires to members of a specific pilot.

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Users should be registered on that platform.
Post-conditions	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • The questionnaires should be successfully delivered to the intended users. • Users should be able to access and complete the questionnaires within the GREENGAGE technologies platform.
Potential technologies	Collaborative environment, GREENGAGE app, UrbanTEP /VISAT

7.2.7 GREEN Engine tools

Execution of Citizen Observatory campaigns (piloting). Firstly, potential citizen observers are contacted through a survey on modality use, with an extra question on whether they wish to join a more intensive study of this phenomenon. Such questionnaire can be prepared through Collaborative Environment or indexed in it as part of the Citizen Observatory preparation. Secondly, the voluntary participants are encouraged to take part in gathering GPS tracking data and decision-making processes. This second phase requires the gathering of data by the citizen observers, through the following tools:

- **Multimodal Tracking Data Project:** Local, non-GREENGAGE mobile app that tracks the mode use and routes through the urban region and allows for the sending of survey questions to its users.
- **MODE (AIT):** This technology is a trip recording and mode detection framework. It consists of two main software components: a data recording module for iOS and Android apps and a backend data analysis module. The purpose of the MODE library is to provide the out-of-the-box solution for mobility surveys via smartphone app and web service. It yields high-precision, multimodal mobility data for traffic planning, mobility research, cities, and communities. The most important functionality it provides for GREENGAGE are the routes and used travel mode(s) of users. The MODE library will be integrated into the GREENGAGE App to enable the citizen observers to track their commuting routes with specific means of transport, thus providing crucial data about transportation patterns.
- **GREENGAGE App (AIT):** This is an adaptation of the previously developed tool – HotCity App. Key idea behind is to provide a universal tool to help engage Citizen Observatories in the research within the scope of the project through completion of Pilot-defined tasks in a comprehensible and gamified manner. Whereas the initial tool had a primary focus on the measuring of the excessive heat signatures of the cities’ facilities, the GREENGAGE App version allows for a broader scope of research like visitor density, free-text surveys, route evaluation and overall, POI (Point of Interest) liveability reporting and validation. It can be further used to report obstacles, POIs (high traffic spots, unlit street areas, etc.) or already enhanced area spots (evaluate pre-defined data through self-reporting – to be agreed at a later stage). Moreover, citizen observers can validate those spots (reported by other observers or administrators) to raise the data accuracy and reliability . Like the Brainport Bereikbaar app, this module gives insight into sections of route or sophisticating the travel patterns. The Brianport Bereikbaar app is focused on the Brainport regions. Alternative regions within the province can potentially be tracked through GREENGAGE App with MODE integration.
- **Realtime Mapping and Image Analysis (MindEarth):** This technology can allow the organisation of survey campaigns aimed at collecting, for specific locations and temporal windows of interest, information on how specific routes or public spaces are being used and by what types of people (youth, adults, elderly) as well as to count the number and type of vehicles being used. The collection device could be carried by operators walking or standing still but could also be mounted on bicycles (i.e., riders’ helmets or the bicycle

itself) to cover a larger area. It also can help to identify and annotate elements that may cause disruption in traffic or environmental quality factors that might prevent people from taking a certain route (i.e., rubbish, absence of sidewalk, street holes).

- **Collaborative Environment (DEUSTO):** This digital environment would be essential for managing the citizen observers' teams, co-ideating campaign goals, and orchestrating the campaign's different phases. Furthermore, it can be employed to survey and involve users in the extraction of specific information. Surveys can be created, indexed, and shared from it.

Collective learning by analysing the Citizen Observatory's data. The gathered data will be added to North Brabant's DIGITWIN to visualise the travel patterns. Together with the citizen observers, the quality of the data will be assessed as well as possible dataset connections to further explore the decision process – now more on spatial level. The following technologies can be of use here:

- **DigiTwin (Argaleo):** North Brabant has this cloud platform to amalgamate diverse datasets from various sources, enabling the visualization of static and real-time data for the province. These datasets cover urban design, mobility, energy, and demography. Users can request access to specific or all datasets to conduct multi-purpose analyses and 3D visualizations. The application is modular and customizable based on user needs. It primarily integrates reliable open-source datasets from governmental organizations like Netherlands' Cadaster, CBS, the Ministry of Infrastructure and Water Management, and municipalities. In the GREENGAGE project, GPS and questionnaire data from Citizen Observatories in North Brabant will be integrated into DigiTwin for in-depth analysis of travel behaviour and its relation to socio-economic, demographic, land-use, and urban design factors. The bikeability metric can be used to visually distinguish neighbourhoods.
- **Data Quality and Structure Dashboards (VRVis):** This component helps not only to visualise the data but also to co-curate it, reflecting on its quality and revealing gaps in the decision-making process.
- **Realtime Mapping and Image Analysis (MindEarth):** Checking specific well or poorly used routes to map and chart eye-level factors can further qualify modality choices on micro scale. The collected images would be processed and analysed to extract metrics of interest on number of people of different demographic segments using a specific route or public place in a moment in time or over a specific time window. Aggregation units could be defined collaboratively with other technology providers to ensure that different data collected by the projects are comparable.

Data-driven policy making and verification (sharing). Reflect on the outcomes of the Citizen Observatory campaign, draw some conclusions and lessons learnt. Consider how these findings could influence and inspire new policies or how those findings are able to validate or refute some policies that have previously been put in place.

- **GREENGAGE Toolbox:** open datasets generated, new open-source tools developed, manuals and HOWTOs developed should enrich the catalogue with Citizen Science resources assembled within GREENGAGE Academy.
- **GREENGAGE Knowledge Assets:** training materials, engagement practices, citizen science resources as part of Citizen Observatories
- **GREENGAGE White Book:** the most valuable insights per Citizen Observatory campaign should feed the project's white book.

7.3 Turano Valley

7.3.1 Background and Context

The Turano Valley is located north-east of the city of Rome, on the first hills that rise about fifty kilometres from the urban settlement of the capital. It covers a geographical area of 322.14 km² and has 10,250 inhabitants. A very high naturalistic and landscape value also corresponds to great difficulties deriving from the roughness of the territory and its morphology.

It is bordered on its eastern side by the mountain range which can be considered as a continuation of the Simbruini mountains, i.e., that of the Carseolani mountains, which have the highest peak at 1,508 meters of Monte Navegna and on the western side by the eastern offshoots of the Sabine mountains, on average less elevated than the Carseolani. The average height is between 600 and 900 meters.

There are 11 villages that are part of the valley, and, based on their geographical location, we group them into the following 3 groups:

- The villages that dominate and overlook the Turano Lake: Ascrea, Castel di Tora, Colle di Tora, Paganico Sabino.
- The village gravitating along the road “Via Salaria”: Belmonte in Sabina.
- The innermost villages: Collalto Sabino, Collegiove, Longone Sabino, Nespolo, Rocca Sinibalda, Turania.

The valley is characterized above all by the Turano Lake, located at 536 m. above sea level, along the course of the Turano River which is about ten kilometres long and has a perimeter of about 36 km. The artificial basin created by the then Soc. Terni, between the years 1935-1939 through the construction of a dam over 80 meters high, which blocks a reservoir with a capacity of over 150 million cubic meters of water connected to the twin reservoir of Salto by an approximately 9 km long tunnel, whose waters serve to feed powerful hydroelectric plants which supply important industries, first those of Terni. The lake extends at the foot of the nature reserve of Mount Navegna/Cervia (1506 m), a nature reserve covered by woods, and is characterized by the presence on its shores of ancient villages and castles which are reflected in the clear waters.

The Turano Valley is part of the EU Next Generation (PNRR action – National Programme for Resilience and Recovery), specifically the “United Villages of Turano Valley for Territorial Resilience and Recovery”. The PNRR expect to collect reliable and detailed data on mobility and air quality to provide input to Lazio’s Mobility, Transport and Logistics Plan (PRMTL), the main regional planning tool in the regions, drawn up in collaboration with the State, the Regions and Rome.

Its villages are recognised as some of the most beautiful villages in Italy and are coordinated by the association Borghi Piu Belli d’Italia. However, the area is suffering from hydrogeological criticalities, progressive growth of the elderly population, loss of rural cultural heritage, and increased presence of unoccupied houses, a phenomenon that began with constructing the artificial lake in 1939 and continued until the 70s. Currently, the most exploited areas are those few, flatter and closer to the lake, where the infrastructures and settlements are concentrated. This is where the economy of the villages is based on: rural resources, some craft businesses and tourism.

The territorial context of Turano Valley, including municipalities like Castel di Tora, Paganico Sabino, Ascrea, and Collalto Sabino, faces various challenges that contribute to a complex socio-economic landscape:

- The inadequacy of the road infrastructure system in Turano Valley hinders the movement and economic activities of and between the residents. Coupled with the lack of a direct train connection between Rome and the Valley (the nearest railway being in Carsoli, approximately 25 km away), it makes it even more difficult for people to commute to and from the capital city. Also, the absence of a cohesive and integrated public transport system within and between the municipal areas of the Valley further prevents access to essential services, like education and job opportunities. The infrastructure deficiency not only affects the daily lives of the local population but also inhibits businesses from accessing broader markets and opportunities.

- Beside transportation, Internet connection is either lacking or rather slow in the region. Expanding or upgrading the broadband network infrastructure (for high-speed connection) would satisfy basic needs of citizens for access to online services, global opportunities and resources, social connections, and overall, would increase the territorial competitiveness to the territory in relation to the rest of the country. The Ultra Broadband project financed by the Lazio Region ([Link](#)) aims to tackle this by providing high-speed Internet connection of at least 30 Mbit/s in 53 municipalities. Yet, the infrastructural development priorities historic centres over rural areas, where the presence of fibre optic connections are fewer or still await implementation.
- Population ageing together with intra-regional migration and depopulation trends constitute critical challenges and widen the urban-rural divide. In Italian villages, population has reached 289,000 residents with less than 10,000 inhabitants in the period 1951-2019. This is because remote regions face difficulties in keeping families and young adults because of loss of services and infrastructure. Meanwhile, young adults leave to study and work in cities, whilst older populations decide to move into quieter villages as residential preferences change during life course. Economic changes and environmental factors put additional pressure, raising questions about the adequate provision of health services, schools, and labour, as well as the diversification and sustainable future of local economy.
- As a result, these struggles and the economic crisis of the recent years has had an impact on the income levels of the residents. Still, disparities can be seen within the Valley.
- Without adequate support in remotely sparsely populated areas, low levels of schooling are observed among the youth population, including school dropouts, low educational level, lack of alternative educational resources.
- Meanwhile, the Valley is facing constant growth of both "secular" and religious excursion tourism which will require the provision of more services and infrastructure in the future.

Goals and objectives

The goals of this pilot project align with the "Borghi united for the cultural and social regeneration of the Turano Valley" programme. The programme was launched in the Turano Valley between 2022 and 2026, was funded from the National Recovery and Resilience Plan, and led by the municipality of Paganico Sabino. Its main purpose is to counteract the phenomenon of depopulation, improving liveability in the region, and strengthening the attractive potential of its villages. The GREENGAGE project will help achieving these goals by engaging citizens in the collection and analysis of data, such as mobility and environmental data, that can support evidence-based decision-making in urban regeneration efforts.

Mobility data analysis involves analysing patterns of movement and travel using data from sources such as GPS devices, mobile phones, and transportation systems. This can provide insights into how people move and interact with different areas, which can help policymakers and planners make more informed decisions about how to allocate resources and plan for future growth.

Remote working services, which allow people to work from anywhere, can be an attractive option for individuals who want to live in a depopulating area but still have access to job opportunities and professional networks. This can help attract and retain residents, especially those who are looking for a better work-life balance.

Urban regeneration involving stakeholders refers to a collaborative process of revitalizing urban areas through the involvement of local residents, businesses, and community groups. This can help to create more attractive and liveable neighbourhoods, improve access to services and amenities, and enhance social cohesion and community pride. The project can take advantage of the after-the-pandemic momentum, which freed workers from large urban centres and encouraged them to re-populate more remote areas, push forward an agenda for urban revitalisation and sustainable growth.

7.3.2 Pilot specification

The pilot project seeks to address two of the critical elements mentioned above, namely the inadequacy of the road infrastructure system and the phenomenon of the progressive depopulation of the villages to boost urban revitalisation upon careful territorial planning and services. The pilot project addresses

two EU Green Deal areas: 'Area 1: Increasing climate ambition: Cross-sectoral challenges' and 'Area 10 - Empowering citizens for the transition to a climate-friendly and sustainable Europe.

The pilot project will invite citizens and residents to take part in the Turano Valley's Citizen Observatory. A multidisciplinary group of people of different ages, genders, and occupations, each with localised knowledge will ensure a participatory, situated, and user-centred approach. The pilot will also provide tools to the participants to explore and contribute to existing use cases, co-create new ones, collect and visualise data, as well as evaluate and assess the impact of all these experiments. Citizens will have the opportunity to employ authoritative and auxiliary open data to solve problems deemed relevant to the community and use advanced technological tools to make sense of their own environment or design their own experiments at a later point. These actions can provide useful insights to public administration for interventions and/or policy making.

7.3.3 Turano's GREENGAGE Observatory

Turano's GREENGAGE Observatory as part of the GREENGAGE project will analyse and understand the social and economic dynamics of the Turano Valley territory. During the monitoring activities, particular attention will be paid to several crucial issues that influence the quality of life and development of the community. In this context, particular attention will be paid to the following aspects: The GREENGAGE Observatory will bring together the sparse regional population to explore:

- Mobility data and in particular the analysis of mobility flows
- Infrastructures to support remote working, notably the Internet connection, paying particular attention to the speed and availability of signal or fibre optic cables. At the same time, the GREENGAGE Observatory will examine the coverage of mobile networks and evaluate the impact of electromagnetism, ensuring that working environments are safe for health. The presence of co-working spaces is another central element, with an assessment of their availability, quality, and accessibility. These spaces must offer not only reliable Internet connection, but also ancillary services such as printers, scanners, and refreshment points with Wi-Fi connection. The overall picture will also include analysis of policies and initiatives that support agile working, such as tax incentives and training programmes. It is important to consider the presence of digital tools and collaboration platforms, which can facilitate remote working. Furthermore, attention will be paid to quality-of-life indicators influenced by agile working, such as work-life balance, reduction of commuting and its effect on workers' mental health. The GREENGAGE Observatory will implement data collection mechanisms, such as surveys and feedback from agile workers, to obtain real-time information on their needs, concerns, and suggestions to improve services related to remote working. Finally, relevance will be given to technological innovation and digital inclusion, ensuring that agile working initiatives are accessible and inclusive for all citizens, avoiding digital divides and promoting the participation of all segments of the population. These elements will provide a comprehensive and detailed view of the agile working environment in the city, allowing the identification of improvement opportunities and new initiatives to support a flexible and modern workforce.
- the urban regeneration plan suggested by the "Borghi united for the social and cultural regeneration of the Turano Valley" project, especially in the light of environmental risks and the Do No Significant Harm (DNSH) principles, according to which regeneration activities should not cause severe damage to the environment:
 - a. Presence of asbestos in buildings and soils.
 - b. Characterization of soils and groundwater.
 - c. Degradation risks of the historical-artistic heritage connected to meteorological phenomena and hydrogeological instability.
 - d. Soil fertility and biodiversity including that of the subsoil and the presence of protected habitats and species.

The collected data and their analysis will provide valuable information to support decisions and identify strategies for regeneration with a focus on mobility, environment, and quality of life. Despite other critical issues, mobility is mostly prioritised here based on citizens' preference and due to the opportunity, it will

provide to turn Turano Valley more accessible from neighbouring regions and the capital of Rome, allowing for better and faster connectivity and thus, residential attractiveness.

The aim of Turano's CO is to corroborate the development of more sustainable and efficient transport policies and infrastructures. Sensing data collected from earth and the street through the active participation of citizens will be used to increase the analytical capacity of decision-making regarding mobility and quality of life (Services, Economy, Infrastructure, Environment, Culture, Quality of social and institutional processes).

GREENGAGE Observatory Journey

There are 4 main phases that characterize the Citizen Observatory journey within the GREENGAGE project, namely the:

1. *Activation* phase, which is characterized by stakeholder involvement and engagement, inviting the communities identified in the stakeholder mapping and recruiting them as Citizen Observers
2. *Design and co-creation* phase characterized by the training of Citizen Observers and their involvement in the development of shared participatory activities that relate to critical issues of the natural and built environment as well as the political and societal sectors.
3. *Implementation* phase characterized using tools, methods, and resources from Citizen Observers to collect, analyse and reflect on data. This phase in turn contains 3 sub-phases:
 - a. The first relates to "discovery & sensing", collecting and sharing data using sensors, observations and uploading data to the GREENGAGE sharing platform.
 - b. The second concerns the understanding of data, through meetings and workshops, using in-depth and interrogation tools.
 - c. The third is "innovation", using new and existing data, to define with stakeholders' new points of view that have emerged thanks to the data and prototype potential new services and tools that address problems to improve integrated sustainability.
4. *Celebration* phase features a closing event to illustrate the results achieved, to show the usefulness of datasets to support decisions for the fields of policy, science, and technology and to thank all stakeholders involved for their commitment and contribution.

A transversal activity is represented by the monitoring activity to supervise all planned activities and to make sure that they are carried out as planned.

Expected Impact of Pilot

1. Map out local challenges in intra-municipal commuting, digital infrastructure, and air quality to influence decision-making in relation to mobility, life quality, and residential attractiveness.
2. Build a database that integrates quantitative data through satellites and sensors with qualitative information from surveys, interviews, and focus groups to generate intelligence for regional planning.
3. Collect data on mobility flows and monitor environmental phenomena, like air quality, to support mitigation planning for hydro-geological hazards and extreme atmospheric phenomena.
4. Gather opinions from various stakeholders to draw impactful planning scenarios and formulate suggestions for targeted political decisions.
5. Develop guidelines for the Municipalities of Turano to improve urban and transport planning as well as the quality of life whilst tackling depopulation and promoting cultural and social regeneration.

6. Provide the opportunity to citizens to experience and reflect on their environment in terms of mobility and liveability of the areas based on gathered evidence.

Figure 12: Turano GREENGAGE Observatory Journey.

7.3.4 Governance model

Governance is characterized by the following sets or groupings of actors drawn inside or outside (based on their scale of influence) of the territorial area of the Turano Valley:

Government – constituted by the authorities and institutions that influence the territory and represent the sphere of political influence and that owns the **capital of regulatory knowledge and** (are mentioned here in specify: Borghi Italia which coordinates the pilot, ANCI Lazio, the Lazio Region, the Province of Rieti, ASTRAL the company of the Lazio Region responsible for the Design, Construction, Maintenance, Administrative Management of about 1,500 kilometres of Road Network Regional, and finally, the 16 municipalities or villages located in the Valle del Turano area).

Economic system – represented by local companies and industries, utilities, and any larger companies, national, European, international that may have some influence on the local economic system.

Media/Public – represented by the actors that make up the social and information capital, from local citizens to non-profit associations to citizens' committees, up to the media, local newspapers, as well as tourists and regional, national and international media that can influence the territory.

Educational system – represented by research centres and universities that gravitate in the territory for studies and research and those that may have interest in it at a potential level.

Stakeholders

Stakeholders in the Turano pilot project include:

7. **public institutions:** Turano municipality.
 - **organized groups:** local associations
 - **unorganized groups:** citizens of the Turano municipality, local businesses etc.

Target groups of GREENGAGE Observatories

- **Public Institutions**
 - Policy makers (both civil servants and political representatives) who want to explore the issues of mobility and issues relating to the climate change and wish to increase their skills and services.
- a. **Academia or groups of experts**
 - Universities students and professors that work in the field of regeneration, archaeology, and cultural studies who can benefit from the collection of new data in their research activities.
- **Private enterprises**
 - Local businesses who can use the project results to market their services, better target their clientele, and become more competitive in the regional market.
- **NGOs or other third sector groups**
 - Third sector that seeks visibility and is proactive in solving problems related to mobility, climate, and sustainability in general.
- **Residents (current or prospect)**
 - Citizens of Turano Villages who want to improve mobility and services in the area, become aware of climatic and atmospheric phenomena, and protect the natural environment of the region. Future residents who look to migrate in the area to improve their quality of life.

Figure 13: Situational understanding of collective actors for Turano pilot.

7.3.5 Use Cases

Use case #538: Participatory environmental monitoring

Monitor environmental data such as air quality, noise levels, waste management, etc. in Gerace. Citizens would capture such data using portable sensors; then analyse & visualise them using a shared platform to identify sustainable improvements.

- Measure the concentration of air pollutants such as PM2.5, PM10, NO2, SO2, CO, etc.
- If possible, monitor other environmental parameters such as water quality or other phenomena.
- Recording ambient noise levels in different areas of the pilot.
- Measure the temperature and humidity in various zones.
- Collect data on the presence of biodiversity in parks and green areas.

Use case #578: Mobility Pattern Analysis to determine accessibility to shops, schools, services, and other local amenities

Use techniques such as GPS tracking and to determine routes that citizens take to local amenities and identify improvements. Categorise routes by mode of transport and analyse alternative travel modes.

The analysis of mobility models plays a fundamental role in understanding the dynamics of accessibility within the Turano community. To fully evaluate this aspect, a structured approach is adopted:

- Purchasing 6 months of regional GPS data (Lazio) for flow analysis. This data serves as a basis for understanding commuting patterns and preferences within the community. Measuring distances and travel times between homes and major destinations is critical. A quantitative

analysis will provide valuable insights into the temporal and spatial aspects of accessibility, helping to identify potential bottlenecks or areas for improvement.

- Collecting new data on transport modes, which will allow a large-scale understanding of the mobility patterns within the region. This includes walking, cycling, using a car, public transport and more. This information is fundamental for defining transport policies and infrastructure development.

Beyond quantitative data, qualitative data will give paint a richer picture of the stakes at hand. Collecting citizens' opinions and feedback on the accessibility and use of urban space will help policy makers and planners to adapt their strategies for the future. Specifically, understanding community sentiments will help create targeted interventions aligned with residents' needs and preferences. Tracking the availability and use of parking spaces will facilitate commuting from and to key destinations. Monitoring this information will not only address traffic concerns, but will also inform urban planning strategies, ensuring parking facilities align with community mobility patterns.

Use case #580: Analyse citizens' usage of public spaces and determine attractiveness of public spaces.

Use GPS data and analyse the usage profile of public spaces. Identify spaces that are the most used and the least used during different times of the day.

Other elements that will be taken into consideration:

- Collect data on the number of people using public spaces at different times and days of the week.
- Record the average time people spend in public spaces.
- Collect citizens' feedback on the attractiveness and usability of public spaces through questionnaires, interviews or focus groups.
- Trace the use of facilities such as benches, play areas, walking paths, bikes paths, etc.
- Record events or activities that take place in public spaces and public participation in them

7.3.6 Data Collection Requirements

ID	FR-DC.1
Name	Collect data on road and sidewalks usage (e.g., number of people gathering near shops or other amenities)
Description	Implement a mechanism to collect data on the usage of roads and sidewalks both from people passing by and from people standing in front of shops and other places.
Rationale	Understanding the usage patterns of roads and sidewalks, particularly in relation to areas with high foot traffic near shops and amenities, is essential for urban planning, optimizing infrastructure, and identifying areas for improvement or potential interventions.
Fit criterion	Data accurately represents the usage of roads and sidewalks, including comprehensive information on trip origins and destinations, travel modes (wide diversity should be provided), distances, durations, and accessibility features.
Pre-conditions	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • The system should have access to sensors or devices capable of detecting and counting people in specific areas. • The special areas such as shops or other amenities should be detected and defined.
Post-conditions	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Data on road and sidewalk usage should be successfully collected and stored in the system. • The collected data should be available for analysis and decision-making purposes.

Potential technologies	MODE (AIT), GREENGAGE app (AIT), Portable Devices for environmental data capture (HOPU)
ID	FR-DC.5
Name	Collect real-time GPS data
Description	Capture and collect real-time GPS data to track the location and movements of individuals, vehicles, or assets within the city.
Rationale	Collecting real-time GPS data provides valuable information for various purposes, including transportation planning, traffic management, public safety, and resource allocation. It enables city officials and service providers to monitor and analyse movement patterns, identify congestion points, optimize routes, and make informed decisions based on real-time location information.
Fit criterion	The system should be capable of collecting and recording real-time GPS data accurately. It should capture the location coordinates, timestamps, and any additional relevant information associated with the tracked entities
Pre-conditions	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> The tracked entities (e.g., vehicles, individuals) should be equipped with GPS-enabled devices (mobiles).
Post-conditions	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Real-time GPS data should be continuously collected from the tracked entities. The collected GPS data should include accurate location coordinates, timestamps, and relevant metadata. The data should be accessible for analysis, visualisation, and integration with other systems or applications.
Potential technologies	GREENGAGE app (AIT), Realtime Mapping and Image Analysis (MindEarth)
ID	FR-DC.8
Name	Import historical mobility data
Description	Enable the import of historical mobility data into the system for analysis and visualisation purposes.
Rationale	Importing historical mobility data allows for a comprehensive understanding of past mobility patterns, trends, and behaviours. It facilitates data-driven decision-making, supports urban planning initiatives, and helps evaluate the effectiveness of mobility interventions and policies.
Fit criterion	Availability of imported historical mobility data into GREEN Engine data repository.
Pre-conditions	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Historical mobility data is available in a suitable format for import. The system has the capability to validate the imported data and ensure its integrity.
Post-conditions	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Historical mobility data is successfully imported into the system. The imported data can be combined with real-time or other existing data sources for comprehensive mobility analysis.
Potential technologies	UrbanTEP/VISAT (GISAT)

7.3.7 GREEN Engine tools

Execution of Citizen Observatory campaigns (piloting). Firstly, potential GREENGAGE observers are contacted through a survey on modality use, with an extra question on whether they wish to join a more intensive study of this phenomenon. Such questionnaire can be prepared through Collaborative Environment or indexed in it as part of the GREENGAGE Observatory preparation. Secondly, the voluntary participants are encouraged to take part in gathering GPS tracking data, air-quality data, habits on remote and on-site working, and usage of urban areas. This second phase requires the gathering of data by the GREENGAGE observers, through the following tools:

- **Collaborative Environment (DEUSTO):** This digital environment would be essential for managing the GREENGAGE observers' teams, co-ideating campaign goals, and orchestrating the campaign's different phases. Furthermore, it can be employed to survey and involve users in the extraction of specific information. Surveys can be created, indexed, and shared from it.
- **MODE (AIT):** This technology is a trip recording and mode detection framework. It consists of two main software components: a data recording module for iOS and Android apps and a backend data analysis module. The purpose of the MODE library is to provide the out-of-the-box solution for mobility surveys via smartphone app and web service. It yields high-precision, multimodal mobility data for traffic planning, mobility research, cities, and communities. The most important functionality it provides for GREENGAGE are the routes and used travel mode(s) of users. The MODE library will be integrated into the GREENGAGE App to enable the GREENGAGE observers to track their commuting routes with specific means of transport, thus providing crucial data about transportation patterns.
- **GREENGAGE App (AIT):** This is an adaptation of the previously developed tool – HotCity App. Key idea behind is to provide a universal tool to help engage Citizen Observatories in the research within the scope of the project through completion of Pilot-defined tasks in a comprehensible and gamified manner. Whereas the initial tool had a primary focus on the measuring of the excessive heat signatures of the cities' facilities, the GREENGAGE App version allows for a broader scope of research like visitor density, free-text surveys, route evaluation and overall, POI (Point of Interest) liveability reporting and validation. It can be further used to report obstacles, POIs (high traffic spots, unlit street areas, etc.) or already enhanced area spots (evaluate pre-defined data through self-reporting – to be agreed at a later stage). Moreover, citizen observers can validate those spots (reported by other observers or administrators) to raise the data accuracy and reliability.
- **Realtime Mapping and Image Analysis (MindEarth):** This technology can help map and chart well-used or less popular routes and public spaces to qualify demographics profiles of users (i.e., gender, age-group, social grouping), to further qualify modality choices on a micro scale (i.e., presence of different vehicle types). The tool can also be used to map the environmental quality of streets and places, highlighting elements that might encourage (i.e., benches, water fountains, green elements) or dissuade (i.e., rubbish, absence of sidewalk, street holes) people from taking a certain route or visiting a certain place. Additional analysis includes characterisation of green areas and their usage by citizen.
- **Portable Devices for environmental data capture (HOPU):** Sensor devices with air quality (measuring PM, CO, SO₂, NO₂, O₃, and NO), noise and crowd monitoring capabilities, will be used to analyse the air quality and noise and its impact on the public health. ATMOTUBE devices from Libelium will be useful to measure air quality and to collect detailed data on the levels of air pollutants at specific key points within the city, including fine particulate matter (PM_{2.5}), ozone (O₃), carbon monoxide (CO), carbon dioxide nitrogen (NO₂). Noisecapture app will help monitor noise pollution, building upon the notions of participatory sensing and citizen science. They will be linked to EU Copernicus services.

Collective learning by analysing the Citizen Observatory's data. The gathered data need to be stored, analysed, and visualised. Together with the citizen observers, the quality of the data will be assessed as well as possible dataset connections to further explore the decision process – now more on spatial level. The following technologies can be of use here:

- **Urban TEP/VISAT (GISAT):** Key component of the Urban Thematic Exploitation Platform1 is a web- based Visualisation and Analytical Toolbox (VISAT) provided by GISAT. It allows easy integration of different data, their exploration, visualization and analysis and some collaboration functionalities for data/results sharing. VISAT is based on our Panther technology and current is under major technological upgrade. VISAT functionality is offered to support GREENGAGE activities in a similar role as in UrbanTEP here - to explore and visualise geospatial data related to mobility patterns. By employing this tool, real-time mobility patters may be analysed in real-time and compare them with historical data to extract conclusions about the implemented changes. Visualisation of data shown in Urban TEP can highlight the impact of specific recurring mobility patterns on a larger (environmental) scale.

- **Data Quality and Structure Dashboards (VRVis):** to not just see citizens as data gatherers, co-curating the data and reflecting on its quality can further highlight gaps in the known decision process.
- **Realtime Mapping and Image Analysis (MindEarth):** The collected images would be processed and analysed to extract metrics of interest on number of people of different demographic segments using a specific route or public place in a moment in time or over a specific time window. Factors qualifying environmental quality of the built fabric would also be extracted. Aggregation units could be defined collaboratively with other technology providers to ensure that different data collected by the projects are comparable.

Data-driven policy making and verification (sharing). Reflect on the outcomes of the Citizen Observatory campaign, draw some conclusions and lessons learnt. Consider how these findings could influence and inspire new policies or how those findings are able to validate or refute some policies that have previously been put in place.

- **REENGAGE Toolbox:** open datasets generated, new open-source tools developed, manuals and HOWTOs developed should enrich the catalogue with Citizen Science resources assembled within REENGAGE Academy.
- **REENGAGE Knowledge Assets:** training materials, engagement practices, citizen science resources as part of Citizen Observatories
- **REENGAGE White Book:** the most valuable insights per Citizen Observatory campaign should feed the project's white book.

7.4 Gerace

7.4.1 Background and Context

Gerace is an Italian village in the Province of Reggio Calabria. It extends over 28.6 km² and has 2,399 inhabitants. Near the municipalities of Agnana Calabria, Portigliola i Canolo, Gerace is located 46 km southeast of Vibo Valentia, the largest city nearby and situated at an altitude of 500 metres. It falls under the jurisdiction of the Aspromonte National Park authority.

Recently, the Calabria Region selected the municipality of Gerace to coordinate the Porta del Sole, a Next-generation EU Programme through the National Programme for Recovery and Resilience (NPRR) to regenerate, revitalise and enhance the heritage of Gerace village in support of the objectives of the EU Green Deal for sustainable city regeneration. Its objective is the cultural, economic, and social regeneration of the village by rebranding it as a cultural attraction and based on that, build an economic model that boosts local employment and residential attractiveness. With a budget of 20 million euros, the programme envisages nine interventions which aim at the recovery and enhancement of buildings, at improving the accessibility of the village, and at the provision of tourist, cultural and entertainment services, as well as training and incentives for businesses. All these actions will have an impact not only on Gerace but the entire Calabria Region but also in Italy, as a model of sustainable regeneration. Porta del Sole is to be implemented by 2026 involving citizens in data monitoring following the Do No Significant Harm (DNSH) principle¹.

Socio-political context

Currently, the area is facing the following challenges:

- Gerace (as Turano Valley) is recognised as one of the most beautiful villages in Italy and is coordinated by the association Borghi Più Belli d'Italia. However, the climate change and the accelerated environmental degradation of the recent years due to the hydrogeological instability of Gerace cliff, puts the village at risk of severe damage, even evacuation. In that reason the hydrogeological instability of the Gerace cliff requires strategic planning to guarantee safety and sustainability.
- Preserving historic structures while adapting them to modern needs is a delicate balance, and maintenance costs and restoration efforts represent significant challenges that may be addressed by the ongoing "Porta del Sole" project.
- In Gerace there is an urgent need to revitalize its urban areas not only to preserve the rich historical and cultural heritage, but also to position the municipality as an attractive destination for investments, promoting socio-economic growth. The careful restoration and modernisation of urban spaces will be essential to create an environment that attracts investors and entrepreneurs. By finding a harmonious balance between preserving the city's unique identity and implementing contemporary amenities, Gerace can increase its attractiveness for both residents and businesses. A well-executed urban revitalisation plan will not only attract financial investment but also stimulate job creation and local commerce, contributing to a more dynamic and resilient economy. This transformation would breathe new life into the urban fabric and act as a catalyst for Gerace's overall socioeconomic prosperity, ensuring a sustainable and vibrant future for generations to come.
- At social level, the declining demographic trends pose challenges to supporting local communities, just as the ageing population places a strain on social services and limits the productivity of the workforce. Within the framework of the "Porta del Sole" initiative in Gerace, revitalisation through culture stands out as a pivotal goal. This is a strategic approach to stimulate economic growth via culture, recognising the inherent value of Gerace's cultural heritage. Fostering cultural initiatives, such as events, festivals, and artistic endeavors will serve as a catalyst for socio-economic development. The integration of cultural elements will not only draw tourists but will also contribute to a flourishing local economy.

Goals and Objectives

The vision for Gerace and the Porta del Sole programme is to increase the awareness of the citizens regarding urban regeneration phenomena and how they can contribute to create a robust and sustainable governance model for a small historical preserved village. This mission is further strengthened by the will to align with the ISO 9001 certification requirement which promotes "services

aimed at enhancing, maintaining and recovering the national cultural heritage of memories and monuments, and at promoting tourism in the participating Municipalities".

The future aspirations of the municipality are twofold. On the one hand, it is vital to educate citizens on Gerace's hydrogeological instability considering the historical precedents recorded in the south-eastern part of the region. Based on the elements mentioned above, it is necessary to consider mobility and infrastructure planning issues at a strategic level:

- Developing a global mobility plan for the Gerace area to address the challenges of sustainable mobility and improve connectivity and accessibility for residents and tourists.
- Ensuring the active participation of the community in decision-making processes for collaborative urban planning capable of addressing different needs and preferences.
- Developing policies that promote long-term environmental and social sustainability to preserve the unique characteristics of Gerace.

Part of that education is to improve the residents' ability to analyse the risks of degradation of the natural and built heritage as a result of these phenomena. The analysis will look at the current conditions of the inhabited centre and examine previous interventions carried out to protect the buildings in the village. By acting so timely, Gerace can set up a precedent for the wider region and serve as a model for other municipalities with similar morphological characteristics.

On the other hand, the vision for the "Gerace porta del sole" project favours citizen science and a participatory approach in environmental monitoring. Thus, and at a societal level, the goal is to involve citizens to monitor their environment through various means, advocating for more inclusive and participatory decision-making processes that improve the sustainability and resilience of the community. Upon success, the experiment will allow other remote and rural villages in Italy and Europe to adopt the same governance approach.

Overall, the regeneration of Gerace seeks to achieve:

- Stakeholder engagement.
- Community well-being, improving the quality of life of the community.
- Social cohesion, bringing the community together.
- Economic prosperity, reducing unemployment rates.
- Environmental sustainability, reducing negative impact and promote sustainable practices.
- Physical resilience, by building or renovating existing housing properties and infrastructures and assessing the current state of built environment.

7.4.2 Pilot Specification

The GREENGAGE pilot project will support the municipality of Gerace to create a new local mobility plan, adopt measures against environmental degradation, and improve the quality of life of the local residents, through participatory decision-making processes informed by data and empirical evidence. The objective is to contribute to the sustainable transformation of Gerace into a shared treasure of history, art, culture, and tradition with the help of state-of-the-art technologies and without harming any of its unique natural, built, or social features, according to the DNSH principles.

The pilot project will operate alongside the Porta del Sole programme, supporting it in three ways: firstly, it will provide an implementation strategy for the regeneration, secondly, it will employ citizen science methods in the making, and thirdly, it will help evaluate the success of the Porta del Sole programme through the collection and analysis of data. Since sustainable regeneration is a complex process that involves multiple aspects of social, economic, and environmental sustainability, the collaboration and mutual support of the two projects is necessary.

The GREENGAGE pilot project will deal with both qualitative and quantitative data collected from GREENGAGE observations and official public services, like satellite data, respectively. The available data will increase the decision-making ability of citizens and of local authorities, and their analytical capacity for evaluating and implementing the regeneration process in Gerace. Below are some examples of data that can be used:

Qualitative Data:

- From surveys, interviews, and focus groups with stakeholders, shedding light on the perception of people about the regeneration process.
- Data on community's health, safety, access to services, and overall wellbeing.
- Data on community's sense of belonging, trust, and social connections.

Quantitative Data on:

- Employment rates, income levels, and business growth
- Carbon emissions, energy consumption, and waste reduction
- Constructions, demolitions, and renovations, and the quality of built environment

The data should be analysed and interpreted in the context of the project's goals and objectives, with a focus on identifying areas for improvement and opportunities for future development.

Multiple expertise will be required for this: data science, software development, transport planning knowledge, and most importantly community engagement. Yet, the pilot project will primarily give the opportunity to citizens to: (a) collect and submit high-quality and frequent data; (b) participate in collective, educational and decision-making-oriented activities, such as discussion forums, where they will gain valuable insights for their built environment; and (c) design other relevant experiments and solutions to solve further community problems. Therefore, the GREENGAGE pilot success will be evaluated on both its capacity to engage Observatory participants, as well as its efficiency to collect representative data and generate useful insights and recommendations that will feed into the Porta del Sole regeneration programme.

7.4.3 Gerace's Citizen Observatory

The pilot project intends to support a GREENGAGE Observatory in collecting data about the DNSH indicators so that the community can actively participate in monitoring and evaluating the impact of various regeneration activities and projects in Gerace and hold parties accountable for any negative impacts. The involvement of Observatory participants in the monitoring process can promote transparency and accountability and increase community trust in decision-making processes.

The indicators considered of greatest interest to the community of Gerace relate to its specific contextual conditions and touch upon air quality and water, noise levels, waste management practices, biodiversity conservation and social impacts on local communities. GREENGAGE Observers will monitor and report these indicators through various means, such as surveys, sensor networks and community mapping exercises.

GREENGAGE Observatory Journey

The collection and analysis of the above-mentioned data will be supported by the GREENGAGE methodology of value-added participatory monitoring for territorial governance. The participants of Gerace's GREENGAGE Observatory will:

1. Participate in training activities.
2. Collect data and report values for relevant DNSH indicators intuitively and securely on a bespoke web application (GREENGAGE app).
3. Validate and aggregate reported data, linking them to established KPIs by the PNRR project through a secure and scalable back-end database and in a processing engine.
4. Analyse and visualise aggregated data to generate insights and recommendations to improve the sustainable and inclusive governance system.
5. Engage with collective actions, social network activities, and feedback mechanisms and suggestions to incentivize more citizens to contribute to the data collection.
6. Contribute to generate ideas, suggestions addressed to the sustainable plans and evaluate the compliance of actions with the municipal project planning.

Expected Impact of Pilot

Leverage satellite data and active citizen participation to improve the analytical capacity of the municipality, offering valuable insights on the performance and execution of urban regeneration programmes in terms of environmental sustainability and community well-being:

1. Integrate new data and analysis into the regional open data portal (<https://dati.regione.calabria.it/>).
2. Develop a sustainable mobility plan for the Municipality of Gerace so as the latter serves as a model for sustainable urban regeneration practice.
3. Create guidelines to improve the liveability of the village and increase its attractiveness throughout the year.
4. Create a digital tool for participatory processes to support strategic decisions for urban, transport and environmental planning.
5. Determine important indications on air quality and noise during the regeneration works of the "Porta del Sole" project.
6. Establish a Do No Significant Harm (DNSH) monitoring system to ensure municipal development initiatives follow environmental conservation principles and to prevent environmental damage resulting from planned interventions.
7. Promote community commitment and empowerment, instilling a sense of ownership and enabling citizens to play an active role in decision-making and the shaping of their locality.
8. Ability to demonstrate a set of good practices that can be shared with other municipalities and regions that face similar issues.

Figure 14: Gerace GREENGAGE Observatory Journey.

7.4.4 Governance model

In terms of governance, the "quintuple helix" model was taken into consideration, which enhances the emergence of social innovation, emphasizing and giving dignity and autonomous consideration both to the role played by organized civil society and to that so far less valued of "unorganized or informal civil society" and its role with intelligent specialization and the innovation process within rural territories. Since the pilot activity is concentrated exclusively in the territory of the Municipality of Gerace, a pentagon-shaped graphic representation was chosen to highlight in a simple way the governance proposed according to the five-fold helix model characterized by the following sets of actors:

- **Government** – represented by the authorities and institutions that influence the territory and represent the sphere of political influence and that possesses the **capital of normative** knowledge and have been specifically identified in particular: Borghi Italia which coordinates the pilot, the Province of Reggio Calabria, the Calabria Region, the Municipality of Gerace which manages the project "*Gerace, porta del sole*" funded by PNRR.
- **Economic system – represented by local companies** grouped in informal associations of traders "*Siamo Tutti Ruggero*" and "*Il Borgo Incantato*", by utilities and by any larger companies, national, European, international that may have some influence on the local economic system.
- **Media/Public** – represented by the actors that make up the social and information capital, from the citizens of the territory to the non-profit associations to the citizens' committees present in the territory: "*Leggendo tra le righe*" Association; "*Proloco*" of Gerace (Association promoting local culture and tourism), up to the media, local newspapers ("*City Now*" and "*Lente Locale*"), the National Association "*Touring Club*" which awarded the "*Bandiera Arancione*" to the territory of Gerace and assigned to localities that not only enjoy a valuable historical, cultural and environmental heritage, but are able to offer tourists a quality welcome; as well as tourists and regional, national and international media that can influence the territory.
- **Educational system** – represented by research centers and universities that gravitate in the territory for studies and research and those that may have interest in it at a potential level. In particular, at the local level the nearest structures are the University for Foreigners Dante Alighieri of Reggio Calabria and the University of Mediterranean Studies of Reggio Calabria.

Stakeholders

Stakeholders in the Gerace Urban Regeneration pilot project include:

- Public institutions (Gerace municipality, Calabria region)
- Organized groups (local associations)
- Unorganized groups (citizens of the Gerace municipality, local businesses, etc.)
- Third sector organizations (NGOs) who can benefit from actively participating in the collection and exploitation of data produced within the Citizen Observatory.

Target groups of GREENGAGE Observatories

Through municipal information channels and online platforms, citizens (2,353 inhabitants) will be invited to actively participate in the GREENGAGE Observatory.

- Public Authorities and Institutions:

- Borghi Italia (coordinating the pilot)
- Province of Reggio Calabria
- Calabria Region
- Municipality of Gerace (managing the "Gerace, porta del sole" project funded by PNRR)
- Local businesses:
 - Local companies (especially those in associations like "Siamo Tutti Ruggero" and "Il Borgo Incantato")
 - Utility companies
 - Private enterprises
- Media/Public:
 - Citizens of the Gerace municipality
 - Non-profit associations
 - Citizens' committees (e.g., "Leggendo tra le righe" Association, "Proloco" of Gerace)
 - Local media (e.g., "City Now," "Lente Locale")
- Educational bodies
 - Research centers and universities in the territory (e.g., University for Foreigners Dante Alighieri of Reggio Calabria, University of Mediterranean Studies of Reggio Calabria)
 - Research institutions with potential interest in the area
 - The University of Reggio Calabria and "Università Mediterranea di Reggio Calabria" will be invited to the Citizen Observatory, fostering joint initiatives between academia and the observatory.

Figure 15: Situational understanding of collective actors for Gerace pilot.

7.4.5 Use Cases

Use case #538: Participatory environmental monitoring

Monitor environmental data such as air quality, noise levels, waste management, etc. in Gerace. Observatory participants would capture such data using portable sensors; then analyse & visualise them using a shared platform to identify sustainable improvements.

- Measure the concentration of air pollutants such as PM2.5, PM10, NO2, SO2, CO, etc.
- If possible, monitor other environmental parameters such as water quality or other phenomena.
- Recording ambient noise levels in different areas of the pilot.
- Measure the temperature and humidity in various zones.
- Collect data on the presence of biodiversity in parks and green areas.

Use case #581: Analyse citizens' usage of public spaces and determine attractiveness of public spaces.

Classifying routes based on the mode of transport and analysing alternative travel modes and suggestions for a Sustainable Mobility Plan is recommended. Analysing the use of public spaces by citizens and determining the attractiveness of public spaces can be achieved through the MindView App to identify the most used and least used spaces at different times of the day.

Other elements that will be taken into consideration:

- Collect data on the number of people using public spaces at different times and days of the week.
- Record the average time people spend in public spaces.
- Collect citizens' feedback on the attractiveness and usability of public spaces through questionnaires, interviews or focus groups.
- Trace the use of facilities such as benches, play areas, walking paths, bikes paths, etc.
- Record events or activities that take place in public spaces and public participation in them.

7.4.6 Data Collection Requirements

ID	FR-DC.1
Name	Collect data on road and sidewalks usage (e.g., number of people gathering near shops or other amenities)
Description	Implement a mechanism to collect data on the usage of roads and sidewalks both from people passing by and from people standing in front of shops and other places.
Rationale	Understanding the usage patterns of roads and sidewalks, particularly in relation to areas with high foot traffic near shops and amenities, is essential for urban planning, optimizing infrastructure, and identifying areas for improvement or potential interventions.
Fit criterion	Data accurately represents the usage of roads and sidewalks, including comprehensive information on trip origins and destinations, travel modes (wide diversity should be provided), distances, durations, and accessibility features.

Pre-conditions	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> The system should have access to sensors or devices capable of detecting and counting people in specific areas. The special areas such as shops or other amenities should be detected and defined.
Post-conditions	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Data on road and sidewalk usage should be successfully collected and stored in the system. The collected data should be available for analysis and decision-making purposes.
Potential technologies	MODE (AIT), GREENGAGE app (AIT), Realtime Mapping and Image Analysis (MindEarth)

ID	FR-DC.2
Name	Collect environment data from portable sensors
Description	Deploy portable sensors to collect environmental data such as temperature, humidity, air quality, and noise levels.
Rationale	Gathering accurate and up-to-date environmental data is crucial for monitoring and assessing the quality of the urban environment. Portable sensors provide a flexible and efficient way to collect data across different locations and capture variations in environmental conditions.
Fit criterion	The system should be capable of collecting environment data using portable sensors for various parameters, including temperature, humidity, air quality, and noise levels.
Pre-conditions	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Sensors capable of measuring temperature, humidity, air quality, and noise levels should be available. (Portable?) The sensors should be properly calibrated and configured to ensure accurate data collection. If the sensors are static, the location where they are placed must be carefully chosen.
Post-conditions	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Environmental data, including temperature, humidity, air quality, and noise levels, should be successfully collected from the deployed portable sensors.
Potential technologies	Portable Devices for environmental data capture (HOPU)

ID	FR-DC.5
Name	Collect real-time GPS data
Description	Capture and collect real-time GPS data to track the location and movements of individuals, vehicles, or assets within the city.
Rationale	Collecting real-time GPS data provides valuable information for various purposes, including transportation planning, traffic management, public safety, and resource allocation. It enables city officials and service providers to monitor and analyse movement patterns, identify congestion points, optimize routes, and make informed decisions based on real-time location information.
Owner	Copenhagen, Gerace, North Brabant, Turano, Bristol
Fit criterion	The system should be capable of collecting and recording real-time GPS data accurately. It should capture the location coordinates, timestamps, and any additional relevant information associated with the tracked entities
Pre-conditions	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> The tracked entities (e.g., vehicles, individuals) should be equipped with GPS-enabled devices (mobiles).

Post-conditions	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Real-time GPS data should be continuously collected from the tracked entities. The collected GPS data should include accurate location coordinates, timestamps, and relevant metadata. The data should be accessible for analysis, visualisation, and integration with other systems or applications.
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Potential technologies	GREENGAGE app (AIT)
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ID	FR-DC.7
Name	Import air quality data in different formats (CSV, JSON, etc)
Description	Provide the capability to import air quality data to the GREEN Engine in different formats
Rationale	Supporting multiple data formats allows for compatibility with diverse sources and systems, ensuring comprehensive coverage of air quality data.
Fit criterion	Availability of imported air quality data into GREEN Engine data repository
Pre-conditions	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Available air quality data formats from compatible sources
Post-conditions	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Air quality data successfully imported and accessible within the GREEN Engine data repository
Potential technologies	Data Quality and Structure Dashboards (VRVis), UrbanTEP/VISAT (GISAT)

ID	FR-DC.8
Name	Import historical mobility data
Description	Enable the import of historical mobility data into the system for analysis and visualisation purposes.
Rationale	Importing historical mobility data allows for a comprehensive understanding of past mobility patterns, trends, and behaviours. It facilitates data-driven decision-making, supports urban planning initiatives, and helps evaluate the effectiveness of mobility interventions and policies.
Fit criterion	Availability of imported historical mobility data into GREEN Engine data repository.
Pre-conditions	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Historical mobility data is available in a suitable format for import. The system has the capability to validate the imported data and ensure its integrity.
Post-conditions	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Historical mobility data is successfully imported into the system. The imported data can be combined with real-time or other existing data sources for comprehensive mobility analysis.
Potential technologies	Data Quality and Structure Dashboards (VRVis), UrbanTEP/VISAT (GISAT)

7.4.7 GREEN Engine Tools

Execution of Citizen Observatory campaigns (piloting). Firstly, potential GREENGAGE observers are contacted through a survey on modality use, with an extra question on whether they wish to join a more intensive study of this phenomenon. Such questionnaire can be prepared through Collaborative Environment or indexed in it as part of the Citizen Observatory preparation. Secondly, the voluntary participants are encouraged to take part in gathering GPS tracking data, air-quality data, habits on remote and on-site working, and usage of urban areas. This second phase requires the gathering of data by the Observatory participants, through the following tools:

- **Collaborative Environment (DEUSTO):** This digital environment would be essential for managing the citizen observers' teams, co-ideating campaign goals, and orchestrating the campaign's different phases. Furthermore, it can be employed to survey and involve users in the extraction of specific information. Surveys can be created, indexed, and shared from it.
- **MODE (AIT):** This technology is a trip recording and mode detection framework. It consists of two main software components: a data recording module for iOS and Android apps and a backend data analysis module. The purpose of the MODE library is to provide the out-of-the-box solution for mobility surveys via smartphone app and web service. It yields high-precision, multimodal mobility data for traffic planning, mobility research, cities, and communities. The most important functionality it provides for GREENGAGE are the routes and used travel mode(s) of users. The MODE library will be integrated into the GREENGAGE App to enable the citizen observers to track their commuting routes with specific means of transport, thus providing crucial data about transportation patterns.
- **GREENGAGE App (AIT):** This is an adaptation of the previously developed tool – HotCity App. Key idea behind is to provide a universal tool to help engage Citizen Observatories in the research within the scope of the project through completion of Pilot-defined tasks in a comprehensible and gamified manner. Whereas the initial tool had a primary focus on the measuring of the excessive heat signatures of the cities' facilities, the GREENGAGE App version allows for a broader scope of research like visitor density, free-text surveys, route evaluation and overall, POI (Point of Interest) liveability reporting and validation. It can be further used to report obstacles, POIs (high traffic spots, unlit street areas, etc.) or already enhanced area spots (evaluate pre-defined data through self-reporting – to be agreed at a later stage). Moreover, citizen observers can validate those spots (reported by other observers or administrators) to raise the data accuracy and reliability.
- **Realtime Mapping and Image Analysis (MindEarth):** This technology can help map and chart well-used or less popular routes and public spaces to qualify demographics profiles of users (i.e., gender, age-group, social grouping), to further qualify modality choices on a micro scale (i.e., presence of different vehicle types). The tool can also be used to map the environmental quality of streets and places, highlighting elements that might encourage (i.e., benches, water fountains, green elements) or dissuade (i.e., rubbish, absence of sidewalk, street holes) people from taking a certain route or visiting a certain place. Additional analysis includes characterisation of green areas and their usage by citizen.
- **Portable Devices for environmental data capture (HOPU):** Sensor devices with air quality (measuring PM, CO, SO₂, NO₂, O₃, and NO), noise and crowd monitoring capabilities, will be used to analyse the air quality and noise and its impact on the public health. ATMOTUBE devices from Libelium will be useful to measure air quality and to collect detailed data on the levels of air pollutants at specific key points within the city, including fine particulate matter (PM_{2.5}), ozone (O₃), carbon monoxide (CO), carbon dioxide nitrogen (NO₂). Noisecapture app will help monitor noise pollution, building upon the notions of participatory sensing and citizen science. They will be linked to EU Copernicus services.

Collective learning by analysing the Citizen Observatory's data. The gathered data need to be stored, analysed, and visualised. Together with the Observatory participants, the quality of the data will be assessed as well as possible dataset connections to further explore the decision process – now more on spatial level. The following technologies can be of use here:

- **Urban TEP/VISAT (GISAT):** Key component of the Urban Thematic Exploitation Platform1 is a web- based Visualisation and Analytical Toolbox (VISAT) provided by GISAT. It allows easy integration of different data, their exploration, visualization and analysis and some collaboration functionalities for data/results sharing. VISAT is based on our Panther technology and current is under major technological upgrade. VISAT functionality is offered to support GREENGAGE activities in a similar role as in UrbanTEP here - to explore and visualise geospatial data related to mobility patterns. By employing this tool, real-time mobility patterns may be analysed in real-time and compare them with historical data to extract conclusions about the implemented changes. Visualisation of data shown

in Urban TEP can highlight the impact of specific recurring mobility patterns on a larger (environmental) scale.

- **Data Quality and Structure Dashboards (VRVis):** to not just see citizens as data gatherers, co-curating the data and reflecting on its quality can further highlight gaps in the known decision process.
- **Realtime Mapping and Image Analysis (MindEarth):** The collected images would be processed and analysed to extract metrics of interest on number of people of different demographic segments using a specific route or public place in a moment in time or over a specific time window. Factors qualifying environmental quality of the built fabric would also be extracted. Aggregation units could be defined collaboratively with other technology providers to ensure that different data collected by the projects are comparable.

Data-driven policy making and verification (sharing). Reflect on the outcomes of the REENGAGE Observatory campaign, draw some conclusions and lessons learnt. Consider how these findings could influence and inspire new policies or how those findings are able to validate or refute some policies that have previously been put in place.

- **REENGAGE Toolbox:** open datasets generated, new open-source tools developed, manuals and HOWTOs developed should enrich the catalogue with Citizen Science resources assembled within Green Academy.
- **REENGAGE Knowledge Assets:** training materials, engagement practices, citizen science resources as part of Citizen Observatories
- **REENGAGE White Book:** the most valuable insights per Citizen Observatory campaign should feed the project's white book.

7.5 Copenhagen

7.5.1 Background and Context

Amager Vest is selected as pilot demonstration site for the GREENGAGE project. It is a district in Copenhagen located to the southwest of the city centre on the island of Amager, along the nature reserve of the 'Common'. It is a mixed area that expands over historic working-class neighbourhoods, social housing, but also areas with larger one family houses. Within the last 20 years the district has expanded quite significantly with the addition of Ørestad and Nokken, two new brownfield developments, that apart from adding approximately 25.000 new residents also 25.000 university students and faculty within Law, Humanities, and IT and another 25.000 professionals to new HQs in Ørestad.

Expansions of this magnitude bring stress to the existing infrastructures, most visible within mobility. Although a new metro line and regional train stations connect the area to public transport the old roads maintain historical dimensions where congestion is inevitable. To add to this Amager is located as a bridge between the main road network and new large developments; one is the construction of a new island, Lynetteholm from landfill into the ocean as an expansion of the City of Copenhagen, where 300 large lorries per day add to the congestion and the insecurity for the residents.

Partly from popular uprising coordinated by the Amager Vest Local Council the City of Copenhagen has agreed as part of Budget 2024 to initiate a new paradigm of 'Local Traffic Plans' and include the public in developing these. The assignment of the GREENGAGE project is to support the Amager Vest Local Council to engage citizens in this effort and promote data collection that can support the development of new solutions to the traffic jam which has been imposed on the area.

The overall goals for the new local traffic plan have been defined from the City of Copenhagen:

- reduce CO2 emissions by increasing infrastructure for active travel modes.
- increase road safety and reduce excessive speed.
- limit heavy truck through-traffic in residential areas.

The City Hall plan focusses on including private road owners as the element of public engagement. However, the Local Council of Amager West have upped the ante and expanded the scope to focus much more on climate and behaviour change towards responsible consumption, and cross-sector benefits such as health, social cohesion and more. The main instrument will be the public engagement of all people living, studying, and working in the district by engaging them in collecting traffic data, stories and lived experiences from the consequences of a car centric economy. As such the project will also enact the Copenhagen Climate Plan 2035 and its focus on reducing consumption-based emissions. This effort is rooted in the Local Council's strategies to expand local climate actions. The operational responsibility has been delegated to Miljøpunkt Amager, a local citizen centric NGO with more than 20 years presence in the district. Miljøpunkt Amager is organised as an independent fund but receives basic financial funding from City of Copenhagen and the two Copenhagen districts, situated on the island of Amager.

7.5.2 Pilot Specification

Amager Vest reflects many of the 'roles' urban districts posit. It is a regional economic centre with a high influx of commuters to the area; a residential area with segments at different stages of life; an area with many students studying, living and commuting to. As such it is a micro cosmos of urban dynamics, and the GREENGAGE pilot project will provide an opportunity to offer valuable insights onto local policy that can later be adopted and adapted for other larger settings.

By engaging local stakeholders and citizen observers, the pilot project will utilise a citizen-centric perspective and work across silos. By doing so, it will tackle current political issues that demonstrate little coordination between urban and transportation planning. Case be the areas around train stations whose design is not mainly driven by the objective to improve the quality of commuters' journey but the infrastructural and economic efficiency to combine multiple means of transport into a multi-modal local hub.

Data collection will be an important part of this citizen-centric perspective and will play a role in supporting local democratic dialogue and decision process. It will be carried out by residents,

commuters and other participants of GREENGAGE Observatory in Copenhagen and the initial results will provide locals with insightful information and tools to reflect and comment on the local traffic infrastructure plan for the district of Amager West.

The pilot's use cases will build on previous and existing initiatives in the neighbourhood. The efforts have followed a two-pronged approach. The first is trying to reverse the physical structures that hinders quality of life. This may include from ambitious attempts to have the motorway covered to combat noise and air pollution to smaller-scale initiatives to seek out spaces for greening the urban environment. The second approach evolves around transforming the area into a resilient people-centred area. A few initiatives have tried to identify citizens' needs without solid take up from decision makers. For example, local companies are working together to build a wider consensus on turning the neighbourhood into a Positive Energy District (PED), meaning a sizeable living lab for a climate positive neighbourhood.

7.5.3 Copenhagen's GREENGAGE Observatory

Copenhagen's GREENGAGE Observatory will mediate between residents and commuters to explore and contest the city's dual role as both a residential area and an economic center. It will rely on citizen science methods and live activities like civic gatherings with few selected representative participants to allow for direct participation as a strategy to achieve large-scale engagement and improved data validity.

The overall vision for the GREENGAGE Observatory in Copenhagen is to align urban planning with climate change goals while improving conditions for urban living. This includes transforming local neighbourhoods, like that of Ørestad, into places where people enjoy living, spending time and interacting with others. It seeks:

- To test and investigate if citizen science and crowdsourced data collection can be utilised positively to engage Observatory participants in local democratic dialogues in the pursuit of new solutions towards creating a climate-positive neighbourhood.
- To use data collection to illuminate the existing lived experience and conditions in the neighbourhood as a baseline for generating citizens' ideas as to where to improve the urban layout.
- To use new digital solutions of data collection to understand citizens' needs for mobility, including local, hyperlocal and commuting, as well as access to the city in wider perspectives, and how integration into city planning processes can improve conditions.

7.5.4 GREENGAGE Observatory Journey

The three objectives will be carried out by following these steps:

1. *Prepare the project* - identify key stakeholders who will and can lead the vision for the neighbourhood forward.
2. *Establish a baseline* - utilising access to cutting edge technologies the Greengage project will establish a baseline collected by citizens to document existing living and environmental conditions in a manner where data are trustworthy and verifiable.
3. *Enable a shared dialogue* - feedback loop to the neighbourhood on data and findings that is recognised by main stakeholders. From 'shared dialogue' key actions to follow and monitor are determined.
4. *Plan the implementation* - work to secure financing and political mandate for delivering long-term outcome.

The GREENGAGE Observatory will engage different societal segments representing the current population and professionals in the neighbourhood. Once part of it, the Observatory participants will participate in collecting data, which will then be shared with the community. Data collection will be centred around how the current design of the neighbourhood influences its use and will be augmented with open data from various publicly available sources. The intention is to start a conversation through data that will spur more people to engage in data collection and instigate cross-sector dialogues towards new solutions.

Expected Impacts of Pilot

1. Use participatory data collection to produce a recognised and validated data set as a basis for professional planning and democratic debate.
2. Find new solutions and alternatives to fossil-based socio-economic and environmental functioning of cities.
3. Investigate how digital solutions can be added and instrumentalised as part of local democratic processes.
4. Results from visualisations, and simulations of mobility patterns and environmental conditions (air quality and biodiversity) can inform planning decisions and decision-making processes and help evaluate a sustainable redevelopment process in the city via the new local traffic plan.
5. Provide comprehensive understanding of complex issues, such as mobility patterns and air quality, and how they relate to each other.
6. Create a new open dataset and a series of visualisations and simulations which will be available to citizens and will complement the existing data.
7. Influence the development of local traffic plan to prioritise quality of living, soft mobility, low carbon emissions, and preservation of biodiversity.

Figure 16: Copenhagen GREENGAGE Observatory Journey.

7.5.5 Governance model

There are several partners involved in the pilot project.

1. **City Hall** - The citizens' representative legislative body of Municipality of Copenhagen, governed by a Lord Mayor and 6 deputy mayors. 55 elected members. The relevant deputy mayor is Line Barfod, Mayor of Technical and Environmental Affairs.
2. **Amager Vest Local Council** - Ørestad lies within the district of Amager Vest. An elected local council has local authority, including the mandate to drive the environmental and climate forward. Local Council of Amager Vest delegates (together with the Local Council of Amager East) this responsibility to Miljøpunkt Amager.
3. **OICC, 'Ørestad Innovation City, Copenhagen'** - the companies' resident in Ørestad as well as building Investors are organised in collaboration to increase innovation in new urban solutions, focusing on climate change mitigation.
4. **GFS** - The residential building association is maintaining the part of area that is not under municipal maintenance. GFS coordinates between municipality, investors, and residential building owners. GFS is an amalgamation of all smaller building associations in Ørestad.
5. **Miljøpunkt Amager MPA** - is a community driven NGO focusing on climate and environment, especially to support the city's goals to become climate neutral. MPA is organised as an independent fund with an independent governing board, and receives some partial funding from two local councils, and altruistic funds.

Stakeholders

Key stakeholders in the Ørestad pilot will be fully identified during the project preparation phase. Currently, Ørestad Innovation City has been identified as one of the main stakeholders. This is a collaboration among companies residing in Ørestad to increase innovation in new urban solutions, focusing on climate change mitigation.

7.5.6 Use Cases

Use case #537: Analyse citizens' usage of public spaces and determine attractiveness of public spaces

Use GPS data and analyse the usage profile of public spaces. Identify spaces that are the most used and the least used during different times of the day.

Use case #576: Participatory environmental monitoring

Monitor environmental data such air quality, noise levels, waste management, etc. in Gerace. Citizens would capture such data using portable sensors; then analyse and visualise them using a shared platform to identify sustainable improvements.

Use case #577: Mobility Pattern Analysis to determine accessibility to shops, schools, services, and other local amenities

Use techniques such as GPS tracking and to determine routes that citizens take to local amenities and identify improvements. Categorise routes by mode of transport and analyse alternative travel modes.

7.5.7 Data Collection Requirements

ID	FR-DC.1
Name	Collect data on road and sidewalks usage (e.g., number of people gathering near shops or other amenities)
Description	Implement a mechanism to collect data on the usage of roads and sidewalks both from people passing by and from people standing in front of shops and other places.

Rationale	Understanding the usage patterns of roads and sidewalks, particularly in relation to areas with high foot traffic near shops and amenities, is essential for urban planning, optimizing infrastructure, and identifying areas for improvement or potential interventions.
Fit criterion	Data accurately represents the usage of roads and sidewalks, including comprehensive information on trip origins and destinations, travel modes (wide diversity should be provided), distances, durations, and accessibility features.
Pre-conditions	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> The system should have access to sensors or devices capable of detecting and counting people in specific areas. The special areas such as shops or other amenities should be detected and defined.
Post-conditions	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Data on road and sidewalk usage should be successfully collected and stored in the system. The collected data should be available for analysis and decision-making purposes.
Potential technologies	MODE (AIT), Realtime Mapping and Image Analysis (MindEarth), REENGAGE App (AIT)

ID	FR-DC.2
Name	Collect environment data from portable sensors
Description	Deploy portable sensors to collect environmental data such as temperature, humidity, air quality, and noise levels.
Rationale	Gathering accurate and up-to-date environmental data is crucial for monitoring and assessing the quality of the urban environment. Portable sensors provide a flexible and efficient way to collect data across different locations and capture variations in environmental conditions.
Fit criterion	The system should be capable of collecting environment data using portable sensors for various parameters, including temperature, humidity, air quality, and noise levels.
Pre-conditions	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Sensors capable of measuring temperature, humidity, air quality, and noise levels should be available. (Portable?) The sensors should be properly calibrated and configured to ensure accurate data collection. If the sensors are static, the location where they are placed must be carefully chosen.
Post-conditions	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Environmental data, including temperature, humidity, air quality, and noise levels, should be successfully collected from the deployed portable sensors.
Potential technologies	Portable Devices for environmental data capture (HOPU)

ID	FR-DC.4
Name	Collect ground images of city greenery
Description	Capture and collect ground-level images of city greenery, including parks, gardens, trees, and other vegetation, using appropriate imaging devices or tools.
Rationale	Collecting ground images of city greenery provides valuable visual data to assess and monitor the quality and quantity of urban green spaces. It enables city planners and environmentalists to evaluate the health and condition of vegetation, identify areas in need of maintenance or improvement, and track the impact of green initiatives.

Fit criterion	The system should facilitate the collection of ground images of city greenery. The captured images should accurately represent the green spaces, including their location and the quality of vegetation.
Pre-conditions	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Accessible green spaces and areas with vegetation should be identified and mapped • Platforms that allow geographically map and identify these areas in should be available. • Imaging devices capable of capturing ground images should be available"
Post-conditions	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Ground-level images of city greenery should be successfully collected. • The images should be georeferenced or linked to their respective locations for spatial analysis.
Potential technologies	GREENGAGE app (AIT), Realtime Mapping & Image Analysis (MindEarth)

ID	FR-DC.5
Name	Collect real-time GPS data
Description	Capture and collect real-time GPS data to track the location and movements of individuals, vehicles, or assets within the city.
Rationale	Collecting real-time GPS data provides valuable information for various purposes, including transportation planning, traffic management, public safety, and resource allocation. It enables city officials and service providers to monitor and analyse movement patterns, identify congestion points, optimize routes, and make informed decisions based on real-time location information.
Fit criterion	The system should be capable of collecting and recording real-time GPS data accurately. It should capture the location coordinates, timestamps, and any additional relevant information associated with the tracked entities
Pre-conditions	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • The tracked entities (e.g., vehicles, individuals) should be equipped with GPS-enabled devices (mobiles).
Post-conditions	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Real-time GPS data should be continuously collected from the tracked entities. • The collected GPS data should include accurate location coordinates, timestamps, and relevant metadata. • The data should be accessible for analysis, visualisation, and integration with other systems or applications.
Potential technologies	GREENGAGE App (AIT)

ID	FR-DC.7
Name	Import air quality data in different formats (CSV, JSON, etc)
Description	Provide the capability to import air quality data to the GREEN Engine in different formats
Rationale	Supporting multiple data formats allows for compatibility with diverse sources and systems, ensuring comprehensive coverage of air quality data.
Fit criterion	Availability of imported air quality data into GREEN Engine data repository
Pre-conditions	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Available air quality data formats from compatible sources
Post-conditions	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Air quality data successfully imported and accessible within the GREEN Engine data repository

Potential technologies	Data Quality and Structure Dashboards (VRVis), UrbanTEP/VISAT (GISAT)
ID	FR-DC.8
Name	Import historical mobility data
Description	Enable the import of historical mobility data into the system for analysis and visualisation purposes.
Rationale	Importing historical mobility data allows for a comprehensive understanding of past mobility patterns, trends, and behaviours. It facilitates data-driven decision-making, supports urban planning initiatives, and helps evaluate the effectiveness of mobility interventions and policies.
Fit criterion	Availability of imported historical mobility data into GREEN Engine data repository.
Pre-conditions	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Historical mobility data is available in a suitable format for import. The system has the capability to validate the imported data and ensure its integrity.
Post-conditions	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Historical mobility data is successfully imported into the system. The imported data can be combined with real-time or other existing data sources for comprehensive mobility analysis.
Potential technologies	UrbanTEP/VISAT (GISAT), DIGITWIN

ID	FR-DC.11
Name	Import satellite imagery
Description	Enable the system to import satellite imagery data for the designated area.
Rationale	Satellite imagery provides valuable insights into various environmental aspects, such as land cover, vegetation health, urban development, and natural resource monitoring. Importing satellite imagery allows for the integration of remote sensing data into the system, enabling comprehensive analysis and visualisation of the area's environmental conditions.
Fit criterion	Opening of data exploration project in UrbanTEP with the required datasets loaded
Pre-conditions	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Access to reliable satellite imagery providers or repositories offering imagery data for the desired area. Platform to interpret and make satellite imagery interactive (UrbanTEP)
Post-conditions	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Satellite data is successfully imported into the system. The imported data can be combined with real-time or other existing data sources for comprehensive geographical analysis.
Potential technologies	UrbanTEP/VISAT (GISAT)

7.5.8 GREEN Engine tools

Execution of Citizen Observatory campaigns (piloting). Potential citizen observers are initially contacted through a survey on modality use and then encouraged to participate in a more intensive study. Voluntary participants are motivated to contribute GPS tracking data and to participate in decision-making processes. Local apps and GREENGAGE technology can be utilized for tracking the modality usage and routes, providing insights into the travel patterns.

- **Collaborative Environment (DEUSTO):** This digital environment would be essential for managing the citizen observers' teams, co-ideating campaign goals, and orchestrating the

campaign's different phases. Furthermore, it can be employed to survey and involve users in the extraction of specific information. Surveys can be created, indexed, and shared from it.

- **MODE (AIT):** This technology is a trip recording and mode detection framework. It consists of two main software components: a data recording module for iOS and Android apps and a backend data analysis module. The purpose of the MODE library is to provide the out-of-the-box solution for mobility surveys via smartphone app and web service. It yields high-precision, multimodal mobility data for traffic planning, mobility research, cities, and communities. The most important functionality it provides for GREENGAGE are the routes and used travel mode(s) of users. The MODE library will be integrated into the GREENGAGE App to enable the citizen observers to track their commuting routes with specific means of transport, thus providing crucial data about transportation patterns.
- **GREENGAGE App (AIT):** This is an adaptation of the previously developed tool – HotCity App. Key idea behind is to provide a universal tool to help engage Citizen Observatories in the research within the scope of the project through completion of Pilot-defined tasks in a comprehensible and gamified manner. Whereas the initial tool had a primary focus on the measuring of the excessive heat signatures of the cities' facilities, the GREENGAGE App version allows for a broader scope of research like visitor density, free-text surveys, route evaluation and overall, POI (Point of Interest) liveability reporting and validation. It can be further used to report obstacles, POIs (high traffic spots, unlit street areas, etc.) or already enhanced area spots (evaluate pre-defined data through self-reporting – to be agreed at a later stage). Moreover, citizen observers can validate those spots (reported by other observers or administrators) to raise the data accuracy and reliability.
- **Portable Devices for environmental data capture (HOPU):** Sensor devices with air quality (measuring PM, CO, SO₂, NO₂, O₃, and NO), noise and crowd monitoring capabilities, will be used to analyse the air quality and noise and its impact on the public health. ATMOTUBE devices from Libelium will be useful to measure air quality and to collect detailed data on the levels of air pollutants at specific key points within the city, including fine particulate matter (PM_{2.5}), ozone (O₃), carbon monoxide (CO), carbon dioxide nitrogen (NO₂). Noisecapture app will help monitor noise pollution, building upon the notions of participatory sensing and citizen science. They will be linked to EU Copernicus services.
- **Realtime Mapping and Image Analysis (MindEarth):** This technology can help map and chart well-used or less popular routes and/or public spaces or specific locations to qualify demographics profiles of users (i.e., gender, age-group, social grouping) and to further qualify modality choices on a micro scale. It also can help to identify and annotate elements that may cause disruption in traffic or environmental quality factors that might prevent people from taking a certain route (i.e., rubbish, absence of sidewalk, street holes). Furthermore, the mapping of large numbers of people can help to identify popular places where people with reduced mobility may have problems getting around.

Collective learning by analysing the Citizen Observatory's data. Part of the GREEN Engine usage scenario. During this phase, the collected data is carefully examined, patterns are identified, and the insights derived from these analyses are shared among the citizen observers, data scientists, and other stakeholders. The process allows for comprehensive understanding, engagement, and shared ownership of data-related findings, promoting further discourse on the results.

- **Data Quality and Structure Dashboards (VRVis):** This component helps not only to visualise the data but also to co-curate it, reflecting on its quality and revealing gaps in the decision-making process.
- **Urban TEP/VISAT (GISAT):** Key component of the Urban Thematic Exploitation Platform 1 is a web-based Visualisation and Analytical Toolbox (VISAT) provided by GISAT. It allows easy integration of different data, their exploration, visualization and analysis and some collaboration functionalities for data/results sharing. VISAT is based on our Panther technology and current is under major technological upgrade. VISAT functionality is offered to support GREENGAGE activities in a similar role as in UrbanTEP here - to explore and visualise geospatial data related to mobility patterns. By employing this tool, real-time mobility patterns may be analysed in real-time and compare them with historical data to extract conclusions about the implemented

changes. Visualisation of data shown in Urban TEP can highlight the impact of specific recurring mobility patterns on a larger (environmental) scale.

Data-driven policy making and verification (sharing). Phase where insights derived from the Citizen Observatory campaigns are synthesized to inform and influence policy-making processes. During this phase, the analysed data and conclusions are translated into actionable recommendations that can contribute to the development of new policies or the amendment of existing ones:

- **REENGAGE Toolbox:** open datasets generated, new open-source tools developed, manuals and HOWTOs developed should enrich the catalogue with Citizen Science resources assembled within REENGAGE Academy.
- **REENGAGE Knowledge Assets:** training materials, engagement practices, citizen science resources as part of Citizen Observatories
- **REENGAGE White Book:** the most valuable insights per Citizen Observatory campaign should feed the project's white book.

8 Recommendations for the PILOTING phase and a manual for CO Academy beyond GREENGAGE

The previous chapters discussed the principles the GREENGAGE Innovation Action is based on, how its interdisciplinary collaborations formed the basic infrastructure for the GREENGAGE Academy – although challenges remained – and illustrated the ideal and localised setup and application of the Academy in the context of the five GREENGAGE pilots. These elaborations culminate in this chapter, which provides an initial overview of guiding actions that can be undertaken when initiating the GREENGAGE Academy in different contexts. The chapter drafts a manual for setting up, running and maintaining material and immaterial infrastructures for COs to both facilitate the GREENGAGE’s PILOTING phase in WP5 as part of the Innovation Action itself, and when setting up COs beyond the lifetime of the project. **Although the recommendations are inspired by and intended to better shape the GREENGAGE PILOTING phase, the aspiration is for them to also serve as recommendations for the operationalisation of other COs outside the project.**

Given the rationale of this deliverable and considering insights from COLLECTIVE LEARNING, the recommendations compiled below consist of implications to consider whilst co-creating and operating COs during the PILOTING phase of the GREENGAGE project (WP5). Thanks to the situated experimentation approach, these implications are inherently informed by the specific context of the GREENGAGE pilots and are thus fit for the situation in each of them. In fact, they are based on concrete recommendations for changes from GREENGAGE partners who participated in the survey that was introduced in Chapter 5. The diverse perspectives and roles of the respondents provide agile pointers for the preparation and performance of the GREENGAGE CO activities during PILOTING.

Despite the contextual inspiration behind these recommendations, this chapter also sees them as guidelines that could be relevant for any Citizen Observatory wishing to adopt and test the concept of GREENGAGE Academy beyond the project. Being specific to GREENGAGE does not deprive them for working as general recommendations.

It should be noted that this process of inductive generalisation is still very much a work in progress and by no means intends to be exhaustive at this point. It will be elaborated further in WP5, when PILOTING and COLLECTIVE LEARNING will be put in practice and more evidence will be collected from the operationalisation of COs. In fact, as part of WP5 activities, the IAB will organise, complement, validate and prioritise these recommendations and coordinate ad hoc working groups responsible for editing and/or adding necessary recommendations. GREENGAGE-specific PILOTING activities can help the IAB to gain insights on how to better monitor the performance of GREENGAGE Observatories, but also COs in general across all levels of governance.

8.1 Performing an organisational structure

The GREENGAGE Academy uses two organisational structures, an IAB team and five PSTs to oversee the Innovation Action. The recommendations below pertain to how these structures can be better organised between and across them. **These are recommendations for changes so that a) the IAB can ensure collective action towards GREENGAGE Innovation and b) PSTs can enable an ongoing and aligned understanding of the pilot specific situations.**

- To avoid overwhelming the Pilots, set up regular/periodic PST meetings with each pilot to ensure availability and responsiveness. These meetings should always function according to the following principles:
- Use an agreed upon communication channel.
- Follow a carefully curated agenda of topics and issues to practically facilitate the PILOTING and avoid overwhelming deviations.
- Follow a clear decision-making process – clarify who has the final say.
- Concrete activities should be allocated in detail immediately (responsible partner, deadline, rationale, and link to WP tasks).

- The goal and function of the PST should be clarified to the Pilot owners early on so that they know what issues to bring to which project board. Currently the PST supports implementation in the PILOTING phase through action-driven tasks.
- Put the responsibility on Pilot owners to reach out to their PSTs to clarify issues. Setting monthly or quarterly milestones for PSTs can be another way to keep them active during Piloting phase.
- PST members of specific Pilots should be aware of the concrete tools possibly used by the pilots as well as the resources available to prevent abstract discussions.
- Share the preparation and moderation of PSTs between technological and engagement partners, depending on the issues discussed.
- The build-up of a PST can change over time. After setting up the pilot planning, the technological infrastructure and the theoretical grounding, new members can be added to the PST team who will be responsible for executing the COs with the Observatory participants on the ground (e.g., data scientists supporting the analysis and interpretation of the air pollution data with the Observatory participants in their local language, technical supporters being on location and having a first walk with the citizens, telling them about do's and don'ts)

8.2 Setting up communication standards for Pilots' GREENGAGE Observatories

The Innovation Action relies on the deployment of pilots to run GREENGAGE Observatories. To ensure this practical application is made possible, some agreements should be made about the communication standards. **These are recommendations to make the information flow more efficient and practically applicable:**

- The practical application of each introduced resource should be discussed and facilitated in an intervention plan that details its use in a GREENGAGE Observatory with Observatory participants and other stakeholders. What a Knowledge Asset, a tool or interaction platform can be used for should be always clear. This includes both the technologies offered, as well as other communication means (such as the data visualisation capabilities of GREENGAGE)
- The Train-the-trainers phase focuses on preparing the pilot owners to be able to support GREENGAGE Observatories on the ground with tasks like surveys, data collection, analysis, and visualisation, design of a use-case etc. However, an interpretation and adaptation of training materials and Knowledge Assets should take place before the second phase of Train-the-Observatory-Participants to allow for a more efficient and practically applicable communication.
- For both Train-the-trainers and Train-the-Observatory-Participants phases, training and co-creation resources should include practical and hands-on and tailored manuals for tools, methods and strategies with hands-on exercises that cater to different participants of GREENGAGE Observatories with different levels of expertise and digital literacy.
- With the focus on the practical application in pilots, reporting and learning are secondary concerns that should not dominate activities (i.e., focusing on writing documents instead of PILOTING).
- A clear overview of binding decisions and methodological suggestions regarding the GREENGAGE Observatory functioning should be presented. Specifically, the freedom of pilots to decide whether they want to apply their GREENGAGE Observatories in a living lab approach or if multiple manifestations are possible should be clear.
- Ensure a resource management structure that is organised for Pilots' GREENGAGE Observatories, instead of adhering to the project WP structure.
- Ensure the GREENGAGE documentation conveys key information and takeaways so that it is accessible for different partners and insightful rather than being only a reproduction of the whole discussion.

8.3 Using existing digital collaboration platforms for partners

We understand that there are at least two different kinds of knowledge assets that we are creating: those about the GREENGAGE Innovation Action as such and those that are located in the different GREENGAGE Observatories. **The following recommendations are targeting a purposeful use of digital platforms for co-creating these assets:**

- The use of tools should be based on actual planned activities and on what tools are available. The materials for COs should be created accordingly.
- Raw assets will be generated through GREEN Engine (datasets, data pipelines, applications and discussion forums, e.g., discourse) and analogue ways of sourcing data (e.g., workshops, forums and informal face-to-face interactions) during PILOTING. There must be a suitable pipeline to transform these raw assets to knowledge assets.
- Specific platforms for co-creation should be identified. Miro boards proved effective due to its collaborative and associative interfaces. Miro was used for coordinating co-creation between the consortium partners and different boards for different pilots can also be used for coordinating amongst PSTs.
- Besides Miro, Figma whiteboards were also used for the GREENGAGE website co-creation before its deployment in WordPress. The tool might remain a useful tool for the partners to visualise ideas and organise workflows between PILOTING (WP5) and project communication strategy (WP7).
- Note that although digital tools help facilitate brainstorming and information exchange across the consortium partners, some of them may require licensing or specialised user knowledge. Therefore, it is worth checking available funding in the project and expertise in the partnership to ensure the tools continue facilitating collaboration.

8.4 Structuring co-creating during the Innovation Action and beyond

The GREENGAGE Innovation Action itself functions as a co-designed living lab as well. To organise a project as such requires coordinating the co-creation of CO-related knowledge assets and the following suggestions are recommended:

- Regular awareness raising (or SCRUM) meetings could help to bring the multidisciplinary partners in a co-creative project up to speed.
- The coordination of co-creation between the consortium partners during the PILOTING phase needs be done first with those who play coordination roles in the various WPs and for the pilots. Such a preliminary coordination efficiently provides a baseline to structure other co-creative meetings by and makes it possible to fully exploit diversified skills based on the actual availability of expected person-months, helping to develop more complete and innovative solutions.
- WP coordinators should plan targeted meetings with key representatives (of both social science and technology partners, when needed) using plenary meetings for sharing of ideas and discussing ongoing challenges. Early planning and alignment of project partners' complementary knowledges and skills can optimise the allocation of funding, time and expertise.

8.5 Monitoring the situation of the pilots

- During the PREPARING phase, the situation of the pilots was gauged through the Situational Screening Questionnaire (see Chapter 5). **To keep this information up to date, the following recommendations should be considered:**
- A Situational Screening Questionnaire and analysis should be performed multidisciplinary when setting up the CO, but also after running its first iteration and before launching full-scale piloting.
- The analysis of this questionnaire should be used to update existing pilot specifications (in PST meetings for instance) to identify and communicate crucial information directly linked to concrete actions of GREENGAGE Observatories.

- Pilot specifications change throughout PILOTING. This is because 'the situation of pilots' is an everchanging reality and an interpretation of that through the lenses of a team of multidisciplinary partners. An ongoing focus on how the GREENGAGE Observatory practices change the situation will be needed to demonstrate the processual nature of governance change based on discursive interventions performed through transdisciplinary knowledge co-creation.
- Continuous feedback on the perceived changes should be gathered from the actors involved in PILOTING in the context of GREENGAGE Observatories, such as the members of PSTs who are part of knowledge co-creation.
- PSTs should screen the public and social media communications during PILOTING to understand the impact of GREENGAGE Observatories on public discourse. This requires an orientating set of pointers and questions, but the actual discussion of this screening should be performed verbally as the quality differs from textual responses.
- Frequent situational analyses of the pilot related changes driven by the GREENGAGE Observatories are a valuable knowledge asset for reflecting, validating and demonstrating the impact of the pilot. Suggested moments are (1) at the beginning of a GREENGAGE Observatory activity and (2) after its completion. If the activity takes over a prolonged period of time (e.g., campaign), an intermediate screening is required to evaluate if any changes in the pilot situation may affect the completion of the activity.
- To make situational analyses more effective, a dissemination and implementation plan of the results is required. These should focus firstly on properly communicating and updating PST teams and all partners involved in the support of CO-related activities. Secondly, PSTs should revisit the pilot planning, technologies, impact assessment criteria, and journey and adapt practical details wherever necessary. For example, adjusting goals and aims (if needed), identifying relevant actors for specific activities, identifying possible indicators, and identifying opportunities to engage politically.
- The PST leads should report any updates for their specific pilots on monthly basis and whenever there are significant changes in the situation. Ideally, these updates can be logged in living documents or create custom trackers in Planio, in order to assign actions to specific partners to respond to the situation.
- The IAB is to support the interdisciplinary creation of a situational screening tool and to coordinate the collective learning across the pilots.

8.6 Gathering and analysing information in and about the pilots

The project's localised approach to GREENGAGE Observatories focuses on gathering, analysing, visualising, and interpreting data through citizens' engagement to inform decision making regarding pressing environmental challenges. Yet, information collection and analysis are also required to support the functioning of GREENGAGE Observatories and their role in shaping policy making even after the end of the project. An interest is placed on data not only collected in the pilots but also about the pilots. The following aspects should be considered when gathering and analysing information about the situation in pilots:

- The Situational Screening Questionnaire can be enhanced by integrating in-system statistics, short interviews, surveys or automated sentiment analysis which may provide more insightful updates on the progress of GREENGAGE Observatories and overall response of Observatory participants.
- For each data-gathering technology in the GREEN Engine, begin collecting in-situ data and use the available results to make further considerations and pilot support strategies, early in the process.
- Study the commonalities between pilots despite situational differences through thematic co-explorations and use cases. Commonalities and differences will increase during PILOTING, due to the interactions between pilot owners, the core group, citizen observers, stakeholders and technological solutions while performing concrete practices of collective research and attempting to influence policy frames.

- A joint analysis across pilots illustrates the extent of different contexts and specific dynamics in which COs can take place. These aid replication and upscaling of localised CO strategies.
- Problem solving techniques from the computational thinking domain can abstract and model generalised and specialised aspects of pilots.
- Interpretative social sciences methods (such as Grounded Theory, Discourse Analysis) can use abductive reasoning to abstract and compare situated, mixed-methods generated data sets, likely to be gathered across pilots.

8.7 Delivering existing and creating new pilot-specific KPIs

GREENGAGE Innovation Action is also concerned with delivering, changing, updating and adding new pilot-specific KPIs during the PILOTING phase. To achieve KPIs remain relevant for the pilots, certain considerations are recommended:

- Update the project risk assessment document according to potential risks identified from the Situational Screening Questionnaire or other assessment tools.
 - Track the adaptation and usage of technologies and technological interfaces like GREEN Engine to ensure that their use, updates with customised features and actual implementation serve the purposes of each pilot.
 - Changing conditions in a pilot are bound to affect not only the delivery of pilot-specific KPIs, but also the metrics employed to achieve them. By communicating clearly precise KPIs and pathways for their measurement in advance of CO activities, monitoring can remain transparent, agile and targeted.
 - KPIs should be SMART:
 - **S**pecific
 - **M**easurable
 - **A**chievable
 - **R**elevant
 - **T**ime-bound
- for each pilot situation. This will address the risk of over-reporting and monitoring activities taking too much time for pilots in this phase.
- Safeguard the feasibility of requested KPIs during the registration of COs. Some pursued KPIs such as disability, deprivation or ethnicity are sensitive, and may deter participants from registering when asked at an early stage. These KPIs should be measured through alternative channels or during other GREENGAGE Observatory activities.
 - Registration forms should gather the maximum amount of information required by the KPIs, while being sensitive of deterring KPI information.
 - Regular assessment and adjustments to KPIs should be organised during the PILOTING phase and ongoing GREENGAGE Observatory activities.

The following recommendations are applicable in case new KPIs need to be created as a result of GREENGAGE Observatory activities at the exploration stage.

- KPIs should be added through dialogue with citizens working in localised GREENGAGE Observatories
- Adding new KPIs during GREENGAGE Observatories activities can be facilitated by WP6 members taking part in PST discussions, in order to ensure the coherence within the general GREENGAGE framework.
- Similar to existing KPIs, new KPIs should also adhere to the SMART principle, explained above.

The abovementioned recommendations provide a work in progress guideline to the application and exploitation of the resources available in the GREENGAGE Academy. While some recommendations specifically deal with the PREPARING phase, others are anticipating the PILOTING phase. These latter recommendations can still be updated during WP5 as they are dependent on the sustained interaction with Observatory participants and other stakeholders. Regardless, these guidelines will help roadmap the possible applications of the GREENGAGE Academy in and beyond the GREENGAGE Innovation Action.

9 Conclusions

As a theoretical, practical and ethical environment, the GREENGAGE Academy enables the creation, dissemination and application of situated understandings on opportunities and challenges for local governance and policy innovation, and fosters cultures of knowledge development and exchange within and across different communities and localities. Its main objective is to ensure that GREENGAGE Knowledge Assets will be widely available to aid co-production of thematic co-explorations arranged within Observatories, enabling thus capacity building for situated, community-led performances of Green Deal objectives.

The deliverable provided a theoretical framework for GREENGAGE Academy, situating GREENGAGE Innovation Action and GREENGAGE Observatories in the wider discourse arena, especially in the context of EU Green Deal and the field of citizen science and public engagement. It also introduced the idea behind its conceptualisation and the development of its role and integration into the whole GREENGAGE project and GREENGAGE Observatories' living labs. The highlight of the deliverable is the implementation of the GREENGAGE Academy in the context of the GREENGAGE pilots, but also the effort to generalise main lessons learned so far to inform both the next stages in the project as well as to start putting together the GREENGAGE White Book as one of the legacies beyond GREENGAGE.

Currently, the GREENGAGE Academy has two interfaces or dimensions. The **GREENGAGE Knowledge Base** (including training materials, tool manuals, reports etc) published at the GREENGAGE website makes one dimension of the GREENGAGE Academy which is accessible for the wider public. The **GREENGAGE Collaborative Environment** (CE) together with the GREENGAGE Toolbox and GREENGAGE Knowledge Assets make the other dimension of the GREENGAGE Academy which is accessible for the onboarded and trained participants of GREENGAGE Citizen Observatories. This latter dimension is driven by the GREEN Engine (suite of community, co-production process and data workflow management tools comprising the whole GREENGAGE platform) which is hosted by two of the partners, DEUSTO (responsible for the layer of community and process management) and VRVIS (responsible for the layers of data capture, storage, analysis and visualisation) and, therefore, only accessible when already being part of a GREENGAGE Observatories' community. Whilst the CE works to support the objective of co-producing thematic co-explorations and applying knowledge assets interdependently to support GREENGAGE Observatories in data collection, analysis and visualisation, it also enables producing further knowledge assets to be published on the Knowledge Base.

This way the GREENGAGE Academy acts as a true collaborative and interaction platform. On the one hand, it engages partners, citizens, and stakeholders as part of the GREENGAGE project to address environmental challenges and inform policy innovation. On the other hand, it brings the project, its activities, actors, and outcomes closer to the wider public by ensuring a constant, open and two-directional channel of communication and exchange with it and by providing a strategy for replicating the idea behind GREENGAGE Academy to other relevant projects, initiatives or action research.

Next steps

This deliverable announces the end of WP3 and the official kick-off of WP5 which will focus on PILOTING phase of GREENGAGE project and full campaigning. As the aftermath of this deliverable, next steps include: (1) to successfully implement GREENGAGE Innovation Action in each pilot; (2) to keep track of the adopted guiding actions that enable the operationalisation of GREENGAGE Observatories; (3) to ensure feedback loops are feeding into COLLECTIVE LEARNING; and (4) to assess the impact and effectiveness of the GREENGAGE Academy as a theoretical, practical and ethical framework and enabling environment during PILOTING, especially as far as running and maintaining GREENGAGE Observatories are concerned. The above steps and their outcomes and reflections will nourish and contribute to the culture of knowledge development and exchange, initiated with this report.

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